

The Australia Telescope 20 GHz Survey and the Search for Young Radio Galaxies

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Abstract

Radio sources with a gigahertz-peaked spectrum (GPS) are thought to be the progenitors of large-scale radio galaxies, with the youngest sources having spectral peaks at the highest frequencies. These young radio galaxies are under-represented in current radio surveys as their peak emission is at frequencies higher than those of the surveys. The declining density of radio sources seen at higher frequencies means that large areas of sky are needed to capture statistically significant numbers of these sources. However, large-area surveys at high frequencies have until now been prohibitive in their required observing time.

A recent survey using the Australia Telescope Compact Array, and a custom-built Wide Band Analog Correlator has drastically reduced the required observing time and made it possible to conduct a high-frequency radio survey that covers the entire southern sky – the Australia Telescope 20 GHz Survey (AT20G). The AT20G provides spectral information at 5, 8, and 20 GHz for ~ 4000 sources, and is thus an rich source of potential young radio galaxies.

In this thesis I describe the development and implementation of the AT20G hardware, the observational techniques, and the calibration and data reduction process for the AT20G survey scanning observations. I describe and present a catalog of sources from the AT20G scanning survey which complements and extends the AT20G follow up source catalog of Murphy et al. (2010).

This thesis also describes the identification and investigation of peaked-spectrum radio sources, with particular interest in the high frequency GPS population with spectral peaks above 5 GHz.

The organisation of this thesis is as follows: In chapters 1 and 2 I give some historical and theoretical background to radio surveys and active galaxies, Chapter 3 presents the technical aspects of the AT20G survey as well as the scanning survey catalog, Chapters 4–6 present an identification and investigation of candidate GPS sources from within the AT20G. A summary of this thesis is given in chapter 7.

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`#Based on code by Tara, adapted by me`

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Declaration of Originality

This thesis contains no material which has been presented for a degree at this or any other university, and, to the best of my knowledge and belief, contains no copy of paraphrase of work published by another person, except where duly acknowledged in the text.

Chapter 5 is a reproduction of a paper published in the Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society in collaboration with other authors. To the best of my ability the contribution of co-authors and collaborators has been outlined at the beginning of each chapter so that a distinction can be easily made between the work that is my own and that which is otherwise.

Paul Hancock

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Publications

Included as part of this thesis:

e-VLBI observations of GHz-peaked spectrum radio sources in nearby galaxies from the AT20G survey **P. Hancock**, S. Tingay, E. Sadler, C. Phillips, and A. Deller; 2009 *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, Volume 397, Issue 4, pp. 2030-2036.

[This paper is presented as Chapter 5 and the contributions of the co-authors is outlined in the preamble.]

High frequency GPS sources in the AT20G survey **P. Hancock**; 2009 *Astronomische Nachrichten*, Vol.330, Issue 2, p.180.

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Other Publications:

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Chapter 1

Active Galactic Nuclei

Preamble

In this chapter I outline the observed properties and current understanding of the relevant physics behind active galactic nuclei (AGN), which make up a large fraction of the sources detected in the AT20G survey. A sub group of AGN are the radio sources which possess a gigahertz peaked spectrum (GPS). An outline of GPS sources is also given as they are of particular interest to later work.

1.1 Setting the scene

Astronomy is arguably the oldest science, but it was not until the early 1800s that the measurements of Herschel's "calorific rays" led to what is now infrared astronomy, and opened up new areas of the electromagnetic spectrum. In 1933 Karl Jansky was investigating sources of radio "noise" at 20 MHz and discovered that there was an extra terrestrial source that seemed to coincide with the sun. Further investigation and comparison with astronomical maps revealed that the source of the radio emission was co-incident with the constellation of Sagittarius, in the center of the Milky Way (Jansky, 1933). Thus began the field of radio astronomy. Jansky's observations have inspired many others to build radio receivers and has opened our eyes to a more complex and fascinating universe than we had ever before imagined. One of the first people to take Jansky's work further was Grote Reber who, in 1937, built a radio telescope in his back yard and conducted the first ever survey of the radio sky (Reber, 1944). The radio frequency map of Reber showed emission from the Galactic plane, with the strongest peak towards the galactic center, and minor peaks in the direction of Cygnus, Cassiopeia, and Canis major, with a minimum in the direction of Perseus. Had Reber been able to observe the southern skies he would have noted maxima in the direction of Centaurus. The Sun was also seen as a source of radio emission.

Since the peaks of Reber's map were all within the extent of the Milky Way, as seen by optical telescopes, it was initially thought that they were of stellar origin. However, a normal star such as our sun has a measured radio brightness that is about 20-30 magnitudes fainter than the emission from the Galactic Center. Therefore the radio emission was either being produced by some exotic radio stars that are radically different from our sun or some other source all together. In 1949 Bolton et al. used a sea interferometer to determine accurate radio positions for Centaurus A and Virgo A and identify them with the galaxies NGC 5128 and NGC 4486 (M87). This was the first time that radio sources had been identified with optical galaxies and led to a new class of objects called radio galaxies. The maxima in the radio map of Reber were later identified with: The center of the Milky Way (Sagittarius A), one of the most powerful radio galaxies 3C405 (Cygnus A), a supernova remnant (Cassiopeia A), and a large H-II region (Sharpless 310 in Canis Major) (Bolton et al., 1949). The radio source Cygnus A was observed by astronomers at Jodrell Bank, Cambridge, and Sydney and although the telescopes were not able to resolve the source, the three observations were enough to be able to predict that the source of the radiation was in fact two lobes of radio energy separated by 1.5 arcmin (Jennison & Gupta, 1953).

1.2 Introduction to AGN

A galaxy with a central region which produces emission in excess of that which can be accounted for by stellar processes is said to have an active galactic nucleus (AGN). The excess emission can be present in nearly any waveband from the radio to X-ray. The source of energy for this excess emission is ultimately the gravitational potential of the central super massive black hole (Urry & Padovani, 1995). The fact that all massive galaxies in the nearby universe possess such a central super-massive black hole implies that all massive galaxies have hosted an AGN at some time in the last 13 billion years, making them an important part of galaxy evolution (Goulding & Alexander, 2009). In many cases the brightness temperature of the excess AGN emission is far too high to be isotropically emitted and there is a lot of evidence to suggest that some components

of AGN emission are highly anisotropic. The cause of the anisotropic emission is generally either obscuration by a dusty disk or torus (Sanders et al., 1989; Pier & Krolik, 1992), or relativistic beaming (Maraschi et al., 1992).

There are various types of AGN, classified according to their luminosity, variability, or spectral characteristics. The most common distinction is made between radio-loud and radio-quiet AGN based on the ratio of radio and optical power (Kellermann et al., 1989). The next most common AGN distinction is based on their optical spectra. Type I AGN have bright continuum emission with broad (Δv of a few thousand kms^{-1}) emission lines, whilst Type II AGN have a weak continuum and only narrow (Δv of a few hundred kms^{-1}) emission lines. Intermediate AGN with broad and narrow lines, are sometimes referred to as Type 1.5. The most variable and active AGN are sometimes called Type 0 AGN but are more often named by other properties (BL-Lac, QSO, etc.).

The many different types of AGN were discovered independently and described separately and a single object may often fall into more than one class of AGN. For instance, Antonucci & Miller (1985) found that the polarised spectrum of a Seyfert type 2 galaxy showed broad lines typical of a Seyfert type 1 galaxy. Barthel et al. (1989) noted that a radio loud type 0 AGN could be the same as a type 1 or 2 AGN when viewed from a different angle.

The increasing amount of overlap of the characteristics of the various types of AGN led to the idea that the AGN may be better understood via a unified model. For an in depth description of the history of AGN see Shields (1999). The unification model for radio loud and radio quiet AGN is described in detail by Urry & Padovani (1995) and Antonucci (1993). An overview is presented here.

1.3 Unified model

Although the unified model is capable of describing many of the observed characteristics of AGN, it is simplistic and modifications need to be made (eg, Kondratko et al., 2005). In particular the unification model does not include factors that are important to the development of an AGN and its host galaxy, such as: age, co-evolution, merger and interaction history, and feedback between AGN activity and star formation. The unified model is none the less a good basis for which to begin the investigation of the underlying physics of AGN.

The unified model has six main features, each of which plays an important role in the observational characteristics of an AGN. These features are shown in figure 1.1, and are: 1) A central massive black hole, 2) An accretion disk, 3) Gas Clouds, 4) An obscuring torus, 5) A relativistic jet, and 6) Viewing angle.

1.3.1 The black hole

To generate the vast amounts of energy observed in AGN, within the small scales implied by variability arguments, requires an accreting super-massive black hole. Black hole accretion is the most efficient mechanism by which energy can be produced, converting up to 40% of the rest

Figure 1.1 : **Left**: The main components of the unified model. **Right**: The effect that viewing angle and the existence of a relativistic jet has on the classification of the active galaxy. Image credit M.Polletta

mass energy of the infalling matter into kinetic and thermal energy (Narayan & Quataert, 2005). Finding enough matter for the black hole to accrete is not a problem as the host galaxy has an almost unending supply of stars and, in spirals, a large amount of gas and dust from the ISM (Shlosman et al., 1990). The real difficulty in fueling an AGN is that for matter to fall into the black hole it must lose most of its angular momentum. A gravitational interaction with another galaxy provides one mechanism by which angular momentum may be removed from in-falling matter and thus help fuel the AGN. It is for this reason that galaxy interactions are thought to play a major role in the evolution of AGN. Meier (2002) (also Rees et al. (1982) and Wilson & Colbert (1995)), suggests that fast spinning black holes produce radio loud AGN, while more slowly spinning black holes produce radio quiet AGN. However, X-ray evidence (Elvis et al., 2002) suggests that the majority of super massive black holes are rapidly spinning. The evolution of a black hole within an AGN is not well understood and the difference between radio loud and quiet AGN may be more complicated.

1.3.2 The accretion disk

A large amount of the radiation seen in AGN is emitted from the accretion disk (Magorrian et al., 1998). As a black hole accretes matter from nearby gas and dust clouds, matter flows toward it from many different directions. Eventually there will be so much matter flowing toward the black hole that the in-falling matter will collide and lose some kinetic energy to friction. The loss of kinetic energy will cause the inner region of gas to heat up and fall closer to the black hole. Temperatures of the in-falling gas can exceed 10^5 K, and can outshine the host galaxy by five magnitudes despite being only about 0.01-0.1pc in diameter. As the gas falls inward angular

¹By comparison Hydrogen burning in a stellar core liberates only about 0.8% of the rest mass energy

momentum must be conserved and so a disk or torus usually results in the same plane as rotation of the progenitor gas clouds. Misalignment between the AGN accretion disk and the plane of the host galaxy supports the idea that galaxy mergers play an important role in the fueling of AGN. The accretion disk will spread out as the inner material transfers angular momentum to the outer material (Balbus & Hawley, 1998). It is also possible that the accretion disk is coupled to a magnetic field which can produce a torque on the disk and remove angular momentum. It has also been suggested that a spinning black hole can heat the inner parts of the accretion disk via magnetic fields that pierce its surface (Wilms et al., 2001). The accretion disk is a source of thermal emission and can be seen in radio, optical, UV and X-ray emission via inverse-Compton scattering from the accretion disk corona (Zhang & Cheng, 1997). The accretion mechanism in some AGN may be more complicated than this simple disk (eg, Frank et al. (2002)).

1.3.3 The gas clouds

A source of the in-falling material are two groups of gas and dust clouds. The first group of clouds is between 0.01 and 1 kpc from the black hole and have small velocity dispersions (Augusto et al., 2001). The continuum emission from the accretion disk photo-ionizes these clouds which then produce emission lines. The low velocity of these clouds presents itself in the narrow line widths of this emission. These clouds make up the narrow line region (NLR) and act as a scattering medium to produce the polarized component of the AGN emission. The second group of clouds are much closer to the black hole (~ 1 pc) and accretion disk and subsequently have much higher velocity dispersion (Gaskell, 2009). These clouds are photo-ionized to a higher degree and produce broad emission lines. This is the broad line region (BLR). As the two regions are heated by different amounts they have different characteristic ionization states. The NLR clouds show only low ionization states such as HI, HeII, [SII] and [OIII], whilst the BLR clouds show higher degrees of ionization such as OVI, NV, CIV and CIII.

1.3.4 The obscuring torus

In the outermost regions of the accretion disk (~ 1 -10pc) the gas temperature and density rapidly drop and the disk gives way to an annular cloud commonly referred to as a torus (Pier & Krolik, 1992), but which may have the shape of a warped disk (Sanders et al., 1989). This torus feeds matter onto the accretion disk and interacts with the emission from it. The torus acts as a veil over the black hole and accretion disk producing large amounts of extinction and thus preventing an observer, whose line of sight intersects the torus, from directly observing the central region of the AGN. Thus the torus blocks the broad line emission that is emitted from the accretion disk and the BLR clouds. The NLR clouds are still visible in the polarized light that they reflect.

1.3.5 The relativistic jet

Recent work has showed that the accretion rate of a black hole depends on whether the accretion disk is thick or thin (Narayan & Quataert, 2005). A thin disk will deliver most of the matter supplied at large distances, to the black hole. In a thick disk very little of the matter will be accreted onto the black hole. Instead the matter will either be caught up in convective motions or

be driven away in an unbound outflow. This outflow can be in the form of a relativistic jet with an orientation perpendicular to the accretion disk, and is stronger and more energetic for more massive black holes (Liu et al., 2006). A spinning black hole is able to provide a secondary source of energy for the jet (Narayan & Quataert, 2005), as well as strong twisted magnetic fields that cause the jet to be highly collimated. The jets of an AGN are intrinsically two sided (Biretta et al., 1995; Sparks et al., 1992; Stiavelli et al., 1992), and can span as much as a few Mpc.

1.3.6 Viewing angle

AGN do not emit energy isotropically and the core is not spherically symmetric. This means AGN will have different characteristics depending on the viewing angle (Urry & Padovani, 1995). Taking the jet to be the primary axis, a viewing angle $\simeq 90^\circ$ will cause the central core to be blocked from view but not the NLR or jet. When viewed at close to 0° the jet, if present, will appear significantly brighter due to Doppler boosting, as well as showing superluminal velocities. At intermediate angles each of the components will be visible to different extents.

1.4 Classification

The many different types of AGN that the unified model sought to unify were discovered and described separately and often had features in common. Although a unified model now exists, the old classification scheme is still used to describe various features of AGN. In this section the main classes of AGN are described.

1.4.1 Seyferts

In the optical wavebands some spiral galaxies are seen to have an extremely bright core with strong emission lines of H, He, N, and O which show large amounts of Doppler broadening implying gas velocities from a few hundred to a few thousand kilometers per second. Such galaxies are known as Seyferts and were identified as early as 1943 (Seyfert, 1943). Once the number of known Seyfert galaxies grew to a large enough number it was apparent that they fell into two groups, one possessing only narrow emission lines (Type 2) and the other having both narrow and broad emission lines (Type 1). The broad emission lines can be highly variable implying a small emitting region close to the core whilst the narrow lines are very stable and most likely originate further out (Augusto et al., 2001). Seyfert galaxies have been detected at radio, ultraviolet and X-ray frequencies.

1.4.2 LINERs

Low-ionization nuclear emission-line region (LINER) galaxies are defined by their optical spectra and feature emission from weakly ionised or neutral atoms such as O, O⁺, N⁺, and S⁺. Strongly ionised atoms are only weakly present in the spectra, if at all. LINER galaxies are very common, making up approximately a third of nearby galactic AGN (Heckman, 1980).

1.4.3 Quasars

In the early 1950's a new class of object was identified using radio telescopes. The new objects appeared as powerful, compact radio sources with no apparent optical components. In 1963 Matthews & Sandage (1963) and Schmidt (1963) finally tied the radio objects 3C 48 and 3C 273 to optical identifications. The optical counterparts appeared as faint blue stars whose spectra implied a redshifts of 0.367 and 0.158 respectively. These quasi-stellar radio objects (QSOs or quasars) had an observed power that, if they were at cosmological distances, was far in excess of any currently known energy production mechanism. When accretion disk energy-production was modeled in the 1970's the luminosity problem was solved and the identification of quasars with high redshift radio sources was widely accepted. Quasars possess broad optical emission lines of H, He, C, Mg, Fe, and O including their highly ionised species, indicating that the gas is being strongly irradiated by the central quasar engine. Some quasars show variability on timescales as short as hours indicating relativistically beamed emission. Quasars with weak radio emission have also been detected and consequently quasars are often divided into radio-loud or radio-quiet.

1.4.4 Blazars

Many of the sources that are now known as blazars were first identified as irregular variable stars, changing in brightness by a few magnitudes on timescales as short as days. Schmitt (1968) made the discovery of radio emission from one such star, designated BL Lacertae (or BL Lac for short), which sparked an increased amount of interest as there was no known mechanisms by which a star could produce such large amounts of radio emission. Schmitt (1968) did, however, note some diffuse emission from the star, and Oke & Gunn (1974) later determined that it was a galaxy at a redshift of $z = 0.07$. Blazars are characterised by short, large amplitude variability and optical polarization and are generally less luminous than many quasars. The spectra of blazars is dominated by a featureless non-thermal continuum. Apparent superluminal velocities are sometimes observed in the inner regions of blazar jets.

1.4.5 Radio Galaxies

The broadest classification of AGN is simply that of radio galaxy. The first detection of radio source outside of our own solar system was made by Jansky (1933) and was found to be our own Galactic center. Radio emission is now known to be produced in most astronomical sources with the primary mechanism being electron synchrotron radiation. The hosts of radio galaxies are almost always large ellipticals. Radio galaxies show a wide range of morphologies, from compact point sources or close doubles or triples, to large scale emission that often shows some degree of symmetry. The most prominent large scale structures are called lobes, which appear as extended ellipsoidal emission regions that appear on either side of a compact core. The lobes are thought to be supplied energy from the core via a jet of relativistic particles. A classification scheme for extended radio sources was worked out by Fanaroff & Riley (1974) and divides radio galaxies into two types. Fanaroff-Riley Type 2 (FR-II) galaxies have edge brightened lobes or hot spots with a jet that is seen at much lower power, while Type 1 (FR-I) galaxies have no obvious radio lobes and a jet that appears much brighter but less collimated.

AGN are often divided into either radio loud or radio quiet. The host galaxies of radio loud and radio quiet AGN are essentially indistinguishable. The unification scheme for AGN does not explain why some AGN are radio loud while others are radio quiet. There has been some debate over the relationship between radio loudness and the mass of the central black hole. Magliocchetti et al. (2004) suggest that there is a minimum black hole mass of $10^8 M_{\odot}$ for the onset of radio emission. However Metcalf & Magliocchetti (2006) suggests there is no correlation between black hole mass and radio emission. Best et al. (2005) examined a large population of radio loud AGN with known black hole masses and found that whilst the distribution of radio luminosities is not generally dependant on black hole mass the *fraction* of radio loud AGN is. Converse to the above, McLure & Jarvis (2004) find a strong correlation between black hole mass and radio power, although a black hole of a given mass can have a radio power that spans many order of magnitude. It is likely that the case and strength of an AGNs radio loudness is dependant on more than just the black hole mass.

1.5 The importance of AGN

Active Galaxies are an important tool for the exploration of the distant universe as their high luminosity allows them to be detected at large redshifts. Understanding the formation and evolutionary history of AGN is thus critical to our understanding of the universe. The development of a unified theory for AGN has been useful in organising a large number of sources into a single group that can be used to understand the underlying physical properties of the individual sources. Whilst not all AGN possess all of the features listed in the previous section, the unified theory provides an excellent starting point for the investigation of any single source, whilst at the same time allows larger populations of sources to be used to probe the evolution of the universe. The dependence on the central black hole and accretion disk as the primary source of energy from these sources allows for the investigation of physical processes on the scale of pc, within galaxies which are many Gpc distant. The ubiquity of AGN is also key in the development and testing of many cosmological models. By investigating the formation and evolution of AGN and their effect on their surrounds we are developing a more effective probe of the universe. A particularly interesting class of AGN are the Gigahertz Peaked Spectrum (GPS) sources which are a prime motivation for this thesis.

1.6 GPS galaxies

Gigahertz Peaked Spectrum radio sources (GPS) were identified as early as 1963 (Bolton et al., 1963) and were characterized by a simple convex spectrum that peaks at a few ($\sim 1-5$) gigahertz. The archetypal GPS radio source PKS 1934-63 is depicted in figure 1.2. GPS sources make up a significant fraction ($\sim 10\%$) of the radio source population selected at cm wavelengths. de Vries et al. (1997) used a sample of 72 GPS sources to derive a canonical or ‘average’ radio spectrum. The spectral index (α , where $S = \nu^{\alpha}$), below the peak was found to be $\alpha = +0.51$ with that above being $\alpha = -0.73$. The spectral index above the peak is also typical for large-scale powerful radio sources, suggesting that the electron acceleration and energy loss mechanisms are the same over most of the lifetime of a radio source (Kellermann, 1966a). GPS sources have been identified with both optical galaxies and quasars. The radio source in GPS galaxies is contained entirely within the central regions ($\leq 15\text{kpc}$) of the host galaxy. It is helpful to think of a GPS galaxy as being

a radio source embedded within a host galaxy and although the evolution of the AGN and host are closely linked, they do not necessarily begin simultaneously. The super-massive black hole at the center of a galaxy may be much older than the radio source that it is currently supporting (Richstone et al., 1998). An in depth review of GPS sources can be found in (O’Dea, 1998).

Figure 1.2 : Spectral Energy Distribution of the archetypal GPS source PKS 1934-63. Data from Kuehr et al. (2009)

Traditionally only sources with observed spectral peaks below ~ 10 GHz have been identified, largely due to the lack of large area, high frequency surveys from which sources can be identified. In the rest frame, some GPS galaxies are seen to have spectral peaks in excess of 10 GHz, which suggests the existence of a new population of sources that peak at high frequencies (de Vries et al., 1997). A local population of high frequency peaking sources (HFP, with peaks $\gg 5$ GHz), would be severely under-represented in 5 GHz selected samples as the nature of their spectrum would cause them to be extremely faint. Until recently, nearly all of the known GPS sources with intrinsically high spectral peaks are at high redshift at which point the population is mostly flaring blazars rather than galaxies. A low redshift population of unknown HFP sources (both galaxies and quasars) could contribute to spurious measurements of the cosmic microwave background anisotropy (Crawford et al., 1996). Surveys at frequencies above 10 GHz are needed to identify and characterise this new population of high frequency peaking GPS sources.

A peaked radio spectrum is indicative of power law emission in the presence of an absorption process. The optically thick part of the radio spectrum, that which lies below the peak, suffers from strong absorption which decreases with increasing frequency until the spectral peak where the optical depth is unity. Above the spectral peak the shape of the radio spectrum is dominated by the emission process and is a characteristic of the energy distribution of the electron popula-

tion responsible for the emission. As the primary mechanism by which radio sources produce continuum emission is synchrotron emission from electrons in the presence of a magnetic field, it is not unreasonable to assume that synchrotron self absorption plays a role in the absorption process. It is also possible that free-free emission (Kellermann, 1966b), or induced Compton scattering (Kuncic et al., 1998) contribute to the spectral peak. Estimates of the magnetic fields within the GPS sources are consistent with the hypothesis that synchrotron self absorption is responsible for the spectral turn over, though free-free absorption is seen to play a significant role in a few cases. Currently the majority of authors favor synchrotron self-absorption as the main cause of the spectral turnover (eg, O’Dea (1998), Snellen et al. (2003)). However free-free absorption cannot be completely ruled out and it is reasonable to conclude that there is more than one process contributing to the spectral turnover. The predicted optically thick spectral index for synchrotron self absorption is $+5/2$, and is $+2$ for free-free absorption. The fact that almost none of the known GPS sources have a spectral index as inverted as $+2$ suggests that the radio source is not homogeneous.

The turnover frequency in a homogeneous, self absorbed, incoherent synchrotron radio source with power law electron energy distribution is given by

$$\nu_{\max} \sim 8B^{1/5} S_m^{2/5} \Theta^{-4/5} (1+z)^{1/5} \text{ GHz} \quad (1.1)$$

where B is the magnetic field in Gauss, S_m is the flux density at the peak in Jy, z is the redshift, and Θ is the angular size in milliarcseconds. Such a spectrum is demonstrated in figure 1.3. The highest frequency part of the radio spectrum is expected to steepen due to radiative losses. The amount of steepening present is dependent on the amount of time that has passed since the electron population was last injected with energy.

Figure 1.3 : Schematic of a typical synchrotron spectrum, from Robson (1995).

There have been a number of scenarios introduced in order to explain the origin of GPS galaxies. The three main contenders have described GPS sources as: 1) Transient events with relatively short lifetimes of $\leq 10^4$ yr (Readhead, 1994; Readhead et al., 1996), 2) old, frustrated sources which are

confined by interactions with a dense ISM (eg, Wilkinson et al., 1984), or 3) Young, evolving sources, which are the progenitors of large scale double lobe radio galaxies (Blake, 1970; Phillips & Mutel, 1982). Presently the evidence is in favor of the youth scenario of young evolving radio galaxies, however other scenarios may be more applicable for individual sources.

1.6.1 The Youth Scenario

Correlations between the peak frequency, peak flux density and angular size of provide strong evidence that synchrotron self-absorption is the cause of the spectral turnovers, and indicate that young radio sources evolve in a self-similar way (Snellen et al., 2000). This applies to GPS galaxies, HFP galaxies and also to the Compact Steep Spectrum (CSS) objects which have a spectral peak below 1 GHz (Bicknell et al., 1997). The evolutionary model that relates the age of a radio galaxy to the turnover frequency is known as the *youth scenario*. In the youth scenario the youngest of radio sources exhibit strongly absorbed radio spectra that peak at the highest frequencies. When gas is accreted onto a black hole either for the first time or as the result of some sort of galactic merger or interaction, the (re-)ignition of a radio source forms a jet which must bore through the ISM of the host galaxy (Begelman, 1996). Initially the jet is confined to such an extent that only the central part of the galaxy will be emitting radio energy; as a source ages it expands through the ISM of the host galaxy and its spectral peak moves to lower frequencies. Although the radio source is initially frustrated by the ambient ISM, it is not confined by it. If the AGN core continues to accrete matter over the time in which the size of the emission region is increasing, then the observed peak flux density will increase as there is less energy being absorbed. This increase in radio power with source size is observed in GPS sources up until the point at which the AGN breaks free of the host ISM (Snellen et al., 2000). At this stage the AGN core is able to develop radio jets that can more efficiently transport energy away from the core and there is an observed drop in the total power of these radio sources. In the youth scenario the evolutionary track is from HFP to GPS to a CSS source which has a spectral peak below ~ 100 MHz, and eventually into the large scale FR-I/II radio galaxies which have no observable peak. Figure 1.4 shows the evolutionary track for the radio power of a self-similar evolving, ram-pressure confined radio source within a King-profile density. Not all GPS galaxies follow this track, however, with some sources becoming extinct before they are able to complete the evolutionary path (Marecki et al., 2003).

1.6.2 Variability and Morphology

Sources which have complex morphologies and possess many hot spots of emission are able to have a peaked spectrum, but unless the spectral peak can be attributed to the core emission such sources are clearly not part of the evolutionary scenario outlined in the previous section. Quasars and Blazars are sources in which peaked spectra can be observed and in which the emission can be attributed to the AGN core, however the peaked spectrum is generally due to either non-simultaneous flux measurements or spectral variability.

A flat spectrum radio source such as a blazar, which is variable in total flux density, is able to appear as a peaked spectrum source when observations are made at different epochs which span the activity cycle of the blazar. Since blazars are not part of the youth scenario it is important

Figure 1.4 : The evolution of a radio source’s radio power and flux density at the spectral peak, as a function of linear size. The source’s size increases as it evolves as indicated by the arrow. Figure adapted from Snellen et al. (2000).

to be able to identify and remove them from any sample of GPS sources. A radio source which has a large fraction of beamed emission is able to exhibit spectral variability as gas clouds and other components drift in and out of the beamed radio jet. Simultaneous flux measurements will not guard against these sources and so long term monitoring is important. Tinti et al. (2005) conclude that even when simultaneous observations are made, monitoring reveals that most of the HFP sources are actually flaring blazars. Indeed of 51 HFP source monitored over 6 years by Orienti et al. (2007), 13 (25%) were found to be variable with 11 being quasars, 1 BL Lac, and 1 unidentified object.

GPS sources in general are the least variable radio sources with only $\sim 10\%$ being variable (Jauncey et al., 2003) and the degree of variability being only $\pm 10\%$ in flux over a year (O’Dea, 1998).

Despite their sometimes similar spectral shape blazars and young radio galaxies show very different characteristics over the majority of their lifetimes. Blazars have significant flux-density and spectral variability, the emission is often polarized, and they have a Core-Jet morphology on scales from a kpc down to a pc. Young radio galaxies, however, show little or no variability and the radio emission is almost completely unpolarized, (at least in the optically thick part of the spectrum), and they show a “Double/Triple” morphology (Orienti et al., 2006). The differences in properties can be largely attributed to the presence or lack of beamed emission. Stanghellini et al. (2005) find that extended emission is associated with GPS sources for 6 of 33 (18%) objects studied. The three GPS quasars in the sample were seen to have core jet morphology, whilst the GPS galaxies had a symmetric morphology. Stanghellini et al. (2005) conclude that the GPS quasars are beamed objects with a continuous supply of energy from the core to kpc scale, whilst the GPS galaxies are likely recurrent, with the extended emission a result of a previous round of activity.

Torniainen et al. (2007) note that for a reliable GPS classification, two things are needed: 1) broadband radio spectral data, preferably at several epochs, to define the turnover, and 2) long-term monitoring data at several frequencies to determine whether the source is variable at one or more frequencies. Only a small fraction of the currently known GPS sources have an observational record that satisfy these conditions.

1.6.3 GPS sources as a probe of radio galaxy evolution

A unified model of AGN takes into account many of the differences observed between the various classes of AGN, the common elements being a super massive accreting black hole, a hot accretion disk, a dusty torus, all within the central few kpc of the host galaxy. The mechanism for producing relativistic jets is not well understood but the jets and lobes that result are well understood. Once a jet has formed from the central part of an AGN it must bore its way through the ISM of the galaxy and then into the IGM. The density profile and relative motion of the ISM and IGM dictate how the jets are constrained and whether or not lobes will form. Radio lobes are thought to be shock fronts where the relativistic (or at least supersonic) particles of the jet collide and are slowed by intervening gas. The evolution of a radio source is thus closely linked to the environment within the host galaxy during its infancy and then to the external environment during its maturation into a large radio galaxy. Any investigation into the host galaxy evolution must therefore take into account the evolution of the AGN core and vice versa.

1.7 Luminosity Functions

The Luminosity Function (LF) for a particular class of objects is the number of objects that are found with a luminosity between L and $L + \delta L$. The LF tells us about the environment in which the object formed, and the processes which effect the evolution of the objects. In particular the LF contains information about the processes that create and destroy galaxies or galaxy clusters, processes that change one type of galaxy into another, and the processes by which mass is transformed into light.

An accurate measure of the LF of GPS sources is a useful tool in the understanding of radio galaxy evolution as a whole, but also to determine what fraction of GPS galaxies are fuelled for long enough to become larger radio galaxies.

Currently the luminosity function of young radio galaxies is drawn from samples of sources selected at frequencies below ~ 5 GHz. The local luminosity function of young radio galaxies is thus restricted to the more evolved sources. As noted by Snellen et al. (2000) the local luminosity function (LLF) of GPS sources cannot be measured directly since so few GPS sources are found at low redshift. Because of this, the LLF of steep spectrum sources is used to supplement that of GPS sources, resulting in large uncertainties. The solution to this problem is larger samples of GPS sources particularly the lower redshift HFP sources.

1.8 Application to this thesis

One goal of this thesis is to increase the number of known GPS sources with spectral peaks above 5 GHz, with particular emphasis placed on the low-redshift ($z < 0.15$) sources which are currently missing from the known GPS population. To achieve this goal it is desirable to have a large area radio survey with an observation frequency in excess of 5 GHz, as well as near simultaneous observations at multiple frequencies. The Australia Telescope 20 GHz (AT20G) survey has recently been completed and contains near simultaneous observations at 4.8 and 8.6 GHz, making it an extremely useful source of GPS and HFP candidates. My PhD thesis time has been divided between

the observation and data reduction of the AT20G survey, as well as the identification and further investigation of GPS and HFP sources within the survey. Before discussing the survey itself it is useful to discuss radio surveys in general, and this will be the focus of the following chapter.

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Chapter 2

Sky Surveys

Introduction

In this chapter I outline the significant contribution that radio surveys have made to astronomy. In particular the large area radio surveys that have allowed for a more statistically accurate description of the astrophysics and cosmology of our Universe.

2.1 Large Area Radio Surveys

Historically the most widely used and hence useful sky surveys have been the large area surveys. The first large area sky survey was the Third Cambridge radio survey (3C Edge et al., 1959) at a frequency of 159 MHz. This survey inspired a southern hemisphere counterpart at 85 MHz (MSH, Mills & Slee, 1957; Mills et al., 1960, 1961). The 3C and MSH catalogues achieved a limiting flux of only 7Jy. In 1967 the Fourth Cambridge survey was completed at 178MHz with a limiting flux of 2Jy, covering the same area of sky as 3C (4C Pilkington & Scott, 1965; Gower et al., 1967). The Parkes radio surveys of 1966 (PKS, Bolton et al., 1964; Ekers, 1969) were done at a frequency of 408 MHz and contained follow-up observations at 1.4 and 2.7 GHz, making it the first large area survey to include high frequency observations. Soon after the completion of the PKS survey the Parkes radio telescope was put to work on the most sensitive, large area, high frequency survey to date (PKSCAT90, Bolton et al., 1979). The survey took nearly a decade to complete and remained unparalleled for over 10 years.

The time required to produce a survey of the sky depends on a number of things: The amount of sky to be covered, the desired flux limit, the field of view of the telescope, and the sensitivity of the receivers being the major factors. It was not until a decade after the 4C/PKS surveys that receiver technology had improved to a point where higher frequency surveys were possible on a time scale that was not prohibitively large. The Molonglo Reference Catalogue of radio sources was completed in 1981 at 408MHz, with a limiting flux of 700mJy (MRC Large et al., 1981), and it would be yet another decade before the next large area survey.

The 1990's brought about several new large area surveys of the sky. The Green Bank telescope was used to survey the sky at 4.85 GHz to produce the 87GB survey that covered another 6 steradians of the northern sky down to 25mJy (Condon et al., 1989). In 1994 The Parkes radio telescope was used to produce the Parkes-MIT NRAO survey also at 4.85 GHz covering 7.4 steradians of the southern sky to 20mJy (PMN, Griffith & Wright, 1993). The PMN and 87GB surveys together made one of the first truly all sky surveys at a single frequency, and with telescopes of comparable resolution and sensitivity. In 1997 the NRAO VLA Sky Survey (NVSS) was completed at 1.4 GHz covering 10 steradians down to 2.3mJy, being one of the largest and most sensitive radio surveys do date (Condon et al., 1998). The Faint Images of the Radio Sky at Twenty-one cm (FIRST, Becker et al., 1995) survey was completed in 2002, also using the VLA, and covered a 2.7 steradian subset of the NVSS survey to a flux limit of 1mJy. In 1997 the Westerbork Synthesis Radio Telescope was used to create a the Westerbork Northern Sky Survey (WENSS, Rengelink et al., 1997), covering half of the northern sky to a limiting flux of 18 mJy at 325 MHz. The VLA was used again in 2007 to produce the VLA Low-Frequency Sky Survey (VLSS, Cohen et al., 2007) which covered nearly all of the sky north of -30° declination to 700 mJy at 74 MHz. In 2003 the Sydney University Molonglo Sky Survey (SUMSS, Mauch et al., 2003) was completed at 843MHz, which in combination with the second epoch Molonglo Galactic Plane Survey (MGPS2, Murphy et al., 2007), covers 3.14 steradians to 6 mJy using a modified and upgraded version of the Mills Cross telescope that was used to observe the MSH catalog some 40 years prior.

Since the PMN/87GB there have been no large area, high frequency sky surveys conducted. This can be directly attributed to the impractical amount of time it would take to survey the sky with a decreasing beam size. In 2002 a project at the Australia Telescope Compact Array (ATCA) was begun to test the feasibility of conducting a survey at 20GHz that would cover the entire southern sky. The observing for the Australia Telescope 20 GHz (AT20G) survey was completed in

Survey Name	Completed	Frequency GHz	Resolution arcmin	S_{lim} mJy	Area steradians
VLSS	2007	0.074	1.2	700	8.9
MSH	1961	0.085	50	7000	7.3
3C	1959	0.159	10	7000	6
4C	1967	0.178	11.5	2000	6
WENSS	1997	0.325	0.9	18	3.14
PKS	1969	0.408	43	2500	7.5
MRC	1981	0.408	3	700	7.9
SUMSS/MGPS2	2007	0.843	0.75	6	3.14
NVSS	1997	1.4	0.75	2.3	10
FIRST	2002	1.4	0.08	1	2.7
PKSCAT90	1979	2.7	7	600	9.3
87GB	1991	4.8	3.5	25	6
PMN	1994	4.8	3.5	20	7.4
AT20G	2007	20	0.17	60	6.3
WMAP	2005+	23-94	52-13	1000	12.6
Planck	2009+	33-1000	33-5	500-1000 ¹	12.6

Table 2.1 : Some large area radio continuum surveys from the last half century. The frequency in column 3 refers is the primary observation frequency, follow-up observations at other frequencies are not listed here. The limiting flux, S_{lim} , in column 5 is an upper limit, some areas of the survey may be complete at a lower flux level. Note: 1 - flux limits estimated as no source catalogs have been released.

2007, and is the largest, high frequency, radio survey conducted with sub arc-minute resolution. The Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe (WMAP, Chen & Wright, 2009) and Planck (Tauber, 2005) missions have as their primary science goals the exploration of the cosmic microwave background (CMB). To avoid contamination by foreground sources, both of these missions detect and remove discrete radio sources and produce survey catalogs at frequencies between 25 GHz and 1000 GHz, with a resolution of between 5 and 52 arcmin. Table 2.1 shows the mentioned radio surveys in order of observing frequency.

2.2 Low Frequency Radio Surveys

Traditionally, AGN-powered radio sources have been described as power law $S_\nu \propto \nu^\alpha$ and have been bundled into two groups; those with a steep ($\alpha < -0.5$) spectrum or those with a flat ($\alpha > -0.5$) spectrum. The spectrum of a radio source is rarely this simple to describe, due to the many different emission and absorption processes in play and the many sites of radio emission that are contributing to the overall spectra. The classification refers mostly to the low (<1 GHz) frequency portion of the radio spectrum and remains widely used despite its short comings. Low frequency radio surveys are thus dominated by steep spectrum radio sources, with some flat spectrum sources. Inverted spectrum sources ($\alpha > +0.5$) are rarely seen in low frequency surveys.

Also present in low frequency radio surveys are the ultra-steep spectrum ($\alpha < -1.3$) classes of

objects. The first class of objects are radio relics and halos of galaxy clusters, where the emission is associated with the intra cluster medium rather than a particular radio galaxy (Ferrari et al., 2008) and are of relatively low radio luminosity. The second class of objects are very radio-luminous and are mostly identified with very high redshift radio galaxies (eg, Breuck et al., 2001). Early low frequency radio surveys found a correlation between steep/flat spectral class and extended/resolved morphology. The steep spectrum radio sources were found to be either powerful radio galaxies with extended lobe emission, or star-burst galaxies with synchrotron radiation from relativistic electrons and free-free emission from HII regions (Condon, 1992). The flat spectrum radio sources were found to be unresolved quasars. The discovery of a new class of Compact Steep Spectrum (CSS) radio sources upset this view (Kapahi, 1981).

Figure 2.1 shows the predicted radio source population at 1.4 GHz. The way that the source population changes with flux density is related to both the intrinsic power of the radio sources as well as their spectral shape. The star-burst and FR-I's show steep spectra at 1.4 GHz and are much stronger at lower frequencies. The flat spectrum blazar (BL-Lac + Quasar) population becomes more dominant at higher flux densities as they are intrinsically more powerful than the star-burst/FR-I galaxies. The FR-II's are some of the most powerful sources seen in the low frequency radio surveys despite their steep spectrum. The FR-II sources owe their high radio luminosity to large, relativistic jet-fed radio lobes.

Figure 2.1 : The predicted radio source population at 1.4 GHz. Image from Jackson & Wall (1999)

2.3 High Frequency Radio Surveys

At high frequencies ($\nu > 5$ GHz) the grouping of sources into flat and steep spectrum is less appropriate than at low frequency, given the large variety of spectral shapes that are observed. Steep spectrum sources may flatten or become inverted, flat spectrum sources can steepen, and inverted spectrum source most often turnover and become steep spectrum again. The classification of high frequency radio sources is much simpler when considered from the viewpoint of the underlying physics as opposed to the observed spectrum. Nearly all of the extra-galactic radio emission seen at high frequency is related to the active galactic nuclei (AGN) discussed in chapter 1.

The surveys of Taylor et al. (2001), and Waldram et al. (2003) at 15 GHz and covered 0.16 steradians and detected 465 sources above 25 mJy, and showed that the existence and flux density of sources at 15 GHz could not reliably be predicted by extrapolation from lower frequency surveys such as the NVSS.

High frequency radio surveys are particularly important to the exploration of the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB), as discrete radio sources are the dominant contaminant of small-scale CMB anisotropies at mm wavelengths. High frequency radio surveys are thus essential for missions such as WMAP and Planck. The complexity of radio source structure make extrapolations from low frequency surveys very unreliable for the estimation of CMB contamination.

2.4 Radio Telescopes

The basic design of a radio telescope is depicted in figure 2.2. The two essential components are; a transducer or receiver that converts the incoming radiation into an electrical signal, and a recording device such as a chart recorder or computer hard drive. More traditional radio telescopes contain and reflecting surface, or dish, which is used to constrain the response of the receiver to a small portion of the sky and also to increase the amount of radiation received. The ability to physically move the dish to a particular of the sky is also useful, but not essential.

The design of radio telescopes is more diverse than their optical cousins. A large factor in the diversity of radio telescope design is the fact that the “radio spectrum” spans more than 5 decades in frequency, with wavelengths spanning from millimeters to meters. The design of a telescope generally reflects the intended operation and types of science that are to be done with the telescope. Larger radio dishes produce more sensitivity and higher resolution, but are more difficult to move than smaller dishes. Higher frequency receivers are more technically challenging to produce as the amount of thermal noise increases with frequency, and electronic equipment that is stable at such frequencies is more expensive. Higher frequency telescopes also require that the reflecting surface is accurate to within a smaller margin of error, leading to more rigid and heavier dishes.

The diffraction limited resolving power of any telescope is determined by the size of the aperture, and is given by:

$$\theta_{\min} = \frac{1.22\lambda}{D} = \frac{1.22c}{\nu D} \quad (2.1)$$

where θ_{\min} is the minimum separation at which two point sources are distinguishable, c , λ , ν are respectively the speed of light, observing wavelength, and frequency, and D is the diameter of the aperture. For optical telescopes this limit is never reached for ground based detectors as the

Figure 2.2 : Schematic of an alt-azimuth mounted cassegrain focus radio telescope. The dish and sub-reflector act to collect and guide the radio signals into the receiver, where the signal is then amplified and sent to a recording device for later analysis.

amount of atmospheric seeing is too great. For space based optical detectors the best resolution is a function of the CCD used to capture the image. For radio telescopes the atmosphere is generally transparent, and other factors such as ionospheric disturbances become more important. With wavelengths of millimeters to meters available radio telescopes are nearly always working at the diffraction limit.

The major difference between a radio and optical telescope is that a radio telescope does not by default provide an image of the sky. With an optical telescope a CCD detector is placed at the telescope focus and each pixel within the CCD will record an intensity. These pixels are then ordered in a matrix to form an image. Radio telescopes traditionally do not have an array of detector elements at the focus of the telescope. To form an image with a single radio telescope many observations, or pointings, need to be made so that an image can be built up. Essentially a radio telescope will observe a single pixel at a time¹.

¹The exception being the advent of focal plane arrays or multibeam receivers in which an array of radio detectors is placed in the focal plane of the telescope which enables images to be obtained in a single pointing as was done in the HI Parkes All Sky Survey (Barnes et al., 2001)

2.5 Radio interferometers

For a radio telescope to achieve arc-minute resolution at a frequency of 1.4 GHz a single dish would need to be almost 900 m in diameter. Such a telescope would take an enormous amount of resources to construct and would be nearly unsteerable. In order to increase the resolution of radio observations interferometry is employed.

Interferometry is a technique that takes the signal from two receivers and combines them together to form an interference pattern. The amplitude and phase of the interference pattern can be used to gain information about the structure of the source in question. A radio interferometer thus consists of two or more radio telescopes whose received signals are combined pairwise and recorded. Each pair of radio telescopes is referred to a baseline, and will give information about a single Fourier component of the spatial distribution of the portion of sky being observed. By either employing multiple telescopes, or multiple observations with a single pair, a number of Fourier components can be added together to get a more accurate representation of the spatial distribution of the observed sky. One of the main advantages of a radio interferometer is that it has a maximum resolution that is given by equation 2.1, where the maximum receiver separation is substituted for the aperture diameter. Thus, in order to obtain arc-minute resolution at a frequency of 1.4 GHz, a radio interferometer needs only two elements, separated by 900 m, a much more easily achievable task.

With a radio interferometer, the size of the individual radio dishes serves only to increase the sensitivity of the observations, they do not increase resolution. By adding additional receivers to the interferometer it is possible to increase the degree to which the spacial Fourier components are sampled (the u, v coverage), or the sensitivity of the combined system. Radio interferometers have become widely used and the term radio telescope is commonly used for both a single dish or interferometer setup.

2.6 Anatomy of a survey

Any given astronomical survey will have as one of its goals, the identification and characterization of the source population in a particular region of the sky, at one or more wavelengths. The usefulness of a survey will depend on various factors including: what fraction of the true source population has been observed, what fraction of the claimed sources are genuine and not a result of observational artefacts or noise, how large an area of sky has been included, and how accurately have each of the sources been characterized.

For radio surveys the critical statistics of a survey boil down to those listed in the table of 2.1. The resolution of the survey will determine how accurately the morphology of the sources is able to be determined, as well as how well double and multiple sources are able to be disentangled. The completeness level, S_{lim} , is the point at which the survey claims to have captured all of the sources that are brighter than this limit. The area of sky that is covered is important for statistical analysis of radio source populations, and for the identification of rarely seen sources. An ideal survey would cover the whole sky to the confusion limit dictated by the survey resolution. This feat is rarely completed, except at particularly low resolutions. Realistically a compromise needs to be made between the various parameters to maximise the amount of useful information that can

be obtained with a limited budget of time and/or resources.

The sensitivity of an observation (the rms noise level) is given by the radiometer equation:

$$\sigma \simeq \frac{T_{\text{sys}} g \eta}{\sqrt{\Delta\nu \tau}} \quad (2.2)$$

where σ is the sensitivity, T_{sys} is the system temperature in Kelvin, g is the system gain, η is the antenna efficiency, $\Delta\nu$ is the observing bandwidth, and τ is the integration time per observation. For the ATCA $g = 10\text{Jy/K}$ at 20 GHz. Equation 2.2 can be re-arranged to determine the integration time required to reach a certain sensitivity:

$$\tau \simeq \frac{1}{\Delta\nu} \left(\frac{T_{\text{sys}} g \eta}{\sigma} \right)^2 \quad (2.3)$$

Following de Zotti et al. (2010) we see that for a diffraction limited observation of the sky, the number of observations required to cover a given area scales as ν^2 . For a given receiver noise and observing bandwidth, the time taken to detect a source at a flux of S scales as S^{-2} , so for a continuum survey of optically thin synchrotron emission, (where $S \propto \nu^{-0.7}$), the survey time scales as $\nu^{3.4}$. The usable bandwidth is generally proportional to frequency and so the over scaling becomes $\sim \nu^{2.4}$. A survey at 20 GHz will take ~ 14 times longer than one at 1.4 GHz to cover the same area to the same flux density limit, and ~ 600 times longer to reach the same source density if $\alpha = -0.7$. It is for this reason that large area high frequency radio surveys have been uncommon.

2.7 Summary

Astronomical surveys are extremely useful for the understanding of the large scale structure of the universe, and the nature of the various sources that lie within. The usefulness of a survey is increased as the area of coverage and sensitivity of the survey is increased, but the amount of observing time required to achieve these goals is also increased. The observing time is also increased as higher observation frequencies are used resulting in a lack of large area, sensitive, high frequency sky surveys. The AT20G, covers the entire southern hemisphere at a resolution of 0.17 arcmin, and to a limiting flux of 60 mJy (Murphy et al., 2010). This recently completed survey will contribute to the foreground removal of sources from the WMAP and Planck CMB missions, as well as providing an unbiased look at the 20 GHz sky. In the next chapter I will outline the way in which the AT20G survey was carried out and the resulting data was reduced. In the chapters following, I will be making use of the AT20G catalog to investigate the GPS and High Frequency Peaking sources discussed in the previous chapter.

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Chapter 3

The Australia Telescope 20 GHz Sky Survey

Introduction

The Australia Telescope 20 GHz (AT20G) Sky Survey (Murphy et al., 2010) is a 6 year project that began pilot observations in 2002. It was an ambitious project conceived by Ron Ekers to use a prototype wide-band analog correlator developed by Warwick Wilson and Paul Roberts on the Australia Telescope Compact Array (ATCA). A project of its size necessarily requires many people at different stages of its development to bring it to fruition. I joined the team in my honors year (2004-2005), when the project was beginning its first epoch of survey observations. I continued my involvement throughout my PhD candidature.

My contribution to the survey has been to develop and implement a range of programs for: the calibration of the scanning observations, the compilation of these data into sky maps, and the extraction of candidate source lists from these maps. Other members of the AT20G team have contributed to the results in this chapter in the following ways:

- Paul Roberts provided notes and figures for the hardware design in section 3.2
- Mike Kesteven conceived the calibration and map making schemes and wrote the first generation of code that is outlined in sections 3.4 and 3.5 and table 3.2.
- Tara Murphy was responsible for the data reduction of the follow-up observations and the creation of the final AT20G catalog that is use in this chapter
- Lister Staveley-Smith wrote the program WBLOD which is used to convert the correlator output into the format that is used by the calibration and data reduction programs (see table 3.2).

In this chapter I outline: 1) the hardware that was used to observe the AT20G survey, 2) the process by which the observations were calibrated, 3) the way in which the data were used to create maps of the sky, 4) the list of candidate source detections recovered from the maps, and 5) the potential uses of the candidate source list.

3.1 Motivation

The radio-source population above 5 GHz has not been well studied, in most part due to the lack of large-area surveys. Large radio telescopes typically have fields of view of a few arc-minutes at high frequencies, making it extremely time-consuming to carry out such surveys. The high-frequency properties of radio sources are important to our understanding of the nature and evolution of both radio galaxies and the universe itself. Radio galaxy evolution can be explored via the AGN discussed in chapter 1, whilst the nature and evolution of the universe can be explored via studies of the cosmic microwave background (CMB). High resolution radio surveys are crucial for the removal of foreground radio sources (de Zotti et al., 1999) for CMB missions such as Planck (Tauber, 2005), Fermi (Ritz et al., 2009) and the South Pole Telescope (Stark, 1998), where point sources contaminate the measured CMB anisotropy at angular scales of less than 30 arc-minutes.

A Wide-Band Analog Correlator (WBAC) built by Paul Roberts and Warwick Wilson for the Taiwanese Array for Microwave Background Anisotropy (AMiBA Lo et al., 2001), was not used in the production version of the AMiBA project, due to the complexity needed to remove $1/f$ noise in a large correlator. It was realised by Ron Ekers that the WBAC could be used on the ATCA for a large area high frequency survey on a timescale that was not prohibitive.

As mentioned in chapter 2 the time needed to cover a region of sky to a particular flux level depends on both the size of the primary beam and the integration time per pointing (Equations 2.2 and 2.1). The advantage provided by the WBAC was an 32 fold increase in observing bandwidth and thus a 32 fold decrease in the observing time for a survey of the southern sky.

3.2 AT20G Hardware

The AT20G survey was conducted using three of the six antennas that make up the ATCA, along with a custom Wide-Band Analog Correlator (WBAC). In this section we describe the antenna and correlator design.

3.2.1 ATCA telescopes

Antennas 2, 3, and 4 of the ATCA were situated on stations W102, W104, and W106, giving two 30.6m (2-3 and 3-4) baselines and a single 61.2m (2-4) baseline. The antenna design and construction is outlined in Frater et al. (1992), and the 20 GHz upgrade to the compact array is discussed in Wong & Melatos (2002).

3.2.2 WBAC design

The AT20G survey used a wide-band analogue correlator initially designed for the AMiBA project. In 2002/2003 the WBAC was used in a pilot survey as a two element 3.4 GHz bandwidth interferometer at 18 GHz. The pilot survey covered approximately 1200deg^2 of the sky between $-59^\circ > \delta > -71^\circ$, for further details see Ricci et al. (2004). The wide-band analogue correlator

Figure 3.1 : Correlator architecture for a single baseline. The multipliers are located at the positions marked by \otimes and the path length differences correspond to the delay spacing of $\Delta\tau$. The complete WBAC consists of three such correlators.

was adapted and expanded to produce a 3 element 8 GHz bandwidth interferometer with a central frequency of 20 GHz, which was used for the main AT20G survey.

Assembly

The lag correlator is constructed from an array of 16 multipliers per baseline, with precise transmission line delays providing the required delay difference for each lag. The architecture chosen is shown in Figure 3.1 and comprises two wide bandwidth power splitters to replicate the input signals, which are then arranged as two parallel counter-propagating sets of signals. The correlators were designed to process a 0-12 GHz input band to avoid having to perform a final down-conversion of the 4-12 GHz IF band to baseband. At the intersection of each corresponding pair of transmission lines is placed a multiplier. To facilitate assembly and simplify any required rework the multipliers are mounted on small second level microwave circuit boards which are inserted into cutouts milled in the correlator boards at the required positions.

The separation of the lag channels, $\Delta\tau$, is determined by the displacement of the multiplier boards as shown in figure 3.1, and is designed to be a half wavelength at 12 GHz (ie Nyquist), which is a delay of 4.2×10^{-2} nsec. The sampling in time delay is not perfectly uniform due to manufacturing and material effects, and may also have a small frequency dependence. This deviation from ideal Nyquist sampling is stable in time and can be accurately measured so the spectrometers performance is not significantly effected. Figure 3.2 shows the transform phases of the WBAC as a function of channel number, for the primary calibrator 1921-293. The deviation from a linear fit to the phases is also shown, and is typically 0.2×10^{-2} nsec, which is less than 5%. The non ideal sampling is overcome by additional data processing steps as outlined in section 3.5. In a digital correlator the delay spacings are able to be adjusted so that the delay spacings are all equal and would result in a flat line at 0 nsec for the right hand plot of 3.2.

Data Acquisition

Timing and data acquisition of the correlator system is controlled from a Linux based computer, running a modified version of the standard compact array correlator control software. High accuracy timing signals are taken from the observatory's 5 MHz reference signal which is derived from

Figure 3.2 : **Left:** The transform phases for the WBAC with reference to an arbitrary time for the primary calibrator 1921-293. The spacing between the correlator channels is of the order 4.2×10^{-2} nsec. **Right:** The deviation from a linear fit to the transform phases. The largest error is 0.7×10^{-2} nsec with a typical value of 0.2×10^{-2} nsec.

a hydrogen maser. The data from the ATCA antennas is transported via an optical fiber to the control room where it is then converted to an electric signal by an optical receiver. The three antennas each have a phase switch in the signal path just after the optical receivers. The phase switching is designed to be mutually orthogonal and take the form of a 350 kHz square wave and two 700 kHz square waves. The signals are correlated and sent to an analogue to digital converter (ADC) where they are accumulated for an integration cycle before being sent to the control computer where the data is archived.

WBAC Performance

Stability of the WBAC system was measured by observing the variance in the integrated spectrum as a function of time using a laboratory noise source and amplifier providing nominal input levels. This variance reduced in accordance with the radiometer equation (2.2), as the inverse square root of the integration time. This measurement was only taken over 10 minutes but was adequate to verify stability for the current transit instrument, which operates with integration time less than 100 ms.

The stability of the WBAC is important for the flux calibration of the survey observations as it allows for the use of a single bandpass and flux calibrator. Instabilities within the WBAC would require calibrator observations more frequently than one per day and would increase the amount of time needed to properly survey the sky. The stability is also important for the timing calibration in section 3.4 as any instabilities would need to be decoupled from those external to the correlator.

3.2.3 Combined System

Figure 3.3 shows a block diagram of the analogue correlation system. The system is comprised of three main parts: The IF transmission system that transports the down-converted received signals to the central site; the actual correlators themselves; and the data acquisition and processing system. The ATCA analogue correlator system at the present time is a transit instrument. The

Figure 3.3 : Schematic representation of the combined antenna and analog correlator system.

absence of variable delay compensator units, which would be required on two of the signal paths, means that sources cannot be tracked in delay. The static delays are adjusted so that the array is directed towards the meridian with the antennas in a East-West linear array.

Performance

Once the WBAC was connected to the telescopes further characterisation and alignment of the system was performed. The static delays were adjusted by observing the fringes produced as a point radio source passed through the beam of the array, and adjusting the antenna and baseline based delays accordingly to set the peak of the fringes at the centre of the correlators at the expected time.

The fringe pattern produced by each lag channel can be Fourier inverted to give the entire system frequency response for each correlator channel. From this data each of the lags can be calibrated. Figure 3.4(a) shows the recorded fringe pattern for a single lag within the correlator as a calibrator source was observed. In figure 3.4(b) the Fourier inverted system band-passes for all 16 lags in the correlator are superimposed on a linear scale. The characteristic saddle shape is dominated by the gain curve of the 4-12 GHz amplifiers used in the IF transmission system. The band has a dip of approximately 6 dB in the centre which would be expected to reduce the effective bandwidth of the system.

The fundamental determinant of performance is the sensitivity achieved with the system. Observations with the full 8 GHz, three baseline system were begun in September 2004. During these observations an average sensitivity of approximately 10 mJy, using 80 ms integration time, was achieved.

Figure 3.4 : ATCA+WBAC system response for AT calibrator 1921-293. **Left:** Delay beam fringe pattern for a single lag channel on baseline 2 – 3. Time is in units of 54 ms, amplitude is arbitrary. **Right:** A Fourier transform of a lag channel fringe patterns gives the system bandpass. All 16 channels are superimposed.

3.3 Scanning strategy

As it was not possible to insert the geometric delays necessary to track a point on the sky, the survey was intentionally restricted to meridian observations. By scanning the telescopes close to the maximum rate of $\sim 15^\circ \text{min}^{-1}$ along the meridian, the natural rotation of the earth allowed the observation of interleaving tracks across the sky. The position of the antennas was recorded every $\sim 50 \text{ms}$. This gave a 0.8 arcmin spacing between observations along each track. The telescope slew speed and integration times were fine tuned so that the tracks would produce closed paths (over a 24 hour period), with each subsequent path being a beam width (2.3 arcmin) from the previous. Figure 3.5 shows the interleaved tracks that are formed when data from multiple days are combined. The closed path allows for the distinction between tracks (interleaves), which is important to ensure that any data which is missed or flagged due to bad weather or instrumental failure is easily recovered. The separation of the tracks by a beam width means that each point on the sky falls within the FWHM of the primary beam of the telescope. Sky locations on the interior of the scan region are covered twice each by this scanning strategy, once in a northward track and once in a (different) southward track. Towards the boundaries of the declination band the coverage becomes less uniform and points are either covered only once, at the extreme edges, or twice with a single track.

The survey mode observations for any given declination band of the sky were carried out contiguously, with all the observations for a particular region of the sky being completed within a single observing period. Observing in this way takes advantage of the stability of the correlators. Table 3.1 shows when the observations for each declination band were taken. To make the best use of the available time, any observations that needed to be redone were collected and generally carried out towards the end of the allocated observing time. For small amount of bad data that occurred towards the beginning or end of a particular interleave, the patching was done during the change over to the next days observation. Due to our meridian scanning technique and the randomness of bad weather or equipment failure, it was not always possible to recover all the data which was lost or flagged. When patching, preference was given to regions with missing data, and then to those with large amounts of noise or bad weather.

Figure 3.5 : An actual example of a scanning interleave pattern for $-40^\circ \geq \delta \geq -50^\circ$. A total of 7 interleaves were required to achieve an interleave spacing equal to the primary beam FWHM of 2.3 arcmin. Data that was flagged from interleave 0 near $14^h 12^m$, is not a terminal problem as the same area of sky is covered by observations scanning in the opposite direction.

3.4 Survey Calibration

As mentioned in section 3.2.2, the WBAC has channel spacings that are not regular and may depend on frequency. In the absence of noise, irregular channel spacing will not affect the recovery of the observed spectrum. When present, noise correlation between lag channels will increase as the spacing diverges from Nyquist. To avoid correlated noise signals, the calibration and data reduction of the scanning interleaves was carried out in the lag domain. Calibration of the lag response can be done using monochromatic signals (Harris & Zmuidzinas, 2001), or *in situ* using astronomical sources (Holler et al., 2007). The AT20G survey had already adopted the approach independently described by Holler et al. (2007).

It is necessary to be able to deduce the location of a source in delay space from the signal distribution of the 16 channels of the correlator. If the calibration is correct over the three correlators then we will derive a common delay from each of them when a source is within the antenna beam. The source's position on the sky is derived from the delay, the antenna elevation, and the UT of the observation. Once the correlators are calibrated this process can be inverted: that is, given a record of 16 lags over 3 baselines, it is possible to estimate, for any delay, the magnitude of a source at a particular location which is consistent with the record. The key to this process is the tracking calibration which gives the signatures for all the delays within the correlator's range. A source on

Declination Band	Epoch
$-30^\circ \geq \delta \geq -40^\circ$	11 Aug - 31 Aug 2004
$-40^\circ \geq \delta \geq -50^\circ$	20 Aug - 31 Aug 2004
$-50^\circ \geq \delta \geq -60^\circ$	9 Sep - 2 Oct 2005
$-60^\circ \geq \delta \geq -70^\circ$	23 Sep - 2 Oct 2005
$-70^\circ \geq \delta \geq -80^\circ$	16 Sep - 20 Sep 2005
$^\dagger -80^\circ \geq \delta \geq -90^\circ$	20 & 29 Sep 2005
$-15^\circ \geq \delta \geq -30^\circ$	16 Aug - 3 Sep 2006
$0^\circ \geq \delta \geq -15^\circ$	23 Aug - 9 Sep 2007
$^\dagger -85^\circ \geq \delta \geq -90^\circ$	7 & 9 Sep 2007

Table 3.1 : The observation dates for the scanning observations for each of the declination bands. Overlapping dates are due to patching data being observed at the end of each years observations. † These regions include the south celestial pole and as such, required a separate program to produce the maps.

the equator observed with a 30m baseline will have 75 recorded samples in the time it takes for the peak correlation to advance from one multiplier to the next.

3.4.1 Overview

The calibration scheme used for the scanning interleave data has five main components, two of which are instrumental and three of which are environmental. The instrumental calibration components are the round trip phase information, and the array alignment correction. These are measured and corrected for on timescales of less than a minute. The environmental calibration components use astronomical sources to detect variations in the correlator delay response and make the required adjustments. Figure 3.6 shows an overview of the calibration contributions.

Figure 3.6 : An overview of the various delay and flux calibration contributions.

As there were no standard programs available that could cope with the specific setup of the WBAC,

it was necessary to create a suite of purpose built programs. The programs were written in FORTRAN 77¹ and implemented as tasks within the MIRIAD environment (Sault et al., 1995). Table 3.2 lists the main programs that were used in the calibration and data reduction of the survey scanning data. The program WBLOD is an adaptation of the standard ATLOD program that converts the RPFITS format data from the Australia Telescope correlators into the miriad data format. The extremely short integration time, and non-standard observing strategy implemented by the AT20G scanning observations required some minor modifications. The programs WB_BPASS and MK_CALFIL use the primary calibrator to obtain a bandpass and calibrator response template. DRIFT_CAL is used interactively to create a basic calibration scheme which is based on the roughly daily observation of calibrator sources. The tertiary calibrators are identified using this calibration scheme. PROCESS_TRACK is used to identify tertiary calibrators within the individual interleaves and CALIB_MERGE is used to automate the calibration of these sources. The maps of the sky are produced from the raw data and calibration tables using MERGE_VIS which also incorporates the instrumental calibrations outlined in figure 3.6. Identification of candidate sources within the sky maps is achieved via CLEAN_PHV. The final program in the list, INJECT_MERGE_VIS, is a modified version of MERGE_VIS which allows for the insertion of new source during the map making process. The rate at which these new sources are recovered by CLEAN_PHV and subsequent filtering processes is used to determine the completeness of the survey catalog and is discussed in section 3.10.

Task	Purpose	Author
WBLOD	convert correlator output to standard miriad format	lss 2002
WB_BPASS	determine the band-pass and calibrator characteristics	mjk 2002-2004
MK_CALFIL	record the primary calibrator response	mjk 2002-2004
DRIFT_CAL	calibrate the secondary calibrators	mjk 2002-2004
PROCESS_TRACK	scan based detection of tertiary calibrators	mjk 2002-2004
CALIB_MERGE	create calibration table based on tertiary calibrators	{ mjk 2002-2004 pjh 2004-2009
MERGE_VIS	create sky maps from calibrated interleave data	{ mjk 2002-2004 pjh 2004-2009
CLEAN_PHV	CLEAN-like searching of maps for candidate sources	pjh 2006-2009
INJECT_MERGE_VIS	create sky maps with new sources injected	pjh 2006-2009

Table 3.2 : The miriad tasks that were created for the calibration and data reduction process. Author key: mjk - Mike Kesteven, lss - Lister Staveley-Smith, pjh - Paul Hancock.

3.4.2 Primary Calibration

The WBAC consists of 3 correlators, each correlating 16 different lag channels on a single baseline. The output from each of the correlators' lag channels can be represented by a single baseline single channel interferometer as depicted in figure 3.7. The following is a simplified derivation of the received signal from each of the correlators, where noise terms, phase differences, and local oscillator mixing effects have been neglected for clarity.

¹and later upgraded to FORTRAN 90

Figure 3.7 : Schematic of a single baseline, single channel interferometer. The astronomical delay τ_{ast} is a function of meridian angle θ , and baseline b . Each correlator within the WBAC computes $C(\tau_{ast})$ for 16 different delays (τ) resulting in the function $C(\tau, \tau_{ast})$. Figure adapted from Thompson (1999)

The signal received from each of the amplifiers can be written as:

$$V_A = A(\nu) * \cos[2\pi\nu t]$$

$$V_B = B(\nu) * \cos[2\pi\nu(t + \tau + \tau_{ast})]$$

where: $A(\nu)$ and $B(\nu)$ describe the band-shapes of the amplifiers, the data transmission path from antenna to the correlator, and the gain equalisation units at the correlator, τ is the compensating delay inserted by the correlator, and τ_{ast} is the astronomical delay:

$$\tau_{ast} = \frac{b}{c} \sin(\theta)$$

for an East-West baseline of length b observing a source at meridian angle θ .

The correlator receives the two signals and multiplies them to form:

$$\begin{aligned} V_A V_B &= M(\nu) A(\nu) B(\nu) \cos[2\pi\nu t] \cos[2\pi\nu(t + \tau + \tau_{ast})] \\ &= M(\nu) A(\nu) B(\nu) \frac{1}{2} \{ \cos[2\pi\nu(2t + \tau + \tau_{ast})] + \cos[2\pi\nu(\tau + \tau_{ast})] \} \end{aligned}$$

where $M(\nu)$ is the bandpass of the multiplier and the result been separated into a high and low frequency component. A low pass filter is used to remove the high frequency component with

frequency $4\pi\nu t$, leaving only the low frequency component which is then integrated to give the correlation function:

$$C(\tau, \tau_{ast}) = \int_{\nu_c - \frac{\Delta\nu}{2}}^{\nu_c + \frac{\Delta\nu}{2}} M(\nu)A(\nu)B(\nu) \cos[2\pi\nu(\tau + \tau_{ast})]d\nu$$

where ν_c is the low pass filter's central frequency and $\Delta\nu$ is its bandwidth.

Integration by parts gives:

$$C(\tau, \tau_{ast}) = M(\nu)A(\nu)B(\nu) \frac{\Delta\nu}{2} \frac{\sin[\pi\Delta\nu(\tau + \tau_{ast})]}{\pi\Delta\nu(\tau + \tau_{ast})} \cos[2\pi\nu_c(\tau + \tau_{ast})] \\ + \int_{\nu_c - \frac{\Delta\nu}{2}}^{\nu_c + \frac{\Delta\nu}{2}} \frac{d}{d\nu} (M(\nu)A(\nu)B(\nu)) \frac{\sin(2\pi\nu(\tau + \tau_{ast}))}{2\pi(\tau + \tau_{ast})} d\nu$$

Figure 3.8 : **Left:** The set $\{C(\tau, \tau_{ast})\}$ for the primary calibrator 1921-293 baseline 2-3. The ordinate is time since the beginning of observation, in units of 54 ms, with transit occurring at $\tau_{ast} = 800$. The abscissa is the lag channel τ . **Right:** A Fourier transform with respect to τ_{ast} , of each of the lag channels will result in the total band-pass $A(\nu)B(\nu)M(\nu)$. The units of the abscissa are arbitrary.

The basic observable is the set $\{C(\tau, \tau_{ast})\}$. Primary calibrator observations are done in a tracking mode where by the calibrator is tracked by the telescopes as it transits the meridian. During this time the set $C(\tau, \tau_{ast})$ is recorded for range of delays τ_{ast} that is large enough to encompass the synthesized beam response. Having the antennas track the calibrator allows the primary beam response of the antennas to be disentangled from the synthesized beam response of the correlator. Once $C(\tau, \tau_{ast})$ has been measured, $A(\nu)B(\nu)M(\nu)$ can be derived via Fourier inversion, and the correlator response can be treated as given in the above equation. Shown in figure 3.8 is the set $\{C(\tau, \tau_{ast})\}$ as derived from the primary calibrator observation of 1921-293, for baseline 2-3. The separation between lag channels ($\Delta\tau$) is $\lambda/2$ where $\lambda = 24\text{mm}$ and corresponds to 85 arcsec in RA. The separation in τ_{ast} is the integration period of 54 ms and represents 1 arcsec in RA.

Round Trip Phase

The optic fibers that carry the data between the telescopes and the control building are buried in conduits to reduce the effects of temperature and humidity variations. Even so, there is a measurable delay variation that needs to be compensated for. The standard ATCA correlator is able to track and compensate for these delays via a 1 GHz signal transmitted along the fibre to each telescope and then sent back along the same path. Round trip phases variations in this signal are measured, halved, and recorded in real time for on line calibration, and are also logged for offline calibration. The WBAC is unable to correct for any variances in the round trip phase so the corrections must be made off-line. The compact array monitoring software (MONICA), is used to record the round trip phase variations. A sample of the round trip phase data is shown in Figure 3.9 as well as the derived baseline phase differences. The large scale variations on the order of 1 day are due to day/night temperature and humidity effects, whilst the small scale variations on the order of $\sim 2 - 3$ hours are due to the air-conditioning units in the correlator room and each of the antennas. The similarities between the round trip phase of each of the antennas is due to the signals to each of the antennas having part of the transmission path in common. Only changes in the difference between the antenna transmission paths need to be calibrated. Given that the three antennas used in the AT20G survey are on adjacent stations of the ATCA it is expected that the baseline phase differences will be small. The lower traces in the plot of 3.9 show how the baseline phase differences change with time. The round trip phase at 20 GHz is 0.3 times that at 1 GHz.

Figure 3.9 : 1 GHz round trip phase, $\Delta\Phi$, as a function of Julian Day. CA02, CA03, CA04 show the round trip phase as reported by MONICA for the three antennas in use (offset by an arbitrary amount). The baseline phases are shown as the differences between the antenna phases and are seen around 0 delay. The baseline phase differences are used to calibrate the scanning observations.

The round trip phase data enables delay calibration on the order of a minute. This calibration measure is the starting point from which the following calibration steps aim to refine.

Array Alignment

The ATCA is an East-West extension interferometer, but the baselines are not true East-West. The small variation from East-West is compensated for in the ATCA digital correlators automatically via the insertion of small delays, and is usually transparent to the users of the telescope. Again, the design of the WBAC is such that we are not able to insert these delays and thus they must be compensated for in the calibration scheme. To within an arc-sec, the compensation for the non East-West nature of the array, at the meridian is:

$$\Delta\tau_{ast} = 170 - 318 \times \cos(\delta)$$

As with the round trip phase, this delay is applied as a baseline calibration and further calibration measures are taken with respect to this delay.

Secondary Calibrators

Secondary calibrators are observed daily, usually in the change over time between consecutive interleaves. Secondary calibrators are observed in a drift or transit mode, where the telescopes are directed at the meridian and the calibrator is left to drift through the primary beam of the telescopes. Since the transit time of the source can be deduced from the LST and position of the source, any environmental or instrumental delays that are not captured by the round-trip phase monitor, are able to be detected and corrected for. In this way each declination band on the sky for which scanning observations were done is interspersed with drift calibrator observations.

To detect and correct for any delay offsets the program DRIFT_CAL is used. This program takes the calibrator observation and uses the known $C(\tau, \tau_{ast})$ values from the primary calibration step to determine which values of τ_{ast} are most consistent with a source transit at the given time. When operating in *lag* mode, DRIFT_CAL will fit $\Delta\tau_{ast}$ for each baseline and time stamp, and then report a $\Delta\tau_{ast}$ that best aligns the baselines for the entire calibrator observation. An example output is shown in figure 3.10 (*Right*) for the calibrator 0537-441 within the Australia Telescope Calibrator database². The vertical lines in the plots of figure 3.10 show the calculated source transit time. When the relative delays between the baselines are corrected DRIFT_CAL can be run in *merge* mode where the overall telescope response is shown. At this stage the absolute offsets can be adjusted to cause the peak to be aligned with the transit time. For source with lower signal to noise, it is possible that DRIFT_CAL will select a value of $\Delta\tau_{ast}$ that corresponds to a side lobe of the synthesised beam, as can be seen to occur towards the outer parts of figure 3.10 (*Right*). In this case the telescope response needs to be viewed to determine which is the correct value of $\Delta\tau_{ast}$ to use for each of the baselines. Given that there are typically only one drift calibrator observation per scanning interleave this process can be done by hand without becoming cumbersome.

Once each of the drift calibrators has a correct calibration recorded the next step is to refine the calibration table even further using tertiary calibration sources.

²On-line at www.narrabri.atnf.csiro.au/calibrators

Figure 3.10 : Diagnostic output from DRIFT_CAL for the secondary calibrator 0537-441. *Left*: The antenna response as the calibrator transits through the primary beam. The vertical line at time= 0 is the calculated transit time of the source. *Right*: The delay which DRIFT_CAL computes for the calibrator as a function of time. The Red, Green, and Blue lines represent the three different baselines. Away from transit the signal to noise becomes degraded and DRIFT_CAL becomes confused with side-lobes of the calibrator response. Delay is in units of 54 ms.

Tertiary Calibrators

At this stage of the calibration process allowances have been made for delay offsets due to changes in the round trip phase, on the order of minutes, and global offsets due to environmental or instrumental effects, on the order of a day, from the secondary calibrators. To further refine the calibration of environmental and instrumental effects on the order of a few minutes, many tertiary calibrators are required.

The initial source of tertiary calibrators come from the AT Calibrator database. All sources with an observed flux density above ~ 50 mJy at 20 GHz which are unresolved on short baselines are used. The density of sources within the AT calibrator catalog for a given 10° or 15° declination band is such that the number of sources expected to fall within a 24 hour observation is small. As the time between sources and calibrator observations increases so too does the likelihood of decorrelation, resulting in a lower survey sensitivity. To increase the ultimate survey sensitivity the number of calibrator sources were increased by using strong sources ($S_{20} \geq 100$ mJy, $\text{SNR} \geq 5$) that were found within the partially calibrated scanning observations. The number of available calibrators was increased from around 500 to a nearly 3000 over the entire sky using this bootstrapping process.

The sources used for self calibration were detected using the following correlation:

$$S(\tau_{ast}) = \sum C(\tau, \tau_{ast})C_{obs}(\tau) \quad (3.1)$$

where C_{obs} are the measured correlator data; $C(\tau, \tau_{ast})$ is the measured data from the tracking calibration, using the available range of tracking delays τ_{ast} . When the correlator is calibrated we can form the sum $S(\tau_{ast})$ over all three baselines. A source detection is claimed whenever $S(\tau_{ast})$ exceeds a detection threshold set by the off-source noise.

Once a list of tertiary calibrators had been obtained, the program GEN_CALIB_MERGE was used to determine good values of $\Delta\tau_{ast}$ for each of the scanning observations that included one of the

tertiary calibrators. GEN_CALIB_MERGE works by taking the current calibration table, round trip phase information, and the array alignment correction, and tests a range of $\Delta\bar{v}_{st}$ to see if there is a better fit than the current calibration table. GEN_CALIB_MERGE also makes a determination of the amplitude scaling of each of the three baselines to give a flux consistent with that given in the tertiary calibrator list.

The new calibration table produced by GEN_CALIB_MERGE is then filtered to remove calibration points that are not consistent with the original DRIFT_CAL table. Figure 3.11 shows the DRIFT_CAL calibration table, GEN_CALIB_MERGE calibration points, and the final calibration table that was used for the zone $-50 \geq \delta \geq -60$. Evident in the GEN_CALIB_MERGE data are instances where the automated process became confused and chose the incorrect peak for the tertiary calibrators. A filtering program was created that would create a smoothed version of the correct calibration peaks at regular intervals of 4 hours. The final calibration points in figure 3.11 are joined with a line, and represent the linear interpolation that is done between calibration points when applied to the survey data.

Figure 3.11 : Calibration table at various stages of refinement for the region $-50 > \delta > -60$. The large green circles are as determined from secondary calibrator observations. The red points are those suggested by GEN_CALIB_MERGE processing of tertiary calibrators. The blue crosses represent the final calibration table. The delay offset is in units of 54 ms.

After the scanning interleaves had been partially calibrated using known sources from the AT calibrator catalog, and newly discovered sources from within the scans themselves, maps of the sky were created. The creation of these maps and the source retrieval methods are outlined in sections 3.5 and 3.8 respectively. The sources obtained from the sky maps were less likely to be spurious and had better fluxes and positions. Strong sources ($S_{20} \geq 100$ mJy $\text{SNR} \geq 5$) from the sky maps were used to further constrain the calibration table using GEN_CALIB_MERGE. It is from this calibration stage that the candidate source lists, that were used to guide the follow up

observations, were created (for the years after 2004).

Once the follow up observations of the AT20G survey had been completed and a list of confirmed sources had been created, a final round of calibration was done using the improved positions and fluxes of all the sources with $\text{SNR} \geq 5$. It is from this final round of calibration that the catalog presented in section 3.6 was created.

3.4.3 Flux Calibration

In the calibration scheme outlined in the previous sections, the primary focus is on timing calibration. Whilst the calibration tables themselves contain both delay and amplitude calibration measures, the stability of the correlators meant that the primary calibrator was enough to ensure that fluxes were as correct as could be expected from the relatively short observation time of each source. For a typical source in the interior regions of a map that has no flagged data, there will be 6 observations of 54 ms each. Three in a northward scanning interleave and three in a southward scanning interleave. This gives a total integration time of 0.324 ms and with a T_{sys} of 300–400 Jy, equation 2.2 gives a sensitivity of 10 – 14 mJy.

In the time between the scanning survey observations and the follow-up confirmation observations the true flux scale for a particular regions was not accurately known. However, the stability of the WBAC meant that the flux scale within a declination band was constant. When scheduling the follow-up observations, the strongest sources were given higher preference so that, in the absence of clustering, they were observed before the weaker sources. Once the follow-up observations were complete and the data had been reduced it was then possible to scale the scanning survey fluxes to that of the follow-up observations. This re-scaling does not add any extra information to any of the sources within the follow-up catalog, but it is useful when computing the completeness of the two surveys as discussed in section 3.10.

Figure 3.12 shows a comparison between the follow-up survey catalog (FSC) fluxes and the scanning survey fluxes as a function of declination. The scatter in the flux ratio is due to the fact that the follow up observations were much more sensitive and have better (u, v) coverage, allowing for a more accurate measure of the flux. The variation between regions that were observed contiguously is much less than that of regions that were observed in different years. In each year of observations the source 1921-293 was used as the bandpass calibrator. The exception to this is 2007 ($0^\circ \geq \delta \geq -15^\circ$) where 0003-066 was substituted since the observation of 1921-293 for that year did not encompass enough of the primary beam response to obtain a good band-pass calibration. The flux of the band-pass calibrator sets the flux scale for each particular region, if the flux of 1921-293 is accurately known then the flux scale should be unity. The flux of 1921-293 varies slowly enough that it possible to interpolate the observations of the AT calibrator monitoring project to obtain an accurate flux. The flux history for 1921-293 is show in figure 3.13. There is no evidence for any significant structure of 1921-293 at any of the frequencies between 18-22 GHz, so the $\sim 20\%$ variation in flux seen is due to the intrinsic variability of the source and also the different frequencies at which the observations were taken. Any discrepancy in the primary calibrator flux will result in a change in the flux scale for a particular years' observations and cause the variation seen in figure 3.12. For the observing years of 2004 and 2005, the declination zones observed show a flux scale that is consistent to within a 1σ deviation. The region $-70^\circ \geq \delta \geq -80^\circ$ has a flux scale that is lower than the rest of the 2005 observations, but remains consistent to within 1σ .

Figure 3.12 : Ratio of follow-up survey catalog and scanning survey fluxes. The horizontal black lines represent the mean flux ratio for each declination band, the values of which are printed below the data. The red lines represent a 1σ deviation from the mean. The mean flux ratios were used to bring the survey map flux scale in line with the more reliable follow-up observations. The year of scanning observations is given at the top of each declination band.

Figure 3.13 : Flux history for the primary calibrator 1921-293, as reported by the AT calibrator database. The blue triangles along the lower section of the plot represent the times during which the AT20G scanning observations were carried out. Observations were not all taken with the same array configuration, and vary between 18-22 GHz.

The cause for the lower flux scale in this region is thought to be due to the rapid change in both the linear scale, and sky coverage between the northern to southern boundaries of the maps. This effect is evident within the $-80^\circ \geq \delta \geq -90^\circ$ map of the sky, where the flux scale changes by an order of magnitude between the northern and southern boundaries. As the south pole region has not yet been completed this hypothesis cannot be tested.

3.5 Imaging the sky

Once a suitable calibration scheme had been developed as described in section 3.4, it was then possible to combine the scanning interleaves to produce a map of the sky. Due to the non-uniform spacing of the delays within the correlator it was not possible to create a map using standard Fourier inversion techniques as given in most software packages, without introducing a correlated noise signal. As outlined in section 3.4.1 new programs were built to process the scanning interleave data and produce maps of the sky.

As each part of the sky falls within the primary beam of more than one observation (see figure 3.5) it was necessary to create an auxiliary map of weights that would allow the maps to be normalised once all of the observations had been processed. Pixels were weighted according to their distance from the beam center, and the weights were scaled so that a pixel that was observed at the beam center had a value of 1. By scaling the weights in this manner it was possible to use this auxiliary map to determine how well each part of the sky had been covered by the scanning observations. This sky coverage map was used to give quantitative confidence levels in the source detection stage (section 3.8), as well as serving as a way to determine the survey sky coverage (section 3.7).

Figure 3.14 : **Left:** A histogram of pixel values for a map at low galactic latitude. The histogram has a tail extending out to ± 10 Jy. **Right:** A similar histogram for a map away from the Galactic Plane. For clarity only the central region of has been plotted. The green line is the map rms as calculated with IMHIST unconstrained. The blue line is the noise rms as calculated with IMHIST constrained to pixel values of $-0.05 \text{ Jy} < S_{20} < 0.05 \text{ Jy}$. By constraining IMHIST, the map rms calculation is not contaminated by large numbers of strong sources.

The system temperature, sky coverage and calibration effectiveness are all critical to producing maps with high signal to noise. To calculate the rms noise in each of the survey maps the MIRIAD task IMHIST was used. IMHIST creates a histogram of all the pixel values within a map and fits a Gaussian, from which the map rms is calculated. However, IMHIST makes no distinction between pixels that are part of a source and those that are empty sky, that is, it calculates the map rms as opposed to the noise rms. For many of the maps the rms noise level is not affected by the sources within the map, however when there are many sources, particularly strong or extended sources, the map rms is significantly different from the noise rms. Figure 3.14 shows a histogram for an

extreme case in the Galactic plane, and a typical case away from the Galactic Plane. For the Galactic Plane map shown in figure 3.15, the map rms calculation is dominated by a large number of strong sources that create a non-zero background level. When a Gaussian is fitted over the entire 20 Jy range, the result is a very wide Gaussian that fits the central region of the histogram very poorly. By forcing IMHIST to only consider pixels with fluxes below that of the strong sources the fitting routine produces a Gaussian that is much more representative of the noise rms. A limit of $-0.05 \text{ Jy} < S_{20} < 0.05 \text{ Jy}$ is sufficiently far above the noise rms level ($\sim 0.010 - 0.015 \text{ Jy}$) that an accurate measure can be made, and is also far enough below the flux of strong sources ($\geq 5 \text{ Jy}$) that they do not contaminate the result. The right hand plot of figure 3.14 shows the effect of constraining IMHIST for a typical map that does not have a large number of strong sources within it. The difference between the two rms calculations in this case is smaller than 0.1 mJy.

Figure 3.15 : Part of the map from which the histogram of figure 3.14 was created. The complex bright sources seen here are within the Galactic plane and cause the discrepancy between map rms and noise rms. The red lines are 1.5° from the galactic plane and bound the region which was excluded from the survey (and follow-up) catalog.

Figure 3.16 shows the rms noise level for each of the maps within the survey region. The typical rms noise is around 10 mJy/beam, which is in agreement with that calculated in section 3.4.3 for a system temperature of 300 Jy. The region $-30^\circ \geq \delta \geq -50^\circ$ has a higher rms noise value of around 14 mJy which is consistent with a system temperature of 400 Jy. The variation in rms noise level seen in the region $-60^\circ \geq \delta \geq -70^\circ$ around $\alpha = 15^h$ is due to patching observations that were done using the incorrect interleave number and thus areas of poor data were not recovered.

The resulting map of the sky is still convolved with the telescope response pattern. As mentioned previously a CLEAN algorithm was not able to be used to deconvolve the map as a straight forward Fourier inversion would not produce a map consistent with our data. A specialised source detection program was created that would match sources to the telescope's response to the primary calibrator. Further details are discussed in section 3.8.

Figure 3.16 : The corrected rms noise level for the survey maps. The rms noise level is consistent with system temperatures of 300-400 Jy. Variations within a declination band are due to variations in the survey coverage.

3.6 Motivation for a Survey Catalog

Initially the purpose of the scanning observations was to detect individual sources so that more accurate, follow-up observations could be made of the stronger sources. The amount of time between scanning observations and follow-up observations was typically only 2-3 weeks in order to minimize the effects of source variability. This required that the calibration and production of candidate source lists be done as quickly as possible. The lists of candidate sources obtained from the scanning data were used only as an intermediary between scanning and follow-up observations. The fluxes and positions had low accuracy and early on in the survey the candidate sources were often spurious. If the accuracy of the positions and fluxes of the candidate source lists could be improved, and the number of false positive sources reduced or at least well characterised, then the candidate source lists become a useful catalog in their own right. Once the AT20G survey was completed, the time restrictions were lifted and it became possible to do a more detailed analysis of the map-making and source detection programs. It also became possible to use the final AT20G source catalog to gauge the effectiveness of different calibration and map making procedures.

The remainder of this chapter is devoted to creating the best possible catalog of sources using the scanning survey data from the AT20G. To avoid confusion, the sources that constitute the final release version of the AT20G catalog (Murphy et al., 2010) will be referred to as *follow-up sources*, or as belonging to the *follow-up source catalog* (FSC). The sources that were identified within the survey maps will be referred to as *survey sources* or as coming from the *survey catalog* (SC). Although the FSC should logically be a sub-set of the survey catalog, this is not strictly the case. Of the sources within the FSC 89% of them are also within the survey catalog, the 11% discrepancy can mostly be attributed to the differing ways in which the candidate sources were extracted from the scanning observations over the years, with further details and discussion given in section 3.8.

A catalog produced from the scanning observations is able to cover a larger area of sky than the subsequent follow-up observations and to a lower limiting flux. The reliability of the claimed sources within the survey catalog will not be as high as if follow-up observations had been done, as there is no way to directly confirm a source's existence. A catalog which is more complete and yet less reliable than the follow-up source catalog will be of particular use for the construction of foreground masks for CMB anisotropy missions. In the measurement of the CMB anisotropies, excluding a real source from the mask is far more detrimental than the inclusion of a noise spike, and thus the most complete catalog is the most useful, even when not all of the claimed sources are real. A secondary use of the survey catalog is to identify sources that were excluded from the FSC due to observing time constraints or poor weather. If the reliability and completeness of the survey catalog is characterised well enough, it is then possible to estimate the completeness of the FSC as was done by Murphy et al. (2010).

Instead of detailing the way in which the scanning observations were turned into candidate source lists and how this differed for each region of the sky and what such implications would be, the remainder of this chapter will detail the final iteration of the source detection process as it is considered to be the most reliable and accurate.

3.7 Sky Coverage

As mentioned in section 3.5 the procedure that created the sky maps also created a map of the pixel weights which, when correctly scaled, become a map of the sky coverage. Figure 3.17 shows a region of sky and the corresponding coverage map. The map of the sky coverage reveals a lot about how the survey was conducted and what sorts of problems were encountered. The interior parts of the map are scanned at least twice with a separation between scans being of the order of days, and the scans are in opposite directions. Figure 3.17 shows that the typical sky coverage is around 3 ± 0.5 scans/pixel, with variation due to the way that the different scans overlap at each point on the sky. As the telescopes require some time to turn around at the northern and southern boundaries of each declination band, the spacing between observations decreases and the sky coverage increases dramatically toward the boundaries. The coverage at the turn-around points of the scans can be as much as 20 scans/pixel. When data is flagged for poor quality on the interior of the map, and no patching has been done to recover the data, there is a reduction in the sky coverage at that point. The boundary regions of the maps, whilst still having a twofold redundancy in coverage, have a scan separation of only a few seconds, and thus data flagged for a contiguous block of time removes scans in both directions. The small gap in the map at

$14^{\text{h}}44^{\text{m}}20^{\text{s}} - 14^{\circ}57'23''$ is a result of data that was flagged out due to the presence of emission from Jupiter. When a significant amount of data is lost due to bad weather or otherwise, an attempt is made to re-observe the data and the patching data generally overlaps the flagged data by a minute or more. The result in this over-patching is better coverage for some parts of the sky. This is also evident in figure 3.17 where the coverage increases to almost 6 scans/pixel in some places.

Figure 3.17 : **Top**: Convolved sky map for a small region of the sky. There is a small amount of sky missing at the top of the map due to flagged data. Three sources with flux densities of 222 mJy (left), 286 mJy (middle), and 284 mJy (right) are easily visible. **Bottom**: Sky coverage map for the same region. Areas in white have no data, whilst black areas have a coverage lower than 2 scans/pixel. The effect of flagged data on the northern boundary can be seen. The scan in green is an instance of patching data that overlaps with good data and thus increases the sky coverage for a small part of the sky.

For the most part, variations in the sky coverage do not affect the quality of the survey catalog as they are only small. However there were problems with the zenith ($-30^{\circ}18'46''$ for the ATCA), that caused a lot of data to be flagged at the hardware level and were not able to be recovered. The large amount of flagged data around -32° declination causes the sky coverage to drop below 1 scan/pixel. The amount of sky that is affected is small but the areas of low coverage produce

many spurious sources that make the detection of real sources in this area quite difficult and thus decreases the completeness of the survey.

3.8 Source Detection

The way in which candidate sources were detected using the scan data changed over the course of the AT20G observations. In 2004 the scan data were processed as time ordered data using a stream-based approach. The final candidate source detection of 2007 was based on the scan maps discussed in the previous section. Intermediate years used a combined approach with the detection rate of the followup observations increasing year by year. In each case it was necessary to have a fast turn around for the candidate source lists, as follow-up observations were typically scheduled within 2-3 weeks of scanning observations to reduce the effects of variability. The two detection methods are discussed below.

3.8.1 Stream-Based Detection

In the early years of the survey, before the intra-scan calibration methods had been refined, candidate source lists were required quickly, so that follow-up observations could be done. The quantity $S(\tau_{ast})$ from equation 3.1 was used to identify candidate sources whenever a signal to noise of 5 or more was reached. This method was relatively fast and easy to compute but was not very sensitive to sources that were towards the half power point of the primary beam. Also, due to the lack of intra-scan calibration, sources that appeared in two separate data streams often had position and flux discrepancies. The problem of side-lobe and multiple detections was significant and despite the best efforts of those involved, many side-lobe or duplicate sources entered into the follow-up observations. Once a follow-up observation had been made such occurrences were easily detected. In 2004 the confirmation rate of the follow-up survey was as low as 50%, meaning that up to half of the observing time allocated to follow-up observations was wasted. In 2005 the detection scheme, calibration, and duplicate/side lobe rejection methods were improved. The problem of missing sources that were in parts of the sky not scanned close to the beam center remained. During 2005 the calibration scheme was improved to such an extent that a map based detection method was comparable in reliability to the stream based method, and a correlation of the two results was used as a candidate source list. From 2006 onwards the map based detection method was reliable enough that it was used alone.

3.8.2 Map-Based Detection

As the final maps were still convolved with the antenna response, it was necessary to create a specialised source detection program – CLEAN_PHV. In essence the program works in a very CLEAN-like manner: searching for the largest peaks in the map, fitting to a predetermined model, and removing it from the map (Högbom, 1974). The primary calibrator was used to determine the antenna response which makes up the template against which candidate sources are matched. The antenna response to the primary calibrator 1921–293 is shown in figure 3.18. Starting at the highest peak in the map an iterative process was run where by the template was matched to the peak, a flux and position were recorded along with: a measure of how well the source response

matched the calibrator template, the number of pixels that were within the fitting area, the number of blanked pixels within the same area, and the sky coverage at the source position. A region of the map around the peak was then blanked and the process continued until some minimum flux density was reached. The maps were produced in blocks of $1^h 6^m$ in RA and between 10° and 15° in DEC. The extra six minutes of overlap in RA between the map and its neighbours avoids problems involved when detecting a source on the boundary of a map.

Figure 3.18 : The convolved image of primary calibrator 1921-293, which was used to create the template used in the detection of sources within the convolved sky maps. The lowest contours are (red/blue) ± 0.25 Jy/beam with consecutive contours doubling up to 8 Jy/beam. Primary beam sidelobes can be seen outside of the contours at a few percent of the source flux of 11 Jy.

The searching algorithm does not take account of possible extended sources. For the 30 m survey spacing there is a 50% reduction in amplitude for a Gaussian source with size 45 arcsec, and negligible response for sources much larger than 1.5 arcmin. Deconvolution of the maps was not performed, so any source that is extended will have an underestimated flux. Fornax A, a well known extended radio source at low frequencies, is present within the maps at a level of 50 mJy. All of the extended emission is completely resolved out. A point source that falls within a beam width of a stronger source will not be detected in the source detection program as there is no allowance given for double or multiple sources, however such sources will become evident during follow-up observations. The follow-up observations have an increased (u, v) coverage and integration time, resulting in a better position and flux measurement. The FSC does not suffer as badly from the problem of missing flux for extended sources, although a source with no bright core or hot spots will likely not be detected in the survey maps and thus not make it into the follow up observing schedule and thus not be present in the FSC.

The list of candidate sources found in the maps was filtered to remove side-lobes of strong sources and sources that were detected twice due to their position at the edge of two different maps. The Galactic plane is a plentiful source of extended and close multiple objects of sufficient strength to confuse the source detection algorithm and are not well characterised in the maps. Candidate

sources with a Galactic latitude of $|b| \leq 1.5^\circ$ were thus removed from the list. Areas of the sky that were poorly covered produced many spurious false detections. Such sources were easily identified and removed via the quality control parameters recorded by the search algorithm, which are now discussed.

3.8.3 Source Filtering

Once the initial candidate list had been prepared it was matched against lower frequency sky surveys to determine what limits should be placed on the filtering process to minimise both the number of spurious sources included and real sources excluded. A combination of the Sydney University Molonglo Sky Survey (SUMSS version 2.1 of March 11 2008, Mauch et al. (2003)), and Molonglo Galactic Plane Survey (MGPS2 version 1.0 of August 15 2007, Murphy et al. (2007)) was used to identify sources within the candidate source lists that were likely to be real sources. Whilst it was not expected that the lower frequency catalog would be completely recovered, it was known from previous observations (in particular Ricci et al. (2004)), that almost all sources detected at 20 GHz were previously known at lower frequencies. In regions where the SUMSS and MGPS2 catalogs did not provide sufficient coverage (that is, for regions above a declination of -30°), the NRAO VLA Sky Survey (NVSS, Condon et al. (1998)) catalog was used.

Figure 3.19 : Identification of AT20G follow-up source catalog (FSC) sources with lower frequency catalogs. **Left:** Sources that were identified within either the NVSS, SUMSS, or MGPS catalog. The empty areas in the $0^\circ \geq \delta \geq -15^\circ$ band are where the AT20G followup observations were not carried out due to poor weather and scheduling restrictions. **Right:** The 25 FSC sources not identified with a low frequency counterpart (Table 6 of Murphy et al. (2010)).

Figure 3.19 shows the correlation between sources in the final source catalog (FSC) and the three low frequency catalogs. A source was considered to be identified if had a low frequency counterpart within 1 arcmin. Some FSC sources were initially found to have no counterpart in the relevant catalog, but closer inspection of the survey maps revealed extended sources that were either not listed in the survey catalog (the MGPS catalog contains only the point sources), or that have a

hot-spot that is some distance from the FSC position. Of the approximately 6000 sources within the AT20G FSC only 25 were unidentified (Murphy et al., 2010). This result is consistent with that of Ricci et al. (2004), who found low frequency counterparts to all 221 sources detected at 18GHz.

Figure 3.20 : Low frequency matching rate as a function of corrected survey flux at 20 GHz for the unfiltered **left**, and filtered **right** survey catalogs. The blue line shows the number of sources per flux bin, whilst the red line shows the fraction of sources matched per flux bin. The dotted line represents the random matching probability of 5%. The filtered sources have a SNR of ≥ 5 and a reliability of $\mathcal{R} \geq 50\%$.

The matching rate between the survey catalog and the low frequency catalogs is shown in figure 3.20, where a strong correlation between flux density and matching rate can be seen. This correlation is expected since the number of spurious sources in the survey catalog increases as the survey flux decreases. The anti-correlation with source count is expected for the same reason. The filtering parameters used for the right hand plot of figure 3.20 are explained later in this section.

The correlation with lower frequency surveys was used as a guide to determine what combination of the quality control quantities would produce the largest amount of confirmed detections. The low frequency surveys were used to determine what a real source would look like within the map; a source's presence in a lower frequency survey was not used to determine whether it would be followed up or not so as not to bias the final catalog. Figure 3.21 shows the unfiltered survey catalog source distribution and separates the sources into those that are identified or unidentified in the low frequency catalogs. The raw survey catalog shows features that can clearly be attributed to noise, such as the over density of sources towards the boundary of each declination zone. Variations in the survey coverage are also a cause of spurious sources and can be seen around 18 hours in the $-50^\circ \geq \delta \geq -60^\circ$ zone. The zone $-30^\circ \geq \delta \geq -40^\circ$ contains the zenith as seen by the ATCA and thus has a region of low coverage interior to the map. The overlapping of sources towards the zone boundaries is seen at a much lower level in the matched source plot, which can be attributed to sources that were found in the maps of two different declination zones. At sufficiently low 20 GHz flux densities the correlation between low frequency detection and followup confirmation is expected to break down. For a source to be detected at 50 mJy in the AT20G a spectral index of $\alpha_{1.4,0.8}^{20} \geq (+1.32, +1.28, +1.25)$ would be required to avoid detection in the NVSS, SUMSS, or

MGPS survey respectively.

With a matching radius of 60 arcsec, some matches will be due to chance and not indicative of any real identification between the two sources. Condon et al. (1998) give a probability of 5% for finding an unrelated radio source within 60 arcsec of an NVSS source. The SUMSS and MGPS catalogs have source densities of 30 sources per square degree, which similar to that of the NVSS which has 50 per square degree. Thus we expect that around 5% of the identifications within the middle plot of figure 3.21 are spurious. Figure 3.20 shows a minimum matching rate that is not zero and can be attributed to the same effect. Indeed some of the artefacts discussed are present at a lower level in the matched source plot of figure 3.21.

To distinguish between real sources and those that are likely to be due to poor coverage or high noise peaks, a filtering metric was established with the guidance of a genetic algorithm. It was found that the metrics that produced the greatest separation between the matched and unmatched source populations were variations on equation 3.2. Here S_{20} is the flux in Jy as measured in the survey map, χ is the cross correlation of the source and the calibrator template, cov is the coverage as measured in the auxillary map, and pix is the ratio of good to bad pixels that were within the blanking region around the source.

$$\mathcal{F} = \log_{10} (S_{20}^2 \cdot \chi \cdot \text{cov} \cdot \text{pix}) \quad (3.2)$$

Figure 3.22 shows \mathcal{F} as a function of survey flux for sources within the survey catalog, identified via matching with the low frequency catalogs. The horizontal line at -2 represents the point above which there are an equal number of matched and unmatched sources. A catalog constructed with only sources that have $\mathcal{F} \geq -1$ will have an overall matching rate of 50%. It is expected that nearly all the real sources at 20 GHz will have a low frequency counterpart, however if that counterpart is complex or extended then a more careful match between the catalogs will be required to identify counterparts. For this reason it is expected that some of the 20 GHz sources with $\mathcal{F} \geq -2$ will remain unmatched despite the fact that they are real sources. Similarly not all the sources that are matched at low frequency are expected to be real. In figure 3.22(right) there are 1758 sources below $\mathcal{F} = -2$, which is 4.7% of the 35598 unmatched sources in the same area of the plot. This is in agreement with the 5% random matching rate cited for the low frequency surveys previously. The matched and unmatched sources occupy the different, yet overlapping, areas of (\mathcal{F}, S) space. Using the low frequency identification as a proxy for the detectability of a survey source, it is apparent that eq 3.2 is efficient at separating real sources from noise peaks. Figure 3.23 is the same as 3.22 with the sources matched with the FSC. The same separation of sources can be seen here, indicating that the use of the low frequency catalogs is a good proxy for source detectability.

Figure 3.21 : **Top**: All the sources that are found in the survey maps with a signal to noise greater than 5. **Middle**: Sources that are matched with a low-frequency source. **Bottom**: Sources that are not matched with a low-frequency source. The matching with the NVSS, SUMSS, and MGPS catalogs is a good indicator of sources that are likely to be real.

Figure 3.22 : The filtering metric \mathcal{F} as a function of survey flux for the survey catalog. Blue sources (**right**) are those that have a low frequency counterpart within a 1 arc-min radius, red sources (**left**) are those that do not. The horizontal line represents the point at which equal numbers of sources are matched and unmatched.

Figure 3.23 : The filtering metric \mathcal{F} as a function of survey flux for the survey catalog. Blue sources (**right**) are those that have a follow-up source catalog counterpart within a 1 arc-min radius, red sources (**left**) are those that do not. The horizontal line represents the point at which equal numbers of sources are matched and unmatched at low frequency.

3.9 Reliability

The presence of an apparent source within the survey map does not guarantee that it will be detected in a followup observation. The rate at which false positive detections are made by the source finding program should be taken into account. Figure 3.19 shows the correlation between FSC sources and low frequency catalogs.

To estimate the reliability for each region of the sky within the AT20G a comparison was made between the sources that were found in the source detection process and a low frequency catalog that covered the same area of sky. Figure 3.24 shows how the low frequency matching rate changes with the filtering metric. The rate at which sources are found within one of the three low frequency catalogs is used as the reliability and is denoted by \mathcal{R} . At \mathcal{F} values below -2.5 the fit approaches 0% and above -1.2 it reaches 100%. Neither of these two values are considered to be practical and the reported reliability, \mathcal{R} , of a source is limited to $5\% \leq \mathcal{R} \leq 98\%$.

Figure 3.24 : The fraction of sources that were matched with a low frequency catalog, as a function of the filtering metric. Each declination band has been plotted separately, and they have been offset in \mathcal{F} so that the reliability curves lie on top of each other. The red curve represents the relation between \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{F} that is used to assign a reliability estimate to individual sources. The lower horizontal dotted line represents the spurious matching rate of 5%, whilst the upper dotted line is the point at which half of the sources are matched.

Once the relationship between \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{R} had been established it was then possible to assign a reliability estimate to each source within the survey catalog. Sources that were assigned a reliability of $\mathcal{R} < 50\%$ were removed from the final version of the survey catalog.

3.10 Survey Completeness

The completeness of a source catalog is the fraction of real sources that have been detected above a given flux limit. In theory a comparison between the source catalog and a list of all real objects gives an accurate measure of the catalog completeness, however an *a priori* list of all real objects does not exist. In practice the measurement of a catalog's completeness is done by comparing the catalog source counts with that of a model derived from other catalogs. This method of measuring completeness is complicated as it is sensitive to changes in sky coverage, sensitivity, and data flagging. In general the characterization of the complicating factors is difficult to obtain on small scales and thus the completeness is quoted for the catalog as a whole with notes where there may be significant deviations.

Due to the many calibration steps that were performed at the software level rather than the hardware level, and the relatively static performance of the correlator itself, it was possible to know a lot about how the system responded to a given source. Because of this it was possible to insert 'new' sources into the data stream at the most basic level and then following it through the calibration process. Having this amount of control over the calibration and source detection process meant that it was possible to create an accurate measure of the survey completeness, both in terms of the survey catalog and by extension, the final follow up source catalog.

Survey completeness was estimated in a semi-analytical manner. In order to obtain a set of data that were consistent with the actual observations, whilst including as many of the detrimental factors as possible it was decided that the survey data itself would be used. Specifically, the regions between the detected sources were considered to be an excellent source of data for the compilation of a data set that could be used to estimate the completeness and reliability of the survey.

The injection of sources was achieved by inserting a scaled copy of the primary calibrator into the data stream as it was being processed. Each data chunk that was read was checked against the list of sources to be inserted and if necessary a source was inserted by adding to the data stream a scaled copy of the primary calibrator that had the inverse calibration measures applied. This method is sensitive to relative timing errors (ie. between scans) but not to absolute timing errors. The absolute timing errors are detected via comparison of the final maps to known calibrators or the FSC source positions and fluxes. The completeness estimate is thus assuming that the timing calibration is correct to first order.

For each $1^h \times 10 - 15^\circ$ map of the sky, a list of sources was produced that had a specific range of fluxes and a random distribution of positions. The source positions were constrained so that they were not within a primary beam width of an already detected source. At 20 GHz the density of sources detected is of the order 0.3 deg^{-2} , and as the number of sources injected was around 500 per map, the injected source positions were constrained so that the measured completeness would not be affected by confusion beyond what was expected at 20 GHz. In this way it was possible to create a map of the sky that contained all of the properties of the real observations that would otherwise be hard to characterise and reproduce in a simulated map. Such properties include but are not limited to: sensitivity variations, regions that were subject to patching (possibly multiple times), T_{sys} variations due to weather that were not captured in the calibration process, and data flagging due to solar system objects³. It should be noted that the completeness measurement is

³The Moon, Sun and Jupiter were troublesome for bands above -30° declination

made using only the injected sources and thus deriving a source count model for the survey catalog using the completeness and reliability measures can be done in a non-circular manner.

Figure 3.25 : The recovery rate for injected sources within the region $-15^\circ \geq \delta \geq -30^\circ$. **Left:** All sources. **Right:** Sources with $\mathcal{R} \geq 90\%$. The red bars are the fraction of sources that were recovered from the maps, with the blue line being a fit to equation 3.3.

The survey completeness was determined by first measuring the rate at which sources were recovered from the injected maps as a function of flux. Figure 3.25 shows the recovery rate for all maps within the region $-15^\circ \geq \delta \geq -30^\circ$. To eliminate the effects of noise within the recovery rate measurements, the function in equation 3.3 was fit to the data, where S is the flux, a is the maximum completeness and b, c are shape parameters.

$$\mathcal{G}(S) = a \left(\frac{S}{b} \right)^c \left[1 - e^{-\left(\frac{S}{b} \right)^{-c}} \right] \quad (3.3)$$

Once a fit to equation 3.3 had been obtained for each of the maps, the recovery rate was converted to a source count using the source count model of Sadler et al. (2008) in equation 3.5 as shown in table 3.3. The survey completeness at a flux S is then given by

$$C(S) = \frac{\int_S^{S_{max}} \mathcal{G}(S) N(S)}{\int_S^{S_{max}} N(S)} \quad (3.4)$$

where S_{max} is sufficiently large that the completeness is no longer changing. Although the source count model of Sadler et al. (2008) has uncertainties of 20 – 50% in the actual number of sources within a particular flux bin, the completeness estimate outlined above is sensitive only to errors in the *relative* number of sources within each flux bin. Thus only the errors in the slope of the source counts (α and β) will affect the completeness estimates. The uncertainties in α and β are 3% or less, and when integrated over the range of 50 mJy to 500 mJy the total source count deviates by less than 9%, but this affects the calculation of equation 3.4 by less than 1%.

parameter	value
α	$1.92^{+0.03}_{-0.02}$
β	$2.78^{+0.09}_{-0.07}$
S_*	$1.09^{+0.13}_{-0.18}$ Jy
N_*	$28.9^{+13.7}_{-6.8}$ Jy sr ⁻¹

$$N(S) = \frac{2N_*}{\left[\left(\frac{S}{S_*}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{S}{S_*}\right)^\beta \right]} \quad (3.5)$$

Table 3.3 : The source count model at 20 GHz as reported by Sadler et al. (2008).

Figure 3.26 : The level of completeness as a function of corrected survey flux as measured by the injection and recovery of sources for the region $-15^\circ \geq \delta \geq -30^\circ$. The different coloured lines represent sources with a reliability estimate of $\mathcal{R} \geq (0.05, 0.5, 0.75, 0.9)$. The completeness is given by equation 3.4

Figure 3.26 shows the corresponding completeness levels for the plots of figure 3.25. The effect of filtering is also demonstrated, and can be seen to lower the completeness of the catalog as the reliability is increased. Source that were within 1.5° of the Galactic plane are excluded from the final survey catalog and are thus not included in the completeness calculations. The Galactic sources thus do not contaminate the completeness of the maps.

The major contribution to the degradation of completeness seen in some maps in figure 3.27, is changes in sky coverage. The maps that have a completeness below the average of their region have a different colour. The most obvious are the maps listed in 3.4. In each of these cases the lower completeness is due to data that was flagged as poor but was unable to be recovered during patching observations or that was simply not observed due to weather and scheduling constraints.

Figure 3.27 : The completeness of the survey as measured via the injection and recovery of test sources, at 70 mJy (**Left**) and 100 mJy (**Right**).

δ	α	Scanning data irregularity
-40, -50	8 ^h	half an hour missing on one interleave
-50, -60	17 ^h	half an hour missing on one interleave
	18 ^h	half an hour missing on two interleaves
		one hour missing on one interleave
	19 ^h	ten minutes missing on one interleave
-60, -70	20 ^h	ten minutes duplicated on one interleave
	23 ^h	half an hour missing on one interleave
	00 ^h	half an hour missing on one interleave

Table 3.4 : Maps for which the 70 mJy completeness of figure 3.27 are higher or lower than the region average. With the exception of $(-50, -60, 20^h)$ all maps listed have lower completeness due to missing scanning data.

3.11 Survey catalog

The final version of the survey catalog (SC) is made of from sources with an SNR > 5 and a reliability of 50% or greater. Table 3.6 at the end of this chapter shows the first page of the survey catalog, which contains a total of 7754 sources. The catalog format is as follows:

- Columns 1&2: The source RA/DEC in J2000 co-ordinates
- Columns 3&4: Galactic (l, b) in J2000 co-ordinates
- Columns 5&6: Corrected survey flux density at 20 GHz and the map rms noise (mJy)
- Column 7: Reliability \mathcal{R}
- Column 8: Epoch of scanning observation. Refer to table 3.1 for the precise dates
- Column 9: AT20G name, when the source is in the follow-up source catalog of Murphy et al. (2010)

The typical positional errors in α and δ are ± 15 arc-sec. The flux scale has been corrected to be the same as the follow-up survey catalog, however there may be variations in the individual fluxes due to source variability and the lower signal to noise of the survey maps. The AT20G names are determined by cross matching the follow-up source catalog (FSC) and the survey catalog (SC). The nearest survey catalog source within 120 arcsec is considered to be the correct identification.

Figure 3.28 : Source density of the survey catalog as a function of declination. The three data sets represent sources with fluxes above 50 mJy (top), 70 mJy (middle), and 100 mJy (lower). The excess of sources in the -65° to -70° declination bin is due to the Large Magellanic Cloud.

The density of sources within the survey catalog is 0.37 deg^{-2} , averaged over the hemisphere. Figure 3.28, shows the breakdown of the source density as a function of declination and also flux density. At fluxes of 100 mJy and above, the source density is 0.17 deg^{-2} with the only notable deviation being at -65° to -70° , which has an excess of 55 sources that can be attributed to the Large Magellanic Cloud. The Small Magellanic Cloud does not contribute enough sources to make a noticeable difference in the 100 mJy source density distribution. The source density distribution becomes less uniform as the flux density is lowered, and approaches the 5σ cutoff. This is a direct result of the differing rms noise levels in each of the maps. The quality of the scanning observations, calibration scheme and hence the survey completeness increases throughout the duration of the survey observations. This improvement manifests itself as an increase in the 50 mJy source density from 2004 to 2007.

3.11.1 Comparison with FSC

The overlap between the survey catalog (SC) and the follow-up source catalog (FSC) is 89% for sources with $0^\circ \geq \delta \geq -81^\circ$. Sources that are within the FSC but are missing from the survey catalog are generally in one of two categories: They fall below the 5σ noise level for the corresponding sky map, or they have a sky coverage that is low enough to bring the reliability measure below 50%. Figure 3.29 shows the flux and declination for all the FSC sources that have no survey catalog counterpart within 2 arcmin. The two sources with fluxes above 1 Jy are both extended sources that have symmetric jets that are stronger than the core. The source at -45° is Pictor A, and in the survey maps the north eastern lobe is the brightest component and is identified with AT20G J051926-454554 in the FSC. During the processing of the survey catalog all sources within 7 arcmin of a 1 Jy source are considered as side-lobes and are removed, this caused the core and counter-jet of Pictor A to be removed from the survey catalog. The source at -60° is AT20G J235904-605503. The survey map shows two sources here, but one of them is in a region of very low coverage and was excluded from the survey catalog. The source that did make it to the catalog is AT20G J235922-605719.

Figure 3.29 : The flux density of sources that are within the follow up source catalog (FSC) that are not within the survey catalog as a function of declination. The blue lines represent the average 5σ noise level for each declination zone.

As well as sources within the FSC that are not in the survey catalog, there are sources within the survey catalog that could reasonably be expected to be within the FSC. The survey sources with $S_{20} \geq 0.5$ Jy that are not matched with the FSC are listed in table 3.5. All but four of the sixteen sources fall within an area of sky that was not covered by the follow up observations of the FSC. The four remaining sources require some explanation as to why they are not within the FSC.

	α (J2000) (1)	δ (J2000) (2)	l ° (3)	b ° (4)	S_{20} mJy (5)	rms mJy (6)	reliability \mathcal{R} (7)	epoch (8)	comment
†	08:52:33	-01:17:15	229.1	+26.0	4315	11	0.98	2007	
	11:39:29	-15:53:00	278.7	+43.6	570	9	0.98	2006	PKSB1136-156
†	12:09:05	-00:56:30	281.3	+60.1	1201	11	0.98	2007	
†	16:05:16	-11:39:45	359.9	+29.1	589	10	0.98	2007	
†	16:38:44	-14:15:45	3.3	+21.1	507	10	0.98	2007	
†	16:42:01	-06:21:30	10.8	+25.0	812	10	0.98	2007	
†	16:58:43	-07:39:30	12.1	+20.8	562	10	0.98	2007	
†	17:24:45	-14:44:00	9.5	+11.6	628	10	0.98	2007	
	17:29:20	-23:45:45	2.4	+5.8	1037	9	0.98	2006	NGC 6369
†	17:33:01	-13:04:45	12.0	+10.8	3237	10	0.98	2007	
†	17:43:58	-03:50:30	21.6	+13.1	5447	10	0.98	2007	
†	17:45:26	-07:53:15	18.2	+10.8	969	10	0.98	2007	
	18:03:16	-27:48:15	2.9	-2.8	693	9	0.98	2006	PMNJ1803-2748
	20:05:48	-23:10:30	19.0	-26.1	519	9	0.98	2006	PMNJ2005-2310
†	20:30:14	-06:22:15	38.7	-24.8	512	10	0.98	2007	
†	20:36:40	-06:29:15	39.4	-26.3	610	10	0.98	2007	

Table 3.5 : Strong sources detected within the survey catalog that are not within the FSC. Sources marked with a † are within the a region of sky that was not observed by the FSC due to poor weather. Column 6 is the map rms noise.

11:39:29-15:53:00

This source was not observed in the FSC follow up observations, as it was not detected within the survey maps available at the time. Its position close to the edge of the declination zone puts it in an area of the map that suffers most strongly from coverage variations and missing pixels, so it was flagged as being a spurious source in the initial iteration of the source detection process. It is identified with the redshift $z = 2.62$ QSO, PKS B1136-156 (Ellison et al., 2001).

17:29:20-23:45:45 - The Little Ghost

This source is the planetary nebula NGC 6369. The source was observed during the follow up observations of the FSC. The 20 GHz image indicates that almost all of the flux has been resolved out. The strongest peak found within this image is some distance from the beam center, causing this observation to be flagged as poor due to the large primary beam correction required. It appears in the NVSS catalog with a 1.4 GHz flux density of 1.8 Jy and is also present within the VERA survey (Petrov et al., 2007) with a 22 GHz flux of 150 mJy on baselines up to 70 mega λ , and 490 mJy on baselines of between 100-200 mega λ . The increased amount of flux seen on the longer baselines indicates that this source has a complex structure. The follow up observations have only east-west visibility components and with only 2 snap-shot observations there is simply not enough (u, v) coverage to capture all of the complex structure. Optical images from the SuperCOSMOS Sky Survey (Hambly et al., 2001) indicate a bright compact core with a diffuse ring around it, and no emission between the two. Figure 3.30 shows a radio-optical overlay of NGC 6369. The NVSS

Figure 3.30 : SuperCOSMOS optical image of the planetary nebula NGC 6369 overlaid with 20 GHz AT20G contours in green and 1.4 GHz NVSS contours in red. Optical images suggest a diameter of 36 arcsec, which is easily resolved at 20 GHz with a 15 arcsec beam. The small black + is the AT20G map peak of 92 mJy. AT20G contours are at 25, 50, and 75 mJy. NVSS contours are 150-1000 mJy in increments of 150 mJy.

image (red contours), show an object that is unresolved with a 45 arc-sec beam, that is centered on the optical position. The location of the misidentified peak at 92 mJy is indicated by a black plus. The AT20G contours are consistent with a shell of emission surrounding the optical position, as would be expected from a planetary nebula.

18:03:16-27:48:15

This source appears in the NVSS catalog with a 1.4 GHz flux of 7 Jy, and in the Parkes-MIT-NRAO survey (Griffith & Wright, 1993) with a 4.8 GHz flux of 2.6 Jy. The AT20G images indicate that the source has been resolved out with a flux of less than the catalog limit of 40 mJy. No optical identification is given for this object, and given its low galactic latitude (and longitude, $l=2.9$, $b=-2.8$) it is likely a diffuse Galactic source.

20:05:48-23:10:30

This source was observed twice during follow up observations, but in each case the observation was centered at a side-lobe position. The two observations were flagged as poor due to the large primary beam correction that was required and thus the source was not included in the final version of the follow up source catalog. It is identified with the redshift $z = 0.8$ QSO, PMN J2005-2310 (Sowards-Emmerd et al., 2004).

3.11.2 Confirmation Rate

Ideally the survey catalog sources which have no follow up observations could be observed and the confirmed sources added to the follow up survey catalog. Given that the survey catalog has now been processed using a single consistent algorithm this would make the FSC more uniform in its coverage and more complete overall. Unfortunately the sources detected in the survey maps are subject to variability so follow up observations would not be beneficial enough to warrant the observing time. The historical development of the source detection and follow up observations will always affect the data. Figure 3.31 shows the confirmation rate for candidate sources that have follow up observations. In general the confirmation rate increased as the survey progressed, an indication that the source detection algorithm was improving. The low confirmation rate for October of 2007 is due to a large amount of poor weather. Some of the sources observed during this time were able to be re-observed either later in October of 2007 (labeled as Oct 07c) or during August of 2008. The observations of Oct 07c and Aug 08 were designed to either re-observe sources that had poor data or that were not scheduled due to scheduling restrictions. These ‘clean up’ observations covered the entire sky.

Figure 3.31 : The rate at which candidate sources were confirmed as genuine sources with a 20 GHz flux density ≥ 40 mJy, via follow up observations. Some sources were not confirmed due to poor weather or bad data, as is the case for much of the October 2007 observations

3.12 Summary and future work

Using a novel approach made possible by the use of an 8 GHz analog correlator, the AT20G survey has been able to catalog ~ 6000 extra galactic radio sources in the southern sky. The fast scanning observations and subsequent follow up at 20 GHz and nearly simultaneous observations at 5 and 8 GHz has created a catalog which contains source positions, fluxes, and spectral shapes, that are not hindered by multi-epoch variability problems. A subset of the AT20G sources have been observed at multiple epochs at 20 GHz, which enables the prevalence and magnitude of

source variability to be measured (Sadler et al., 2006). Further observations at 95 GHz for a sample of inverted spectrum sources gives radio spectra spanning more than a decade in frequency (Sadler et al., 2008) and gives a statistical look at the 20 GHz population as a whole. The AT20G source catalog provides flux calibrators for new telescopes such as ALMA (Brown et al., 2004) and enables CMB missions to accurately remove contaminating foreground sources.

New programs were created that allowed for the offline calibration of the scanning survey data. These subsequent calibration scheme was accurate enough that the scanning data could be brought together to form convolved maps of the sky from which candidate source lists could be created. The offline data processing techniques allowed fake sources to be introduced into the data reduction pipeline which allowed for an accurate measurement of the completeness of the scanning survey catalog, and by extension, the followup source catalog (Murphy et al., 2010).

The scanning survey catalog presented in this chapter has a lower flux limit and is more complete than the follow up source catalog, but achieves these goals at the cost of reliability. The follow-up source catalog is $\sim 100\%$ reliable, whilst the scanning survey catalog is $\geq 50\%$ reliable. It is expected that the primary use of this catalog will be to provide foreground masks for CMB missions such as Planck (Tauber, 2005) and the South Pole Telescope (Stark, 1998), where completeness is more important than accurate fluxes or a high reliability.

The completeness and reliability of the survey catalog can be used to create an accurate source count model for the survey catalog and a more accurate estimate of the follow-up source catalog's completeness. This work is in progress and will be presented in upcoming publications (Hancock et al., in prep, Massardi et al., in prep).

α (J2000) (1)	δ (J2000) (2)	l $^{\circ}$ (3)	b $^{\circ}$ (4)	S_{20} mJy (5)	map rms mJy (6)	reliability \mathcal{R} (7)	epoch (8)	AT20G name (9)
00:00:02	-00:22:30	96.0	-60.5	58	10	0.94	2007	
00:00:12	-03:43:45	93.1	-63.6	51	10	0.90	2007	
00:00:20	-32:21:00	4.6	-77.8	160	12	0.80	2004	J000020-322101
00:01:06	-15:51:30	74.4	-73.8	306	9	0.98	2006	J000105-155107
00:01:06	-17:42:00	69.4	-75.0	67	9	0.98	2006	J000106-174126
00:01:12	-00:19:45	96.6	-60.6	53	10	0.87	2007	
00:01:18	-07:47:00	89.1	-67.3	182	10	0.98	2007	J000118-074626
00:01:25	-04:38:30	92.8	-64.5	75	10	0.98	2007	J000124-043759
00:01:26	-06:56:30	90.2	-66.6	69	10	0.98	2007	J000125-065624
00:01:41	-15:41:00	75.1	-73.7	48	9	0.94	2006	
00:02:12	-21:53:30	55.3	-77.6	120	9	0.98	2006	J000212-215309
00:02:22	-14:07:15	79.1	-72.7	78	10	0.98	2007	J000221-140643
00:02:31	-03:31:45	94.5	-63.7	81	10	0.95	2007	J000230-033140
00:02:50	-21:14:30	58.3	-77.5	142	9	0.98	2006	J000249-211419
00:02:53	-59:48:15	313.9	-56.3	104	8	0.95	2005	J000252-594814
00:02:54	-56:21:00	316.2	-59.5	113	8	0.98	2005	J000253-562110
00:03:03	-55:29:45	316.8	-60.3	71	8	0.72	2005	J000303-553007
00:03:10	-54:44:45	317.4	-61.0	151	8	0.98	2005	J000311-544516
00:03:13	-59:05:45	314.3	-57.0	66	8	0.89	2005	J000313-590547
00:03:16	-19:42:15	64.3	-76.7	100	9	0.98	2006	J000316-194150
00:03:19	-19:27:30	65.2	-76.6	129	9	0.98	2006	
00:03:22	-17:27:30	71.5	-75.3	420	9	0.98	2006	J000322-172711
00:03:27	-15:47:15	76.0	-74.1	143	9	0.98	2006	J000327-154705
00:03:45	-11:09:00	85.6	-70.5	53	10	0.94	2007	
00:03:48	-23:30:00	48.9	-78.6	70	9	0.93	2006	
00:03:57	-53:43:00	318.0	-62.0	48	8	0.64	2005	
00:04:05	-11:49:15	84.7	-71.1	618	10	0.98	2007	J000404-114858
00:04:07	-43:45:15	329.7	-70.8	223	12	0.98	2004	J000407-434510
00:04:14	-52:54:45	318.6	-62.8	73	8	0.90	2005	J000413-525458
00:04:15	-07:08:45	91.5	-67.1	51	10	0.85	2007	
00:04:35	-47:36:15	324.0	-67.6	995	12	0.98	2004	J000435-473619

Table 3.6 : The first page of the survey catalog. A pre-publication version of the entire catalog is available at www.physics.usyd.edu.au/~hancock/files/SurveyCatV1.1

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Chapter 4

High Frequency GPS sources in the AT20G Survey

The following is a paper that was prepared for the 4th CSS/GPS conference in Riccione in May of 2008. The conference was a fantastic opportunity for me to interact with so many of the people whose paper I had read many times, and to get some encouragement from the people who I look up to in the GPS community. I would like to thank the SOC and LOC for allowing me the opportunity to present my work, to Elaine for footing the bill for my first international conference, and to my fellow attendees for their friendship and productive interactions. The paper is unchanged from that published in *Astronomische Nachrichten* (Hancock,P., 2008, AN, 330, 180) except for formatting modifications to fit the style of this thesis.

Abstract

The Australia Telescope 20GHz (AT20G) survey was used to select a complete sample of 656 Gigahertz Peaked Spectrum (GPS) sources with spectral turnovers above 5GHz. The AT20G has near simultaneous observations at 4.8, 8.6 and 20GHz, which makes it possible to exclude flat spectrum variability as a cause of a source's peaked spectrum. Optical identification of the sample results in 361 QSOs and 104 galaxies and 191 blank fields. Redshifts are known for 104 of the GPS sources. The GPS sources from the AT20G are discussed and compared to previously known samples. The new sample of high frequency peaking GPS sources is found at a lower redshift than previous samples and to also have a lower 5GHz radio power. Evidence is found to support the idea that the origin of the GPS spectral shape are intrinsically different for galaxies and QSOs. This paper is an elaboration and extension of the talk given at the 4th CSS/GPS conference in Riccione in May 2008.

4.1 Introduction

The Australia Telescope 20GHz survey (AT20G) is the first large area sensitive survey at frequencies above 5GHz. Among the new and interesting sources detected within the AT20G are the High Frequency Peaking (HFP) subset of Gigahertz Peaked Spectrum (GPS) sources. HFP sources are typified as having a spectral turnover above a few GHz (Dallacasa et al. 2002) and thus far have eluded detailed study, due to the very nature of their spectrum and the lack of sensitive large area surveys above 5GHz. In this paper we discuss a group of HFP sources that were selected from the AT20G survey which are good candidates for such a detailed study. All the GPS sources detected in the AT20G survey have turnover frequencies above 5GHz and are thus HFPs.

4.2 AT20G

The AT20G survey used a wide band analog correlator with three telescopes from the Australia Telescope Compact Array (ATCA) to survey the southern sky at 20GHz. The survey was begun in 2004 and observations were completed in 2007. The survey covers the entire sky south of the equator. The survey was conducted in two stages, a fast scanning stage that imaged the entire sky, and a followup stage that observed candidate sources in order to refine flux and position measurements. The scanning observations were done using the wide band correlator setup, and the data was processed using custom software. The images of the sky that were created from the scanning observations were used to create a list of candidate sources that were then followed up in the second stage of observing. Sources that were confirmed at 20GHz were re-observed at 4.8 and 8.6GHz to provide a near simultaneous three point spectrum for each of the sources. Not all sources were able to be observed at the lower frequencies due again to time constraints and also the poor (u,v) coverage available from the ATCA for 4.8 and 8.6GHz at declinations above -15° .

Further details of the AT20G survey and its pilot can be found in Ricci et al. (2004), Massardi et al. (2008), and Hancock et al. (2008 in prep).

4.3 Sample Selection

The AT20G catalog contains a total of 5450 radio sources. Crossmatching with optical data gives a 90% identification rate which breaks down into 65% QSOs, 25% Galaxies, and 10% faint or blank fields. Almost all the extragalactic sources are identified with AGN and are unresolved at 20GHz (largest angular size < 5 asec). Figure 4.1 shows a two colour plot of the 4404 sources in the AT20G which have three frequency observations. Sources that are inverted between the lower frequencies ($\alpha_{4.8}^{8.6} > +0.2$ where $S = \nu^\alpha$) are considered to be HFP candidates and make up around 20% of the sample. Sources that are inverted between 8.6 and 20GHz have been found to turn over before 95GHz almost 100% of the time (Sadler et al. 2008), and are thus included in the GPS sample as sources that have spectral peaks above 20GHz. Sources that are within 2.5° of the Galactic plane are excluded. The resulting list contains 656 GPS sources with peaks above 5GHz.

Figure 4.1 : Near simultaneous two colour spectral index plot for the 4404 sources that have three frequency measurements in the AT20G. The four regions delineated by the x-y axis are identified by spectral behavior.

	Galaxies	QSOs
Number	104	362
Known z	25	75
Average z	0.2	1.2
$\log_5(\text{PW}/\text{Hz})$	24.4	26.6
$\langle B_{\text{mag}} \rangle$	19.4 ± 0.2	19.6 ± 0.1
$\langle S_{20} \rangle$ (Jy)	0.20 ± 0.04	0.38 ± 0.04

Table 4.1 : The properties of the GPS galaxies and QSOs selected from the AT20G survey. The listed errors are errors in the mean.

4.4 Additional Information

Additional information about each GPS source was also collected from SUMSS (280 fluxes at 843MHz, Mauch et al. 2003), NVSS (365 fluxes at 1.4GHz, Condon et al. 1998), NED and 6dF (104 redshifts, Jones et al. 2004), SuperCOSMOS (466 optical identifications and B magnitudes, Hambly et al. 2001).

Optical identifications were taken from the SuperCOSMOS Sky Survey (SSS) class ID. Sources that do not have a SuperCOSMOS class ID were removed from the GPS sample. Redshift information was taken from the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database (NED) and are almost exclusively from the 6dF redshift survey.

4.5 Sample Properties

The 104 sources for which there is existing redshift information, were separated into galaxies and QSOs using the class ID flag from the SuperCOSMOS database. As noted in section 4.6 the origin of the GPS spectrum in galaxies and QSOs is intrinsically different and thus the galaxies and QSOs were treated separately. Due to the small number of data points available for the radio spectra of each object the spectral turnover was estimated and binned into one of three categories: 8-15GHz for sources that have a clear peak around the 8.6GHz data point, 15-30GHz for sources that are inverted but show a flattening at 20GHz, and 30GHz+ for sources that are inverted at 20GHz but show no sign of flattening.

Table 4.1 shows the various properties of galaxies and QSOs within the sample. The percentage of galaxies and QSOs that have known redshifts are similar at 20% and 24% respectively. As expected the QSOs are found at a systematically higher redshift than the galaxies and have a 5GHz radio power that is 2 orders of magnitude stronger. There is a clear difference between the 20GHz flux density of the galaxies and QSOs with QSOs being found at much higher flux levels on average. If this trend is borne out in future surveys then we can expect to find many more galaxies as the fainter radio sources are probed at 20GHz.

Figure 4.2 shows the redshift distribution of GPS sources as a function of spectral behavior. In any sample of sources that is defined by a selection frequency, the GPS sources that are found within the sample will have the observed peak closer to the selection frequency. This is because sources that peak further from the selection frequency will appear fainter and are thus less likely to be

Figure 4.2 : Redshift as a function of spectral turnover. Galaxies are shown by squares and QSOs by triangles.

Figure 4.3 : Distribution of the flux density at the spectral peak, S_p , for galaxies and QSOs.

	Master list	This paper
Typical Peak	1-5GHz	8-15GHz
Number of sources ¹	172 (136)	656 (466)
Galaxy / QSO percent	58 / 42	23 / 77
Average z	0.5 / 1.9	0.2 / 1.2
Typical log P ₅ (W/Hz)	26.3 / 27.7 ²	24.4 / 26.6

Table 4.2 : A comparison of the master list of GPS sources presented by Labiano et al. 2007, and the sources presented in this paper. ¹Only sources with optical identifications (numbered in parenthesis) are used in the calculations of this table. ²Only sources with a listed redshift and 5GHz flux density were included in this calculation (89 in total).

detected. The lower redshift of the higher frequency turnover sources that is common to both the QSOs and galaxies in figure 4.2 is consistent with that which is expected from the shape of their spectrum. The separation in redshift between galaxies and QSOs is due to their differing volume density and luminosity. We do not expect to see as many GPS galaxies at high redshift because they are less luminous and thus not as likely to be seen in a flux limited sample of sources. We do not expect to see as many QSOs at low redshift because of their relatively low volume density.

Figure 4.3 shows the estimated peak flux density distribution for galaxies and QSOs. As with the spectral peak, not enough spectral information was available to reliably fit the spectrum so the peak flux density was estimated by eye. The distribution of the GPS galaxies and QSOs are quite different, with the galaxies being more sharply peaked around 0.1 to 0.35 Jy estimated peak flux and QSOs being more broadly peaked around 0.35 to 1 Jy estimated peak flux. Each of the GPS sources considered in this paper were classified as either galaxy or QSO by adopting the SSS class ID as stated in section 4.4. This classification was done largely automatically and was based on whether or not the sources were resolved on various optical plates and is not influenced by optical magnitude, redshift or any spectral behavior. This clear separation of the two groups of sources in figure 4.3 shows that there are two populations of sources, and not just the same population viewed at different distances.

It should be noted that figure 4.3 shows only the sources for which redshifts are known. Whilst the total fraction of sources with known redshifts is the same for galaxies and QSOs, the distribution of known redshifts is not the same within each of the samples. The percentage of QSOs with known redshift increases with S_p and may be biasing the peak of figure 4.3 in the same direction. The fraction of galaxies with known redshift does not show any such correlation. The width of the two distributions would not be affected by such a bias, only the location of the peak.

4.6 Comparison to known GPS samples

Previous GPS studies have contained mainly sources with spectral turnovers below 5GHz. The updated GPS master list of Labiano et al. (2007)¹ (hereafter master list) contains the most complete listing of GPS and HFP sources currently known. The master list consists of 172 sources with 79 of these identified as galaxies and 57 as QSO. A summary of the master list and the sources in this paper is shown in table 4.2.

¹Online at http://damir.iem.csic.es/~labiano/GPSlist/GPS_List.txt, accessed 2008 August 11

The master list contains mostly sources from the northern hemisphere due to the increased availability of large area surveys in the northern hemisphere, however there are 57 southern hemisphere sources present in the master list. Only three of the master lists' southern hemisphere sources have a listed peak above 5GHz (0745-004 at 5.8GHz, 1522-2730 at 5.8GHz, and 1837-7108 at 8.2 GHz). The AT20G survey does not have 4.8 or 8.6GHz observations for sources above -15° declination so 0745-004 is not included in the AT20G sample. 1522-2730 is present in both samples and peaks in the 8-15GHz bin. 1837-7108 is seen in the AT20G survey but has a steep spectrum with $\alpha = -0.27$, and is identified with a QSO at redshift 1.35.

While GPS sources are generally the least variable class of radio sources (O'Dea 1998), GPS QSOs are known to have a large amount of variability which can often cause false GPS identification when the spectral observations are not simultaneous (Torniainen et al. 2005). The change in the spectrum of 1837-7108 may be due to the non simultaneous observations used in the initial classification.

Taking the master list as a representative sample of previously known GPS sources we can see that the sources detected in the AT20G survey differ in a number of ways. The typical peak frequency of the AT20G selected sources is much higher than the master list, which is expected since the AT20G will not detect any sources with peaks below 5GHz. The number of sources in the AT20G selected sample is about four times larger than the master list, but the amount of information known about each object is much less than the more well studied sources of the master list. The galaxy to QSO ratio of the two samples are also quite different with the master list having slightly more galaxies than QSOs and the AT20G sample having about three times as many QSOs as galaxies. This change in galaxy to quasar ratio has been noted previously by Stanghellini (2003), among others. The fraction of galaxies in a sample of GPS sources is seen to increase as the turnover frequency decreases even into the Compact Steep Spectrum radio sources that can be thought of as GPS sources with a peak frequency below our detection limit. This supports the idea that the GPS emission from galaxies and quasars are intrinsically different, with the quasar emission originating from the core and that of galaxies from micro lobes and hot spots. The AT20G selected sample of sources are at lower redshift and 5GHz radio power than those in the master list. Galaxies at low radio power and redshift are under represented in current GPS samples and correspond to stages of radio source evolution that precede the currently studied sample of sources.

4.7 Observations at 40 and 95GHz

In November 2007 a sample of sources from the AT20G catalog were observed at 40 and 95GHz at the ATCA. The observations were a continuation of the 95GHz study of Sadler et al. (2008), and contained a subset of GPS sources from this paper. The GPS sources were selected to be inverted or to be turning over around 20GHz, and to have a 20GHz flux or spectral index that put their predicted higher frequency fluxes within detection limits. In total 21 sources were observed. With an increased knowledge of the source spectra, the estimated spectral turnover frequency and flux density were able to be fitted using the GPS spectrum of Snellen et al. (1998):

$$S_\nu = \frac{S_p}{1 - e^{-1}} \left(\frac{\nu}{\nu_p} \right)^k \left(1 - e^{-\left(\frac{\nu}{\nu_p} \right)^{l-k}} \right) \quad (4.1)$$

Where: ν_p and S_p are the peak frequency and flux density, and k and l are the optically thick and thin spectral indices.

Figure 4.4 : The galaxy 1818-5508 at a redshift of 0.07. The dotted line is a fit to equation 4.1.

Observations of a number of these sources at the ESO NTT (images and spectra) and Siding Spring Observatory 2.3m telescope (spectra only), as well as data from the literature, are collected and used to probe the dynamics of the radio source. Figure 4.4 shows one such source. The results of these observations will be discussed in more detail in Hancock et al. (2009 in prep).

4.8 Conclusions and Future Work

The AT20G survey has been used to select a complete sample of 656 GPS sources using near simultaneous observations at 4.8, 8.6 and 20GHz. The 361 QSOs and 104 galaxies within this sample are found to be at lower redshifts and lower radio power than those listed in the master list of Labiano et al. (2007), and support the idea that the origins of the GPS spectra are intrinsically different for galaxies and QSOs. Contamination of the GPS sample by variable sources was limited by the near simultaneous nature of the observations, resulting in the largest list of genuine HFP GPS sources so far discovered. Future work to be done on the sample includes: eVLBI observations of a sample of low redshift, low radio power galaxies to probe their milliarcsecond structure; 40 and 95GHz observations of inverted and HFP galaxies; and a program to expand the number of known redshifts.

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Chapter 5

e-VLBI observations of GHz-Peaked Spectrum (GPS) radio sources in nearby galaxies from the AT20G survey

This chapter consists of a paper that has been published in the Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society (Hancock, Tingay, Sadler, Phillips & Deller, 2009). The e-VLBI observations and data reduction were carried out by Steven Tingay, Chris Phillips and Adam Deller to whom I am very grateful. I prepared the paper with input from: Steven Tingay for the observations, Adam Deller for the data reduction, and Elaine Sadler for some extra notes on individual sources. The images and tables are of my own work with the exception of figure 5.1 which was supplied by Steven Tingay. The images and tables have been reformatted from the original MNRAS style to be more consistent with this thesis but the paper is otherwise unchanged.

Abstract

GHz-peaked spectrum (GPS) radio sources are thought to be young objects which later evolve into FR-I and FR-II radio galaxies. We have used the Australia Telescope 20 GHz (AT20G) survey catalogue to select a uniform sample of GPS sources with spectral peaks above 5 GHz, which should represent the youngest members of this class. In this paper, we present *e*-VLBI observations of ten such objects which are associated with nearby ($z < 0.15$) galaxies and so represent a new population of local, low-power GPS sources. Our *e*-VLBI observations were carried out at 4.8 GHz with the Australia Telescope Long Baseline Array (LBA) using a real-time software correlator. All ten sources were detected, and were unresolved on scales of ~ 100 mas, implying that they are typically less than 100 pc in linear size.

5.1 Introduction

Gigahertz-Peaked Spectrum (GPS) radio sources are characterized by a spectral peak and turnover at frequencies above 1 GHz. They were identified as early as 1966 (Kellerman 1966), and are thought to be the progenitors of large radio galaxies (O’Dea 1998). The spectral turnover is usually attributed to synchrotron self-absorption, although free-free absorption plays a role in some sources (Tingay & de Kool 2003, Vermeulen et al. 2003).

Interactions between the central AGN and its host galaxy are especially important in the younger sources, as the host ISM plays a large role in the evolution of the radio source. In the evolutionary scenario (Snellen et al. 2000), the peak of the radio spectrum progressively moves toward lower frequencies as the source evolves. Most current samples of GPS sources are dominated by sources which peak below 5 GHz, and so are either at large redshift or have moved beyond the earliest stages of evolution.

Recently two very nearby ($d \sim 19$ Mpc) galaxies, NGC 1052 (Vermeulen et al. 2003) and IC 1459 (Tingay, Edwards & Tzioumis 2003) have been shown to be GPS radio sources. The turnover frequency of the overall spectrum is close to 2.5 GHz for IC 1459 and 10 GHz for NGC 1052. The radio sources within these galaxies are relatively low-powered ($\sim 10^{22}$ W Hz $^{-1}$ at 5 GHz) compared to the ensemble of known GPS sources, which have typical radio powers above 10^{25} W Hz $^{-1}$.

Both NGC 1052 and IC 1459 (in common with the only other known GPS radio source within 100 Mpc, PKS 1718–649) show strong LINER-like emission lines in their optical spectra and have complex gas kinematics in their nuclear regions, which may suggest that the galaxy has undergone a recent interaction or gas accretion event. Franx and Illingworth (1988) note that IC 1459 has a counter-rotating stellar core, which is also postulated to have formed as the result of a galaxy merger.

The GPS radio sources in both NGC 1052 and IC 1459 are strongly jet-dominated on parsec scales, in contrast to the majority of more distant and luminous GPS radio galaxies where the radio emission is dominated by what appear to be the small-scale analogues of radio-galaxy hotspots. This raises the possibility that there exists a luminosity/morphology relationship in GPS radio galaxies, similar to that seen on much larger scales in FR-I and FR-II radio galaxies (Fanaroff & Riley 1974).

While the interpretation of NGC 1052 is unclear, since the radio source shows the presence of large-scale hotspots indicating that the radio source is not young, it could be classified as a restarted radio source. IC 1459, however, has no large-scale structure and could be interpreted as a young radio source. The apparently two-sided nature of the pc-scale jets in IC 1459 (Sokolova, Tingay & Edwards, in preparation) does not favour a highly aligned jet as an explanation for the lack of large-scale structure.

When investigating GPS radio sources it is important to recognize the potential for contamination from variable sources whose peaked spectrum is not at all related to the evolution of young radio galaxies. Less than 10% of the QSOs identified as GPS sources in the literature retain their classification when subjected to long term monitoring and simultaneous spectral measurements (Torniainen et al. 2005). Similarly-selected galaxy type GPS samples are more reliable with $\sim 40\%$ identified as genuine GPS sources (Torniainen et al. 2007). In each case the contamination rate is seen to increase as the spectral peak shifts to higher frequencies.

To investigate the parsec-scale properties of GPS radio sources at the lowest luminosities further, we have used the high-frequency AT20G survey (Ricci et al. 2004; Sadler et al. 2006, Massardi et al. 2008) to construct a uniform sample of GPS sources with high-frequency (> 8 GHz) spectral turnovers, low redshift ($z < 0.15$) and low radio power ($P_5 < 10^{24.5}$ W/Hz). To avoid as much as possible the contamination from sources unrelated to the evolutionary scenario, we selected only sources that are identified with galaxies. The source names referred to in this paper are drawn from the AT20G survey. In this paper, we present observations from the Australian e-VLBI network at ~ 100 mas resolution as a first step in measuring the angular sizes and structures of these nearby high-frequency GPS sources.

We use the following cosmological values throughout this paper: $H_0 = 71 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $\Omega_m = 0.27$, and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.73$.

5.2 Target Selection

5.2.1 Selecting high-frequency GPS sources

The AT20G full-sample data release (Murphy et al. 2009, in preparation) provides near-simultaneous flux-density measurements at 4.8, 8.6 and 20 GHz for most AT20G sources south of declination -15° . This is important in allowing us to identify candidate GPS sources without the problem of variability giving a false spectral shape.

We selected our high-frequency GPS sample from the ~ 3800 AT20G sources which had good-quality data at all three frequencies, since this gives us enough spectral information to identify an inverted or peaked spectrum. All the AT20G sources observed at 5 and 8 GHz were detected at these frequencies, so there are no upper limits in the AT20G sample. AT20G sources whose radio spectrum peaked above 5 GHz, or rose with frequency over the whole 5–20 GHz range¹ were flagged as GPS candidates. This yielded a final list of 656 candidate high-frequency GPS sources with spectral peaks above 5 GHz (Hancock 2009). The 1.4 GHz NRAO VLA Sky Survey (NVSS,

¹Sadler et al. (2008) found that almost all AT20G sources with rising (‘inverted’) spectra at 5–20 GHz show a spectral turnover between 20 and 95 GHz, so we are confident that most of the “inverted-spectrum” AT20G sources will be high-frequency peaking GPS objects.

Condon et al. 1998) and 843 MHz Sydney University Molonglo Sky Survey (SUMSS, Mauch et al. 2003) catalogues were also used to search for low-frequency emission from the AT20G GPS sources.

5.2.2 Optical identification

We cross-matched our AT20G GPS sample with the optical SuperCOSMOS catalogue (Hambly et al. 2001) to search for optical counterparts. Roughly 70% of our AT20G GPS sample (465/656) had an optical identification above the SuperCOSMOS plate limit. Of these 23% were classified as galaxies by SuperCOSMOS and 77% were stellar objects, which are expected to be QSOs. This is consistent with the finding of Stanghellini (2003) that GPS populations contain many flat-spectrum radio QSOs.

5.2.3 A complete sample of nearby GPS radio galaxies

Since our interest here is in the GPS radio sources associated with nearby galaxies, we considered only the ~ 100 AT20G GPS sources which were identified with SuperCOSMOS galaxies. A radio-optical identification was accepted if the two positions differed by less than 5 arcsec. Redshifts for these objects were obtained from the 6dF Galaxy Survey (6dFGS; Jones et al. 2004) and from the wider literature via the NED online database².

Only about 25% of the AT20G GPS galaxies currently have redshift information, and further redshift measurements are in progress. Using the currently-available redshift data, we identified a sample of 28 GPS radio sources which were associated with nearby (redshift $z < 0.15$) galaxies. All of these had 5 GHz radio powers below $10^{24.5} \text{ W Hz}^{-1}$. Ten of the galaxies from this sample (listed in Table 5.1) were observed in our March 2008 eVLBI run. The low-frequency properties of these sources are summarized in Table 5.2.

5.3 Observations

The targets listed in Table 5.1 were observed using the new electronic - Very Long Baseline Interferometry (e-VLBI) capability of the Long Baseline Array (LBA, Tzioumis 1997) in March 2008, at a frequency of 4.8GHz. The LBA stations used were the Parkes observatory (64m dish), Australia Telescope Compact Array (ATCA, six 22m dishes as a tied array) and the Mopra antenna (22m) of the Australia Telescope National Facility (ATNF). The data were correlated in real time at Parkes using a Distributed FX (DiFX) correlator developed by Deller et. al (2007).

The observations were arranged as a series of 5 minute integrations per source, cycling through those sources that were above the horizon at any time. In this way, a typical ensemble of observations for an individual source consisted of approximately 10×5 minute integrations, over a 12 hour period. A typical uv coverage is shown in figure 5.1. These data were reduced using standard

²<http://nedwww.ipac.caltech.edu/>

Name AT20G	AT20G position		K_s mag	z	S_5 mJy	S_8 mJy	S_{20} mJy	α_5^8	α_5^{20}	$\log P_5$ WHz^{-1}	ν_{peak} GHz	Alt. name
(1)	(2)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
J031010–573041	03 10 10.6	–57 30 41.3	13.1	0.082	45	73	89	+0.82	+0.48	23.8	~20	ESO 116-G10
J051103–255450	05 11 03.8	–25 54 51.0	12.2	0.092	92	113	122	+0.35	+0.20	24.2	~20	PMNJ0511–2554
J054828–331331	05 48 28.5	–33 13 31.5	12.9	0.040	31	38	52	+0.35	+0.36	23.0	>20	...
J074618–570258	07 46 18.7	–57 02 58.6	...	0.130	47	63	94	+0.50	+0.49	24.2	>20	SGRS J0746–5702
J091856–243829	09 18 56.5	–24 38 29.5	14.4	0.056	48	51	64	+0.10	+0.20	23.5	>20	...
J114503–325824	11 45 03.5	–32 58 24.2	10.5	0.038	69	91	75	+0.47	+0.06	23.3	~10	...
J130031–441442	13 00 31.1	–44 14 42.6	10.5	0.032	68	104	77	+0.72	+0.09	23.2	~10	AM 1257–435
J181857–550815	18 18 58.0	–55 08 15.2	11.4	0.072	42	53	74	+0.41	+0.40	23.7	>20	...
J220916–471000	22 09 16.3	–47 10 00.3	7.1	0.005	136	161	122	+0.29	–0.07	21.8	~10	NGC 7213
J224506–433157	22 45 06.0	–43 31 57.3	13.0	0.068	74	90	84	+0.33	+0.09	23.9	~10	...

Table 5.1 : AT20G sources observed in our eVLBI run. Positions and flux densities are taken from the AT20G Final Data Release (Murphy et al. 2009, in preparation). Redshifts are from the Third Data Release (DR3) of the 6dF Galaxy Survey (Jones et al. 2009 in preparation) except for J074618–570258 (Saripalli et al. 2005), J130031–441442 and J220916–471000 (both from de Vaucouleurs et al. 1991). Column 3 lists the total K_s -band magnitude from the 2MASS Extended Source Catalog (Jarrett et al. 2000). The frequency at which the radio spectrum peaks (column 11) is estimated from the three quasi-simultaneous AT20G data points. The errors on the AT20G flux density measurements are typically ~5%, giving typical uncertainties of ± 0.15 in the radio spectral index α .

Name AT20G	S_{SUMSS} mJy	S_{NVSS} mJy	$\log P_{1.4}$ WHz^{-1}
J031010–573041	37.3 ± 1.5	...	23.8
J051103–255450	...	44.1 ± 1.7	24.0
J054828–331331	<10	6.0 ± 0.5	22.3
J074618–570258	194.0 ± 11.0	...	24.8
J091856–243829	...	55.6 ± 1.7	23.6
J114503–325824	39.7 ± 2.2	31.5 ± 1.1	23.0
J130031–441442	26.9 ± 1.3	...	22.9
J181857–550815	627.7 ± 21.2	...	24.7
J220916–471000	119.6 ± 3.8	...	21.8
J224506–433157	38.7 ± 1.5	...	23.7

Table 5.2 : Low-frequency radio properties of the nearby GPS radio sources in our sample. For galaxies south of declination -40° , the 1.4 GHz radio power is calculated from the 843 MHz SUMSS flux density and the measured 0.8–5 GHz spectral index except for the radio galaxies J074618–570258 and J181857–550815, where we assume a spectral index of -0.7 for the extended low-frequency emission. J054828–331331 is undetected in the SUMSS catalogue, so only an upper limit is given.

VLBI data reduction and imaging techniques implemented in AIPS³ and DIFMAP (Shepherd 1994). The observations utilised phase-referencing techniques via observations of bright, compact calibration sources nearby to each target, for calibration of the interferometer phase, enhancing the coherence time of the visibilities and allowing the detection of fainter targets.

The typical one sigma image sensitivity derived from these datasets is approximately 1 mJy/beam. The angular resolution varies with source declination but is typically approximately 100 mas.

5.4 Results

Figure 5.2 shows a typical e-VLBI image of one of the sources in Table 5.1, all of which were unresolved on scales of 200 mas or less.

Table 5.3 lists the maximum angular size of each source as measured from the images using the MIRIAD task IMFIT. An e-VLBI position is also listed for each source along with the 4.8 GHz flux density measured from the e-VLBI (~ 0.1 arcsec beam) and AT20G (~ 15 arcsec beam) images. The uncertainty in the the e-VLBI positions is dominated by the phase referencing of the calibration source, and is typically 10 mas in RA and DEC. Note that the AT20G and e-VLBI flux-density measurements are not simultaneous and were made up to three years apart.

The mean flux ratio ($S_{\text{VLBI}}/S_{\text{AT20G}}$) is 0.90 with a standard deviation of 0.22. If we exclude the source J051103–255450, which appears to be variable (see §5.4.1 below), the mean flux ratio rises to 0.94 and the standard deviation drops to 0.18. These results suggest that (i) the nearby AT20G

³The Astronomical Image Processing System (AIPS) was developed and is maintained by the National Radio Astronomy Observatory, which is operated by Associated Universities, Inc., under co-operative agreement with the National Science Foundation

Figure 5.1 : Typical u-v coverage for the e-VLBI observations of the sources within the sample. Each source has approximately 10×5 minute integrations spanning a 12 hour period.

Figure 5.2 : A typical 4.8 GHz eVLBI image from this program, for the nearby galaxy ESO 116-G10 (J031010-573041). The restoring beam is 0.13×0.02 arcsec in position angle -58° , the rms noise in the image is 0.7 mJy/beam and the peak flux density is 36.5 mJy/beam. Contour levels are 2, 5, 10, 20 and 30 mJy/beam. The source is unresolved.

Name AT20G (1)	eVLBI position J2000 (2)	Δ arcsec (3)	z (4)	M _K mag (5)	Scale kpc arcsec ⁻¹ (6)	LAS arcsec (7)	LIS pc (8)	S _{VLBI} mJy (9)	S _{AT20G} mJy (10)	Flux ratio e-VLBI/AT20G (11)
J031010-573041	03 10 10.6 -57 30 41.68	0.1	0.082	-24.7	1.54	<0.13	<200	36.5	45	0.81
J051103-255450	05 11 03.8 -25 54 49.96	0.5	0.092	-25.9	1.71	<0.11	<188	47.2	92	0.51
J054828-331331	05 48 28.5 -33 13 30.00	1.1	0.040	-23.3	0.80	<0.09	<72	24.5	31	0.79
J074618-570258	07 46 18.6 -57 02 58.21	0.0	0.130	...	2.29	<0.05	<114	62.2	47	1.32
J091856-243829*	09 18 56.5 -24 38 29.39	3.7	0.056	-22.6	1.07	<0.06	<64	46.2	48	0.96
J114503-325824	11 45 03.5 -32 58 23.48	0.3	0.038	-25.6	0.74	<0.05	<37	62.9	69	0.91
J130031-441442	13 00 31.0 -44 14 41.51	0.2	0.032	-25.2	0.63	<0.06	<38	58.6	68	0.86
J181857-550815	18 18 58.0 -55 08 15.30	0.3	0.072	-26.1	1.35	<0.06	<81	47.9	42	1.14
J220916-471000	22 09 16.2 -47 10 00.25	0.5	0.005	-24.5	0.10	<0.15	<15	120.6	136	0.89
J224506-433157	22 45 06.0 -43 31 57.44	0.1	0.068	-24.4	1.29	<0.20	<258	56.5	74	0.76

Table 5.3 : VLBI core positions and upper limits on angular and linear size for the AT20G sources in Table 5.1. Δ (column 3) is the offset between the optical and e-VLBI positions. Columns 9 and 10 list the 4.8 GHz flux density measured from the AT20G (~ 15 arcsec beam) and e-VLBI (~ 0.1 arcsec beam) images. * Note that (as discussed in section 5.4.1) this radio source may be a background QSO.

Figure 5.3 : Blue SuperCOSMOS optical image overlaid with AT20G 20 GHz radio contours at 10, 20 and 50 mJy/beam. As discussed in the text, galaxy A is the AT20G source J031010–573041 and galaxy B has a measured redshift of $z = 0.082$ which is adopted as the redshift of the group.

GPS sources are compact, with $\sim 90\%$ of their 4.8 GHz emission arising on scales smaller than 100–200 pc, and (ii) most of these sources show only modest variability at 4.8 GHz on timescales of 1–3 years.

5.4.1 Notes on individual sources

AT20G J031010–573041

The optical counterpart of this radio source is a member of a compact group of galaxies (Figure 5.3). No redshift has been measured for the host galaxy (object A in Figure 5.3), so we adopt the measured 6dFGS redshift of $z = 0.082$ for the companion galaxy as the redshift of the whole group. None of the other galaxies in this group has a redshift measurement.

AT20G J051103–255450

This source was detected in the Parkes-MIT-NRAO (PMN) survey (Griffith et al. 1994) with a flux density of 53 ± 11 mJy in the 4 arcmin Parkes beam at 4.8GHz. This is significantly lower than the AT20G value of 92 ± 4 mJy (in a 15 arcsec beam), suggesting that the source may be variable. The 6dFGS spectrum shows absorption lines typical of an early-type galaxy but no obvious optical emission lines.

AT20G J054828–331331

The 6dFGS spectrum shows absorption lines together with possible weak [O III] emission. There is a faint NVSS source associated with this object (see Table 5.2), but it lies below the limit of the

Figure 5.4 : J074618–570258 radio contours overlaid on a blue optical image. SUMSS contours (outer) are at 3, 6, 12 and 48 mJy/beam with a beam of 54.3×45 arcsec. AT20G contours (inner) are at 6, 12 and 48 mJy/beam with a beam of 12.7×9.2 arcsec.

843 MHz SUMSS catalogue.

AT20G J074618–570258

This radio source has been identified by Saripalli et al. (2005) as the core of a “double-double” Giant Radio Galaxy. Figure 5.4 shows the optical SuperCOSMOS blue image overlaid with SUMSS radio contours at 843MHz – the total extent of the SUMSS source is 5.5 arcmin, corresponding to a largest linear size of ~ 750 kpc.

This source was classified as FR-I by Saripalli et al. (2005) on the basis of the edge-darkened radio morphology in the SUMSS image. Saripalli et al. (2005) also obtained a higher-resolution 1.4 GHz radio image of J074618–570258 with the ATCA (their Figure 9), which shows an inner pair of radio hotspots indicative of a core-jet morphology with the jet pointing towards the weaker (South-West) of the larger-scale radio lobes. The component identified as the core by Saripalli et al. (2005), which is identified with a $z = 0.13$ galaxy, is also coincident with the AT20G source detected in our *e*VLBI observation.

Saripalli et al. (2005) note that the optical spectrum of this galaxy (shown in their Figure 19) has stellar absorption lines but no obvious emission lines. They suggest that J074618–570258 may be an example of a restarting radio jet within relic lobes.

AT20G J091856–243829

The 6dFGS spectrum of this galaxy shows strong emission-lines of $H\alpha$, [N II] and [S II], although $H\beta$ /[O III] lines are not seen. The *e*-VLBI position is offset 3.7 arcsec north of the optical centroid of the galaxy.

Figure 5.5 : SuperCOSMOS blue image with the galaxy pair AM 1257–435 identified. Galaxy A is the radio source and B the companion galaxy discussed in the text. AT20G 20GHz contours are overlaid at 20, 40, and 80 mJy/beam.

This galaxy has a K-band absolute magnitude $M_K = -22.6$, making it significantly less luminous than the host galaxies of most nearby radio-loud AGN (which typically have $M_K < -24$, see e.g. Figure 8 of Mauch & Sadler 2007). This, together with the relatively flat radio spectrum (compared to the other sources in our GPS sample) and the 3.7 arcsec radio–optical position offset, suggests that the radio emission in J091856–243829 may come from a background quasar rather than the galaxy itself.

AT20G J114503–325824

This galaxy appears in the SUMSS and NVSS catalogues as a point source of 39.7 mJy and 31.5 mJy respectively, suggesting a strong upturn in the radio spectrum above 1.4 GHz. The 6dFGS spectrum shows strong absorption lines and weak [NII] emission, consistent with the galaxy’s designation as a possible LINER.

AT20G J130031–441442

This object is associated with the brighter of the two objects in the galaxy pair AM 1257–435 (galaxy A in Figure 5.5). Galaxy B, the second member of the pair, is 1.4 arcmin away. J130031–441442 (galaxy A) is listed as a shell galaxy in the catalogue of Malin and Carter (1983), who describe it as having “shells NW and SE, 2 companions”. Such shells are generally attributed to a past merger of two gas-poor galaxies. J130031–441442 is also identified with the UV source FC-238 by Brosch et al. (2000), who list it as a SAB(s) peculiar galaxy with UV magnitude of 12.58 ± 0.61 .

Figure 5.6 : J181857–550815: SuperCOSMOS blue optical grayscale overlaid with black SUMSS radio contours at 20, 40, 80, 160 and 320 mJy/beam and white AT20G 4.8 GHz radio contours at 30 and 40 mJy/beam. The galaxy labeled A is J181857–550815. The objects labeled B and C are possible sources of the radio emission.

AT20G J181857–550815

The 6dFGS spectrum of this galaxy (marked as object A in Figure 5.6) shows stellar absorption lines typical of early-type galaxies but no obvious optical emission lines. This galaxy lies between two SUMSS sources, as shown in Figure 5.6. The AT20G source J181857–550815 is at the position of galaxy A near the centre of the image.

The most likely interpretation is that the AGN in galaxy A produces the extended radio lobes which are seen at 843 MHz. The radio observations at 5, 8 and 20GHz from the AT20G show an inverted spectrum with spectral index $\alpha_5^{20} = +0.40$ centered on J181857–550815, which may mean that, like J074618–570258, J181857–550815 is a recently “restarted” radio galaxy. The fact that the radio lobes are extended along the minor axis of the host galaxy is consistent with this scenario, and the 4.8 GHz AT20G image shows a jet-like feature extending roughly 1 arcmin from the nucleus.

A second galaxy, marked as B in figure 5.6 lies close to the centroid of the north-western lobe and may also be responsible for some of the radio emission seen in the SUMSS image. The total SUMSS flux density is 627.7 ± 21.2 mJy and the separation of the two SUMSS components is 1.1 arcmin, implying a largest linear size of at least 90 kpc.

AT20G J220916–471000

The AT20G source J220916–471000 is a well-studied nearby Seyfert 1 galaxy, NGC 7213. The optical spectrum includes many strong emission lines which can be used as diagnostics of the physical conditions in the nucleus (Filippenko & Halpern 1984). Neutral hydrogen was also de-

Figure 5.7 : Relation between core and total radio power at 5 GHz. The dashed line shows $P_c = P_t$.

tected in this galaxy in the HI Parkes All Sky Survey (HIPASS, Doyle et al. 2005).

The radio continuum emission from NGC 7213 may be variable, as noted by Blank, Harnett and Jones (2005).

AT20G J224506–433157

The 6dFGS spectrum shows stellar absorption typical of an early-type galaxy, with no obvious emission lines. The optical counterpart of this source is only slightly extended.

5.5 Discussion

5.5.1 Source sizes

As noted earlier, all ten sources listed in Tables 1 and 2 were unresolved at ~ 100 mas resolution in our e-VLBI observations. Figure 5.7 shows that the radio emission detected by the AT20G survey on scales of 10–15 arcsec or larger is dominated by a central compact component less than ~ 0.1 arcsec in size. The lack of any significant structure in the core on scales larger than 100 pc supports the idea that we are looking at young unevolved radio sources. Even for a very slowly evolving source with hot spot expansion velocities of $0.1c$, a linear size of < 100 pc gives an age of < 3000 years.

For powerful radio galaxies, it is well known that core and total radio power are related (Fabiano et al. 1984), and Slee et al. (1994) found $P_c \propto P_t^{0.73 \pm 0.05}$ at 5 GHz for a sample of 140 galaxies ranging in radio power from 10^{20} to 10^{26} WHz^{-1} . Figure 5.7 suggests that a similar relation applies for the nearby GPS radio galaxies in our sample.

5.5.2 Core spectral index

The distribution of the spectral indices α_{ν}^{g} listed in Table 5.1 is consistent with that of the medium-power sample studied by Slee et al. (1994). These authors attribute the inverted spectral indices of the galactic cores to a combination of synchrotron self absorption (SSA) and free-free absorption (FFA) for sources smaller than ~ 1 mas. For SSA to be responsible for the spectral turnover, the magnetic fields must be either much stronger than previously thought, or well below equipartition values, with the energy in relativistic electrons greatly exceeding that in magnetic fields. Orienti et al. (2008) find that equipartition does hold for high frequency peaking sources, requiring stronger magnetic fields than previously estimated by Slee et al. (2004). For sources larger than ~ 1 mas SSA is no longer viable. Higher-resolution observations of our GPS sample are needed to determine the angular size and structure of the central emission region.

5.5.3 Variability

GPS galaxies are the least variable class of compact radio sources (Rudnick and Jones, 1982). GPS radio sources in general show a low incidence of variability ($\sim 10\%$, O’Dea 1998 and references therein), and many of the high frequency peaking (HFP) sources are QSOs that show peaked spectrum only during outburst/flare events. This is supported by Tornaiainen et al. (2005) who find that nearly all quasar type GPS sources are variable both in spectral shape and radio power with only a small fraction being ‘genuine’ GPS sources. As our sample of sources contains only galaxies we might therefore expect very little variability to be present, but longer-term monitoring is needed to test this. At least two objects in the sample, J051103–255450 and J220916–471000, already show some evidence of variability, as noted in §4.

5.5.4 Extended low-frequency radio emission

At least two of the sources in our sample, J074618–570258 and J181857–550815, show extended low-frequency radio emission on scales of 100 kpc or larger. These may be “restarted” radio galaxies in which the current phase of nuclear activity has been caught at an early stage.

It is particularly remarkable that our GPS sample, selected at 20 GHz, includes the giant radio galaxy J074618–570258 which was first identified by Saripalli et al. (2005) on the basis of its extended low surface-brightness radio emission at 843 MHz. When the redshift coverage of the AT20G GPS sample is completed, it should allow a more detailed study of the duty cycle of activity in nearby radio galaxies.

5.6 Conclusions and Future work

We have presented 6cm *e*-VLBI observations of 10 low redshift, low radio power GPS galaxies selected from the AT20G survey. The angular resolution of the *e*VLBI observations was sufficient to confirm the compact nature of the targets, but not high enough to differentiate between edge-brightened and jet dominated GPS sources. Such a differentiation is required to investigate the

possibility of a luminosity-morphology relationship in radio galaxy progenitors, similar to the FR-I/FR-II relationship. The eVLBI observations do allow us to devise follow-up VLBI observations using the full LBA at a higher observing frequency, to obtain higher angular resolution. The value of eVLBI observations in this context is that fast feedback can be obtained regarding the detectability of the targets, allowing the rapid selection of a sample for more detailed follow-up observations.

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Chapter 6

Observations and properties of candidate high frequency GPS sources in the AT20G survey

This chapter consists of a paper that has been submitted to the Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society. The following people contributed to the collection and reduction of the data for this paper

- 40 and 95 GHz observations with the ATCA were carried out by Elaine Sadler, Elizabeth Mahony and myself. The data were reduced by Roberto Ricci.
- NTT spectra and images were obtained by Dick Hunstead and Helen Johnston as backup targets for a separate observing proposal
- Elizabeth Mahony assisted in the SSO spectroscopic observations as part of a joint observing run.

The reduction of the optical spectra from the SSO observations, plotting of the NTT data, coordinate conversion of the NTT acquisition images, as well as each of the plots included in this chapter were all of my own work. The 2dFGRS spectra are the only plots that are taken from other sources. Unless otherwise stated the remainder of the work was carried out by me.

Abstract

We used the Australia Telescope Compact Array (ATCA) to obtain 40 GHz and 95 GHz observations of a number of sources that were selected from the Australia Telescope Compact Array 20 GHz (AT20G) survey. The aim of the observations was to improve the spectral coverage for sources with spectral peaks near 20 GHz or inverted (rising) radio spectra between 8.6 GHz and 20 GHz. We present the radio observations, but it is just the form of observations of a sample of 21 such sources along with optical spectra taken from the ANU Siding Spring Observatory 2.3m telescope and the ESO-New Technology Telescope (NTT). We find that as a group the sources show the same level of variability as typical GPS sources, and that of the 21 candidate GPS sources roughly 60% appear to be genuinely young radio galaxies. Three of the 21 sources studied show evidence of being restarted radio galaxies. If these numbers are indicative of the larger population of AT20G radio sources then as many as 400 genuine GPS sources could be contained within the AT20G with up to 25% of them being restarted radio galaxies.

6.1 Introduction

Gigahertz Peaked Spectrum (GPS) radio sources are important to our understanding of the evolution of radio galaxies as they are thought to be the progenitors of large radio galaxies. The youth scenario described in O’Dea (1998) relates the spectral turnover frequency to the age of the radio source, with the youngest sources having the highest intrinsic turnover frequencies.

As noted by Tornaiainen et al. (2007) and others, it is important to distinguish between the different causes for a peaked radio spectrum. Nearly all QSO-type objects that have been observed to have a peaked spectrum have done so either due to non-simultaneous observations of variable flat spectrum sources, or to beamed components that are observed in a flaring state. Such sources show a peaked spectrum only for a short period of time and are not related to the evolution of radio galaxies, so are a major source of contamination to any sample of GPS radio sources. Monitoring of sources to exclude variability as a source of the spectral peak is essential, as is optical spectroscopy to identify QSO like sources.

To investigate the properties of the youngest radio galaxies, radio and optical observations were carried out on 21 candidate high frequency peaking GPS sources. The motivation for the radio observations is to identify variability and the high frequency radio properties, including the turnover frequency of each source. The goal of this paper is to investigate the candidate high-frequency GPS sources, and to classify them as being either genuine GPS galaxies, possible GPS galaxies and non GPS galaxies.

Genuine high-frequency GPS galaxies are characterised by:

- A convex radio spectrum with a peak above 5 GHz.
- A compact radio morphology, with a low level of extended flux. Restarted radio sources can show jets and hot-spots from previous epochs of activity. The cores of these sources may still be considered to be genuine GPS galaxies.
- A typical total flux variability of $\sim 10\%$ or less in a year.
- Little or no variability in spectral shape over time.

- An optical spectrum indicative of AGN activity with broad or narrow emission lines or stellar absorption lines, but not the flat, featureless continuum shown by many blazars.

6.2 Target Selection

Sources were selected from the Australia Telescope 20 GHz (AT20G, Murphy et al., 2010) survey’s list of confirmed sources available as of August 2007, and were restricted to $18\text{h} < \text{RA} < 01\text{h}30\text{m}$ to obtain the best visibility during the allotted ATCA observing time. Sources that showed a rising ($\alpha_{4.8}^{20} > +0.2$) spectrum that either remained inverted, or appeared to be peaking above 10 GHz were identified as potential high frequency GPS sources. In total there were 148 sources that met this criteria, however not all were able to be observed due to timing constraints as discussed in section 6.4.1. Previous observations by Sadler et al. (2008) have shown that fewer than 2% of all sources with rising a spectrum ($\alpha_{8.6}^{20} > 0$) continued to rise at 95 GHz, and thus we expect to see a turnover in nearly all the sources selected.

6.3 Optical identification

Optical identification was performed via cross match with the SuperCOSMOS Sky Survey on-line database¹ (Hambly et al., 2001). The nearest object within a radius of 2.5 arcsec was taken to be the optical counterpart. Sadler et al. (2006), using Monte Carlo simulations, find that fewer than 3% of correlations made in this manner will be the result of chance. All but two of the sources were assigned an optical ID in this way. The source AT20G J203540-694407 has an optical ID that is offset by more than the 2.5 arcsec cutoff, as an inspection of optical radio overlays revealed that there were no other nearby optical candidates, and the radio centroid was within the extent of the optical source. Table 6.2 shows the SuperCOSMOS optical counterparts for the sample sources. The B, R, and I magnitudes are taken from the survey catalog, and sources with “...” have a corresponding magnitude that is fainter than the survey limit (~ 23 , ~ 22 and ~ 20 mag respectively). The classification of objects as either stellar (Q) or galaxy like (G) is based solely on the optical morphology. The source J012714-481332 has no optical counterpart within 2.5 arcsec.

6.4 Observations

6.4.1 ATCA 20, 40, and 95 GHz

Sources from the GPS candidate sample were observed in October 2007 using the ATCA in its hybrid H75 configuration. The H75 configuration has a maximum baseline of 82m, and has been shown to provide robust phases at 95 GHz (Sadler et al., 2008). The observations were carried out with a bandwidth of 256 MHz (2×128 MHz – the maximum available at the time), and the resulting synthesized beam sizes were 31, 15, and 7 arcsec FWHM at 20, 40, and 95 GHz respectively. The observing dates are shown in Table 6.3. The 95 GHz observations were conducted

¹<http://surveys.roe.ac.uk/ssa/xmatch.html>

(1) Name AT20G	(2) AT20G position J2000	(3) S_{95} mJy Epoch 2	(4) S_{40} mJy Epoch 2	(5) S_{20} mJy Epoch 2	(6) S_{20} mJy Epoch 1	(7) V_{rms} % Epoch 1	(8) Δt Years Epoch 1	(9) S_8 mJy Epoch 1	(10) S_5 mJy Epoch 1	(11) $S_{1.4}$ mJy NVSS	(12) $S_{0.8}$ mJy SUMSS	
J002616-351249	00:26:16.40	-35:12:49.3	434 ± 38	1150 ± 25	1156 ± 79	1123 ± 43 ^f	<6	2.92	357 ± 18	136 ± 7	24.6 ± 0.9	12.2 ± 1.5
J004417-375259	00:44:17.06	-37:52:59.2	105 ± 9	136 ± 2	94 ± 6	114 ± 5 ^f	7.7	2.92	86 ± 4	66 ± 3	18.4 ± 0.7	45.6 ± 1.8
J004905-552110	00:49:05.62	-55:21:10.5	128 ± 11	204 ± 4	142 ± 9	89 ± 5 ^f	22	1.92	76 ± 4	59 ± 3	-	11.8 ± 1.0
J005427-341949	00:54:27.92	-34:19:49.2	69 ± 6	90 ± 1	82 ± 5	110 ± 4 ^f	13	2.92	90 ± 5	80 ± 4	51.3 ± 2.2	32.9 ± 1.9
J010333-643907	01:03:33.63	-64:39:07.4	279 ± 24	437 ± 9	311 ± 21	323 ± 16 ^f	<6	1.92	235 ± 12	187 ± 9	-	144.7 ± 4.5
J011102-474911	01:11:02.93	-47:49:11.3	<87	82 ± 1	72 ± 4	83 ± 4 ^f	<6	2.92	64 ± 3	30 ± 2	-	10.5 ± 0.9
J012714-481332	01:27:14.87	-48:13:32.1	187 ± 16	276 ± 6	174 ± 12	237 ± 12 ^f	14	2.92	181 ± 9	140 ± 7	-	80.3 ± 2.6
J012820-564939	01:28:20.38	-56:49:39.7	120 ± 10	222 ± 4	131 ± 9	189 ± 10 ^f	17	1.92	141 ± 7	130 ± 7	-	82.6 ± 2.6
J180859-832526	18:08:59.53	-83:25:26.8	<128	93 ± 2	80 ± 5	95 ± 5 ^f	6.1	0.92	71 ± 4	68 ± 4	-	106.8 ± 3.3
J181225-712006	18:12:25.07	-71:20:06.3	<97	25 ± 1	31 ± 2	43 ± 2 ^f	15	0.92	39 ± 2	26 ± 2	-	<6
J181857-550815	18:18:57.99	-55:08:15.0	<99	71 ± 1	55 ± 3	75 ± 4 ^f	14	0.92	54 ± 4	42 ± 5	-	124.4 ± 4.0
J203540-694407	20:35:40.43	-69:44:07.9	<104	106 ± 2	157 ± 10	160 ± 8 ^f	<6	1.92	236 ± 12	188 ± 9	-	16.4 ± 1.0
J203958-720655	20:39:58.06	-72:06:55.0	151 ± 13	266 ± 5	332 ± 22	417 ± 21 ^f	9.7	1.92	244 ± 12	186 ± 9	-	99.1 ± 3.1
J205503-635207	20:55:03.83	-63:52:07.0	<91	28 ± 1	43 ± 2	44 ± 2 ^f	<6	0.92	29 ± 2	12 ± 1	-	<6
J212222-560014	21:22:22.81	-56:00:14.6	<106	64 ± 1	56 ± 3	58 ± 3 ^f	<6	1.92	34 ± 2	28 ± 2	-	<6
J212402-602808	21:24:02.96	-60:28:08.9	<98	60 ± 1	89 ± 6	135 ± 7 ^f	20	0.92	(125 ± 6) ^e	(81 ± 4) ^e	-	33.0 ± 1.3
J213622-633551	21:36:22.08	-63:35:51.2	224 ± 19	354 ± 7	372 ± 25	411 ± 21 ^f	<6	2.92	(281 ± 14) ^d	(198 ± 10) ^d	-	154.5 ± 4.7
J214447-694654	21:44:47.42	-69:46:54.9	104 ± 9	143 ± 3	124 ± 8	119 ± 6 ^f	<6	1.92	94 ± 5	81 ± 4	-	23.5 ± 1.7
J230737-354828	23:07:37.27	-35:48:28.7	98 ± 8	110 ± 2	88 ± 6	190 ± 9 ^f	36	2.92	186 ± 9	112 ± 7	58.7 ± 2.2	93.2 ± 3.1
J233159-381147	23:31:59.43	-38:11:47.3	132 ± 11	316 ± 6	443 ± 30	523 ± 25 ^f	<6	2.92	747 ± 37	592 ± 30	543.2 ± 16.3	429.7 ± 13.0
J234743-494627	23:47:43.68	-49:46:27.8	275 ± 24	411 ± 9	403 ± 27	284 ± 12 ^f	16	2.92	251 ± 13	211 ± 11	-	107.7 ± 3.3

Table 6.1 : Candidate high-frequency GPS sources. Data in columns 1, 2, 6, 9, and 10 are taken from the AT20G catalog. Columns 11 and 12 are from the NVSS and SUMSS surveys. Columns 3, 4, and 5 are new observations from this paper. The 20 GHz variability index in column 7 is defined by V_{rms} in eq 6.2. Column 8 shows the time in years between the Epoch 1 and Epoch 2 20 GHz observations. The year of observation for Epoch 1 is denoted by: a - 2004.75, b - 2005.75, c - 2006.75, d - 2006.83, e - 2007.83. Sources with an upper limit in column 12 are present within the SUMSS survey maps, but are below the 6 mJy detection limit of the catalog. The year of observation for Epoch 1 is designated

Name AT20G	Optical Position		Separation arcsec	— Magnitude —			Class ID
	RA	DEC		B _J	R _F	I _C	
J002616-351249	00:26:16.37	-35:12:48.72	0.7	22.0	19.8	19.4	G
J004417-375259	00:44:17.03	-37:52:58.98	0.4	20.3	19.1	18.9	G
J004905-552110	00:49:05.48	-55:21:10.76	1.2	16.6	15.7	15.1	G
J005427-341949	00:54:27.91	-34:19:49.33	0.3	18.0	17.0	16.6	G
J010333-643907	01:03:33.68	-64:39:07.53	0.4	18.6	17.5	16.9	G
J011102-474911	01:11:02.90	-47:49:10.87	0.5	18.6	17.5	17.0	G
J012714-481332			...				
J012820-564939	01:28:20.51	-56:49:39.46	1.2	16.5	15.7	15.0	G
J180859-832526	18:08:59.75	-83:25:26.29	0.6	21.6	G
J181225-712006	18:12:24.94	-71:20:07.40	1.0	18.4	16.8	16.4	G
J181857-550815	18:18:58.01	-55:08:14.94	0.6	15.9	15.0	14.3	G
J203540-694407	20:35:40.86	-69:44:07.24	2.9 [†]	17.2	16.3	16.1	Q
J203958-720655	20:39:58.07	-72:06:56.15	1.1	17.1	16.6	16.3	Q
J205503-635207	20:55:03.78	-63:52:06.46	0.7	20.2	19.0	18.3	Q
J212222-560014	21:22:22.88	-56:00:14.27	0.8	16.1	15.0	14.4	G
J212402-602808	21:24:02.97	-60:28:08.85	0.7	17.3	16.9	16.5	Q
J213622-633551	21:36:22.03	-63:35:50.87	0.6	19.8	19.0	...	Q
J214447-694654	21:44:47.51	-69:46:54.85	0.1	21.4	20.0	...	Q
J230737-354828	23:07:37.24	-35:48:28.24	0.7	20.9	19.8	20.0	G
J233159-381147	23:31:59.47	-38:11:47.61	0.7	17.3	16.8	16.4	Q
J234743-494627	23:47:43.66	-49:46:27.81	0.2	19.8	18.2	18.9	Q

Table 6.2 : Optical identification of the sources from table 6.1. Optical positions, magnitudes and classes are as reported in the SuperCOSMOS sky survey catalog. Magnitudes listed as “...” are fainter than the detection limit of the survey. Class ID is G - Galaxy, Q - Star-like. Notes: † - This identification was accepted despite being more than 2.5 arcsec from the radio centroid and is discussed in section 6.8.12.

using the 3mm system that had been recently installed on the ATCA (Moorey et al., 2008), and were done on the same day as the 20 GHz observations, which were included to detect variability. The 40 GHz observations were carried out on a separate day to avoid losing time moving the feed translator needed to bring the 7mm feed into the telescope focus. As there is no 3mm receiver on the 6km antenna, the observations were made using five of the compact array antennas in the H75 configuration, with a goal of 3 separate observations at different hour angles to maximize the available (u, v) coverage for each source.

The raw visibility data were reduced using the astronomical software package MIRIAD (Sault et al., 1995). Fluxes were extracted from the calibrated data using the MIRIAD task CALRED, which computes the triple product amplitude (Ricci, Sault & Ekers (in preparation); Cornwell, 1995; Murphy et al., 2010). Compared to measuring the flux densities from images, as is typical, this method of measuring flux densities is robust to the effects of phase decorrelation. The band-passes were calibrated using the strong ATCA high-frequency calibrator PKS 1921-293. The new observations are included in Table 6.1 along with previous AT20G observations and data from the Sydney University Molonglo Sky Survey (SUMSS, Mauch et al., 2003) and NRAO-VLA Sky Survey (NVSS, Condon et al., 1998) catalogs when available.

Table 6.3 : The observation dates of the data for this paper.

Telescope	ν/λ	Observation Date
ATCA	20 GHz	18-19 October 2007
ATCA	40 GHz	18-19 October 2007
ATCA	95 GHz	20-21 October 2007
SSO 2.3m	4000-8000Å	1-5 May 2008
ESO NTT	4000-9000Å	24-29 August 2008

6.4.2 SSO 2.3m spectra

Spectroscopic observations for three high-frequency peaking (HFP) sources were taken during the nights of 1-5 May 2008 with the ANU 2.3m telescope at Siding Springs, using the 158R grating in the blue arm of the spectrometer, without a dichroic. This hybrid setup allows for a large spectral window of 3500-11000Å, with a resolution of $\sim 15\text{\AA}$. Fringing toward the blue end of the spectrum and a reduced sensitivity in the red end reduce the effective spectral window to 4000-8000Å in most cases. Three sources of interest to this paper were observed during this time. The data were reduced using the Interactive Data Reduction and Analysis Facility (IRAF, Valdes, 1984), and spectral features were identified with the aid of the program RUNZ (Saunders et al., 2004), which was developed for the 6 degree field Galaxy Redshift Survey (6dFGS, Jones et al., 2004, 2009). The resulting spectra and redshifts are shown in the Appendix.

6.4.3 ESO NTT imaging and spectroscopy

A subset of sources from table 6.1 were included in a backup observing schedule as part of a program by Dick Hunstead and Helen Johnston, on the 3.58m ESO New Technology Telescope (NTT). Imaging and spectroscopy of the target sources was carried out on the nights of 24 - 29 of August 2008. For each source a short exposure acquisition image was observed to align the slit of the spectrograph, and was followed by longer exposure of 1000sec for spectroscopy. The spectra were reduced using IRAF and redshifts were identified using RUNZ. A byproduct of the observing program is the set of acquisition images for each of the sources. In each case the radio ID was a single, isolated galaxy, with the exception of AT20G J181225-712006 which is discussed further in section 6.8.10.

6.5 Results

6.5.1 Redshift Estimation

For sources that remained without a redshift after observations and searching of the literature, redshifts were estimated. Following the work of Burgess & Hunstead (2006), the redshifts of the sources were estimated based on their B magnitudes using:

$$\log_{10} z = (-3.95 \pm 0.18) + (0.17 \pm 0.01)B_J \quad (6.1)$$

Burgess & Hunstead (2006) also used R magnitudes to estimate the redshift of objects within their sample, however comparison with known redshifts from this sample showed that the B magnitude

Name AT20G	Name Alt.	Redshift	Ref.	Class ID	Spectrum Figure / Type
J002616-351249	PMN J0026-3512	$0.6^{+0.9}_{-0.4}$	est	G	
J004417-375259	PMN J0044-3752	0.483	NTT	G	6.8 em I
J004905-552110	SUMSS J004905-552111	0.0626	NTT	G	6.9 em+abs
J005427-341949	SUMSS J005428-341949	0.11	2dF	G	6.10 em+abs
J010333-643907	PMN J0103-6438	0.163	NTT	G	6.11 em I
J011102-474911	SUMSS J011101-474931	0.154	2dF	G	6.13 em+abs II
J012714-481332	PMN J0127-4813			...	
J012820-564939	PMN J0128-5649	0.066	D03	G	
J180859-832526	SUMSS J180857-832526	$0.5^{+0.8}_{-0.3}$	est	G	
J181225-712006	2MASX J18122510-7120065	0.199	NTT	G	6.16 abs
J181857-550815	PMN J1818-5508	0.073	6dF	G	abs
J203540-694407	PMN J2035-6944	0.875	SSO	Q	6.18 em I
J203958-720655	PMN J2039-7207	1.00	SSO	Q	6.19 em I
J205503-635207	SUMSS J205516-635325	[1]	est	Q	
J212222-560014	2MASX J21222292-5600143	0.0518	6dF	G	abs+em
J212402-602808	SUMSS J212402-602808	[1]	est	Q	
J213622-633551	PMN J2136-6335	[1]	est	Q	
J214447-694654	SUMSS J214447-694652	[1]	est	Q	
J230737-354828	NVSS J230737-354828	$0.4^{+0.6}_{-0.2}$	est	G	
J233159-381147	PMN J2332-3811	1.20	J78	Q	
J234743-494627	PMN J2347-4946	0.643	H08	Q	em I

Table 6.4 : List of redshifts for the sources in table 6.1. Redshifts come from: 2dF - Colless et al. (2001); D03 - Drake et al. (2003); 6dF - Jones et al. (2004); J78 - Jauncey et al. (1978); H08-Healey et al. (2008); NTT - Observations by RWH/HJ; SSO - Observations by PJH/EM; est - approximate redshift estimated from B magnitude using equation 6.1 in section 6.5.1 for galaxies, and as $z \sim 1$ for quasars. The final column lists the figure number for spectra that are shown in this paper as well as the type of spectrum: em - emission lines present, abs - absorption lines present, I - AGN Type I spectrum, II - AGN Type II spectrum.

based estimate was more accurate. Figure 6.1 shows that the model of Burgess & Hunstead (2006) is a good estimator for the redshift for the sources identified as galaxies by SuperCOSMOS. The estimated redshifts are included in table 6.4. The median redshift for the galaxies, including those with estimated redshifts is $z=0.18$, whilst the median spectroscopic redshift of the quasars is $z=1.0$. The sample of sources used to determine equation 6.1 are exclusively galaxies, and thus the stronger blue emission of quasars will result in their redshifts being underestimated. For this reason quasars of unknown redshift were assigned a value of $z=1$. Only quasars with a measured spectroscopic redshift are used in the analysis of this paper.

6.5.2 Radio Variability at 20GHz

The AT20G catalog contains 4.8, 8.6, and 20 GHz flux densities whilst the new observations span 20, 40, and 95 GHz. The overlap at 20 GHz allows for a measurement of variability. Following Barvainis et al. (2005), who use a de-biased variability index which takes into account the

Figure 6.1 : Redshift as a function of B_J . The red circles are sources identified as galaxies (G) by SuperCOSMOS, and the blue triangles are those identified as stellar (Q). The solid line represents equation 6.1. The galaxies are in good agreement with the model fit. The solid markers with error bars are the sources that have had their redshifts estimated.

uncertainties in measurement, the fractional variability V_{rms} is taken to be

$$V_{\text{rms}} = \frac{100}{\langle S \rangle} \sqrt{\frac{\sum [S_i - \langle S \rangle]^2 - \sum \sigma_i^2}{N}} \quad (6.2)$$

where S_i are the individual flux density measurements for the same sources, and σ_i is the error on each measurement, N is the number of measurements, and $\langle S \rangle$ is the mean flux density. When the amount of variability is less than can be measured with the given uncertainties, the radicand becomes negative, and the variability index is then considered to also be negative. Sadler et al. (2006) analyzed the distribution of positive and negative variability indices calculated in this way and found that the minimum amount of variability that could be detected within their data was 6%, and listed all sources with a variability index below this limit to be $<6\%$. This approach was adopted for this data, and 6% is assumed to be the minimum detectable variability.

The 20 GHz variability (and the timescale over which it has been measured) is listed in columns 7 and 8 of table 6.1 for the candidate GPS sources. The Epoch 2 20 GHz flux density is that measured along with the 40 and 95 GHz fluxes in 2007, whilst the Epoch 1 flux density is that measured during the follow up observations of the AT20G. GPS sources are generally the least variable class of radio sources selected at centimeter wavelengths, with a typical variation of $\sim 10\%$ over a year (O’Dea, 1998). Sources that are not related to the evolutionary model described by the youth scenario may appear to have a peaked spectrum during phases of outburst and are thus contaminants to samples of GPS and HFP sources. The level of variability is shown in Figure 6.2(b). For eleven of the twenty sources in the sample the variability is less than 10% on timescales of 1–3 years. The remaining nine sources have higher variability which is an indication that they may not be genuine GPS sources. It is interesting that of the sources that vary more than 10%, 6/9

Figure 6.2 : Variability of the candidate GPS sources. (a) The 20 GHz flux density at each of the two epochs of observation. (b) The percentage variability between the different epochs of observation as a function of the 2007 (Epoch 2) flux density. Galaxies (G) are in filled red circles, star like objects (Q) are in filled blue triangles, the black star is the source J012714-481332 which has no optical ID. Sources that varied by less than 6% are shown as upper limits (empty circles and triangles). The horizontal line at 10% is a typical level of variability seen in genuine GPS sources.

have optical IDs that are galaxies. Figure 6.2(a) shows a direct comparison between the 20 GHz fluxes seen at different epochs. All but two of the sources are observed at either the same or a lower flux level during the second epoch of observations. This behaviour is typical for variable sources in a flux limited sample, with the higher activity phase being more easily detectable than the low activity phase, resulting in more sources being detected in a state of high activity, and subsequent observations being at lower activity. Another consideration is that in general, well monitored AGN show only small flux variations on 1-2 year timescales, with larger outbursts only occurring roughly once every 6 years (Hovatta et al., 2007; Tornikoski et al., 2009).

6.5.3 Radio Spectra

Following the work of Snellen et al. (1998) the radio spectra were fitted using:

$$F(\nu) = \frac{S_m}{1 - e^{-1}} \left(\frac{\nu}{\nu_m} \right)^k \left(1 - e^{-\left(\frac{\nu}{\nu_m} \right)^{l-k}} \right) \quad (6.3)$$

where k , l are the optically thick and thin spectral indices, and S_m , ν_m are the flux density and frequency at which the spectral peak occurs. The SUMSS and NVSS fluxes were not used in the fitting of the spectrum. Figures A6.5(a)-(c) show the radio spectra for each of the 21 sources observed. For sources with low (<10%) variability the SED fit is quite robust, however for sources with larger variability the fit is less well defined. In the cases where the radio spectra remain

Name AT20G	ν_m GHz	α_{low}	Name AT20G	ν_m GHz	α_{low}
galaxy ID			stellar ID		
J002616-351249	29	+1.47	J203540-694407	5	+2.81
J004417-375259	93	+0.32	J203958-720655	26	+0.68
J004905-552110	79	+0.66	J205503-635207	15	+1.54
J005427-341949	53	+0.21	J212402-602808	14	+0.83
J010333-643907	84	+0.40	J213622-633551	30	+0.61
J011102-474911	6	+3.44	J214447-694654	82	+0.29
J012820-564939	85	+0.26	J233159-381147	7	+1.63
J180859-832526	†	+0.16	J234743-494627	73	+0.35
J181225-712006	13	+0.94			
J181857-550815	†	+0.23			
J212222-560014	†	+0.39			
J230737-354828	†	-0.10			
			no ID		
			J012714-481332	89	+0.30

Table 6.5 : The fitted observed-frame turnover frequency, ν_m , and optically thick spectral index, α_{low} . Sources in the left hand column are identified as galaxies within SuperCOSMOS, whilst those in the right hand column are identified as stellar. J012714-481332 has no optical ID. Note: Sources marked with † remain inverted at 95 GHz and so peak above 95 GHz.

inverted at 95 GHz or are of no particular shape, a linear fit was used in place of the above equation. The spectra of individual sources are discussed in the Appendix.

The median value of the turnover frequency is 84.5 ± 8.9 GHz for SuperCOSMOS galaxies, and only 20.5 ± 9.4 GHz for the quasars (SuperCOSMOS stellar objects). As there are not enough accurate redshift measurements to convert all the spectra into the rest-frame, the data in table 6.5 are still in the observed frame. The large difference in median turnover frequency between the galaxy and quasar population may be partly due to the difference in redshift.

6.5.4 Optical Colours

The spectral energy distribution of galaxies is sufficiently regular that it is possible to estimate their stellar populations from the optical colours (Eisenstein et al., 2001; Burgess & Hunstead, 2006). Using the data of Fukugita et al. (1995) the SuperCOSMOS B_J and R_F magnitudes were converted to Johnson-Cousins B and R_C magnitudes. The conversion was done using the B_J-B and R_F-R_C colours of -0.16 and -0.11 for elliptical galaxies, and resulted in a conversion scheme of: $B-R_C = B_J-R_F + 0.05$ mag, and $R_C-I_C = R_F-I_C + 0.11$ mag. The colours were then compared to the models of Fukugita et al. (1995) for a elliptical and S0 galaxies at different redshifts. Eisenstein et al. (2001) use a similar method to show that the redshift loci for different SEDs are degenerate, with different galaxy types following the same locus as a function of redshift but with differing initial points.

Figure 6.3 shows the $B-R_C$ and R_C-I_C colours of sources from the candidate GPS sample with the models of an elliptical and S0 galaxy from Fukugita et al. (1995) shown. The three colour magnitudes within the SuperCOSMOS database are taken from observations that are typically separated by at least a decade. The galaxies that were used by Fukugita et al. (1995) to construct

Figure 6.3 : Colour $B-R_c$ vs R_c-I_c for each of the sources in the sample that were detected in all three bands. Galaxies (G) and star-like (Q) objects are shown as red circles and blue triangles respectively. Error bars are $\sigma_{B-R,R-I} = 0.16$ mag which is typical for objects with $B_J=20$. The black boxes and crosses represent the model of Fukugita et al. (1995) for elliptical and S0 galaxies at various redshifts. Note that the B, R, and I magnitudes were not measured simultaneously, so may be affected by variability.

the elliptical and S0 models are not active galaxies. The separation between the galaxies in this sample and the E/S0 models is in the negative $B-R_c$ direction, indicating that the candidate GPS sources are bluer than the models. The increased amount of blue emission can be attributed to either a non-stellar continuum from the AGN or a young stellar population as a result of recent star formation. The R_c-I_c colour is less sensitive to AGN activity as the red part of the spectrum is still dominated by stellar emission. There is an agreement between the colour of the candidate GPS galaxies and the low redshift end of the E/S0 models which is consistent with the measured and estimated redshifts being less than ~ 0.5 . Some of the sources identified as star like in the SuperCOSMOS database are grouped with galaxies around the $z=0$ end of the galaxy evolution model. The object identified as a galaxy with $B-R_c=1.15$ and $R_c-I_c=-0.09$ is AT20G J230737-354828, and is also the most variable source at 20 GHz. The colours of this object are likely affected by variability, and this source is probably a quasar.

6.5.5 Radio and Optical luminosities

The 20 GHz radio luminosities of the candidate GPS sources are shown in table 6.6. The luminosity distances were calculated using the cosmology calculator of Wright (2006), using $H_0 = 71$ km/s/Mpc, $\Omega_M = 0.27$, and $\Omega_{vac} = 0.73$. The absolute B magnitudes of the objects were calculated without making any K-corrections.

Name	$\log(L_{20G})$ WHZ ⁻¹	M_B	z	Class ID
Spectroscopic z				
J004417-375259	25.7	-21.9	0.483	G
J004905-552110	23.8	-20.6	0.0626	G
J005427-341949	24.4	-20.5	0.11	G
J010333-643907	25.2	-20.8	0.163	G
J011102-474911	24.6	-20.7	0.154	G
J012820-564939	24.2	-20.8	0.066	G
J181225-712006	24.5	-21.5	0.199	G
J181857-550815	23.9	-21.7	0.073	G
J203540-694407	26.6	-26.5	0.875	Q
J203958-720655	26.8	-27.0	1.00	Q
J212222-560014	23.5	-20.7	0.0518	G
J233159-381147	27.4	-27.3	1.20	Q
J234743-494627	26.4	-23.1	0.643	Q
Estimated z				
J002616-351249	$26.7^{+0.8}_{-0.5}$	$-20.7^{+2.5}_{-2.8}$	$0.6^{+0.9}_{-0.4}$	G
J180859-832526	$25.7^{+0.8}_{-0.8}$	$-20.7^{+2.6}_{-2.3}$	$0.5^{+0.8}_{-0.3}$	G
J230737-354828	$25.8^{+0.6}_{-0.8}$	$-20.8^{+2.4}_{-1.7}$	$0.4^{+0.6}_{-0.2}$	G

Table 6.6 : The 20 GHz radio luminosity and absolute magnitude of each of the candidate GPS sources. Redshift and class ID are as in table 6.4. Quasars with estimated redshifts are not shown.

High-frequency GPS sources are very compact ($< \sim 10\text{-}50$ pc) at frequencies of 20 GHz and higher. It is therefore likely that the optical and compact radio emission from the AGN is synchrotron radiation that is being emitted from the same volume and with the same amount of Doppler boosting. This is on contrast to the steep spectrum lobes/jets that are seen in more classical radio galaxies and steep spectrum quasars, where the emission is dominated by lobes that are not sensitive to the core luminosity. If the radio and optical emission is indeed synchrotron then the radio and optical luminosities would be expected to be correlated at frequencies above the self absorbed peak. Stellar emission from the host galaxy would be expected to dominate the optical luminosity up to the point at which the AGN becomes radio loud, and then the optical luminosity would increase with radio power.

Figure 6.4 shows the radio and optical luminosities of the sample GPS sources, as well as a model which describes the above scenario. The model illustrated is:

$$\log(L_{20}) = 25.2 + \log(-M_B - 20.5) \quad (6.4)$$

where the parameters have been chosen to fit the data. A similar correlation was noted previously by Sadler et al. (2008) at 95 GHz, for a sample of inverted spectrum ($\alpha_{95}^{20} > 0$) sources, nearly all of which fit the selection criteria of this paper.

Figure 6.4 : The 20 GHz radio luminosity as a function of absolute B magnitude for the sample. Galaxies are shown as red circles and star like objects as blue triangles. The horizontal line is the radio power which separates FR-I and FR-II galaxies. The solid curve is the model of equation 6.4.

6.6 Discussion

The initial optical identification of the sample of 21 sources was carried out by cross matching with the SuperCOSMOS database. A morphological identification of galaxy or star-like object was based on the SuperCOSMOS catalog.

Based on optical colours, spectra, variability and multi-frequency information from the literature, sources were then reclassified as being: genuine, possible or unlikely GPS galaxies. Sources with an initial identification of galaxy were reclassified as genuine or likely GPS galaxies 75% (9/12) of the time, and sources with an initial identification of star like were classified as unlikely to be a GPS galaxy 75% (6/8) of the time. The single source that had no SuperCOSMOS ID is a possible GPS source. Thus if a sample of GPS sources is to be found, removal of sources classified as star-like within the SuperCOSMOS database is an efficient first step removing 75% of the undesirable candidates whilst rejecting only 17% of the likely GPS sources. Table 6.7 shows the original and revised classification for each of the 21 sources. Notes on individual sources are given in the Appendix.

The optical colours of the source sample were compared to those of normal E or S0 galaxy models. In each instance there was an excess of blue emission suggesting that an AGN or recent star

Name AT20G (1)	Class ID (2)	Revised Class (3)	Notes (4)
J002616-351249	G	x	Likely beamed source
J004417-375259	G	GPS?	BLRG?
J004905-552110	G	x	
J005427-341949	G	GPS	Possibly restarted
J010333-643907	G	GPS	Possibly restarted
J011102-474911	G	GPS	
J012714-481332	-	GPS?	Need more information
J012820-564939	G	GPS?	
J180859-832526	G	GPS	
J181225-712006	G	GPS	Merging components?
J181857-550815	G	GPS	Restarted
J203540-694407	Q	x	
J203958-720655	Q	x	
J205503-635207	Q	GPS?	New radio source
J212222-560014	G	GPS	Cluster member
J212402-602808	Q	x	No optical spectrum
J213622-633551	Q	x	
J214447-694654	Q	GPS	No optical spectrum
J230737-354828	G	x	Large 20 GHz variability
J233159-381147	Q	x	Previously well studied
J234743-494627	Q	x	FSRQ

Table 6.7 : Original and revised classification of candidate GPS sources. Column 2 shows the classification from SuperCOSMOS as either Galaxy (G) or star-like (Q). Column 3 shows the revised class as a genuine or likely GPS galaxy or as unlikely to be a GPS galaxy (x). Notes: BLRG - Broad Line Radio Galaxy, FSRQ - Flat Spectrum Radio Quasar.

formation was present. Where available the optical spectra indicate that an AGN is the most likely cause of the excess emission.

The 20 GHz variability of the candidate sources was measured over a period of 1-3 years. Although the variability was measured on three different time scales there is no significant difference between the variability index for sources in each of the sub-groups, the average being 10-12% over 1-3 years. As a group the sources show the same level of variability as typical GPS sources, however it is interesting to note that in this sample the optically identified galaxies show a slightly higher amount of variability ($13 \pm 2.5\%$) than the star like objects ($9.5 \pm 2.0\%$). The source with the highest variability is classified as a galaxy within the SuperCOSMOS database, but was not considered to be a genuine GPS source.

The radio and optical luminosities of the sample sources are consistent with a scenario in which the two are correlated in the radio loud regime, and unrelated in the radio quiet, for both quasars and galaxies.

Three (25%) of the 12 confirmed GPS galaxies show evidence of being restarted. Such sources exhibit a radio core that is typical of a genuine GPS source, but also show extended emission, hot

spots or jets. These restarted GPS sources are interesting as they show more than one epoch of radio galaxy evolution within a single source (Saikia & Jamrozy, 2010). The evolution of these sources may differ from that of GPS sources that are beginning their radio evolution for the first time. If a merger or star formation history of these sources could be determined then the causes of the quenching and restarting process can be investigated.

If these numbers are indicative of the larger population of radio sources then as many as 400 genuine GPS sources could be contained within the AT20G with up to 25% of them being restarted.

The four sources with the lowest measured redshift in this sample have spectra which peak above ~ 80 GHz, and are all associated with galaxies. This is very promising for future efforts to identify the High Frequency Peaking GPS sources from the AT20G survey.

6.7 Conclusions and Future work

A sample of 21 radio sources with inverted spectra in the AT20G catalog were observed at 40 and 95 GHz to determine their high-frequency spectral shape and turnover frequency. A second epoch of 20 GHz observations was included to measure the variability of the sources. Redshift information was taken from the literature when possible and observations were carried out when no redshift was known. In 7/21 cases the redshifts were estimated based on optical colours.

Detailed study of the 21 GPS candidates reveals that 8 are likely GPS galaxies and 4 are possible GPS galaxies with further investigation required in each case. Nine of the 21 GPS candidates were considered not to be genuine GPS galaxies and do not require further work. Three of the 12 surviving GPS candidates show evidence of previous activity, indicating that, whilst GPS sources are some of the youngest radio sources, a significant number of them have been recently restarted. If these numbers are indicative of the full AT20G sample then as many as 400 genuine GPS sources could be contained within the AT20G with up to 25% of them being restarted.

Further work needs to be done to increase the redshift coverage of the GPS population and to expand upon the number of HFP sources with peaks above 20 GHz.

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6.8 Appendix

This appendix includes the radio spectra for the 21 sources observed at 40 and 95 GHz as well as notes on the individual sources.

For each of the sources the following information is reported, (where available or notable): The optical identification and colours, radio observations from source other than the AT20G and this paper, the radio variability, the radio spectrum, the radio morphology, and other notes of interest. The revised classification of each object will also be given as either genuine GPS or probably QSO based on the criteria set out in the introduction.

The Parkes-MIT-NRAO 4.85 GHz survey (PMN, Griffith & Wright, 1993) is used as an independent measure of flux and to determine source variability. The primary beam of the PMN survey is 4.2 arcmin at 4.8 GHz whilst the AT20G has a primary beam of 2.2 and 0.53 arcmin at 4.8 and 20 GHz respectively. The AT20G does not contain any baselines shorter than 30m and has only limited sensitivity to flux on scales larger than ~ 30 arcsec (Murphy et al., 2010). The AT20G beam is often elliptical at 4.8 and 8.6 GHz and results in elongated radio contours, that appear to be due to extended emission, even when the source is unresolved. The observation dates for the PMN survey sources cannot be determined more accurately than to within the year of 1990, as the survey observations spanned many months within this year.

The SSO and NTT spectra that were observed for this project are included within the individual source notes.

Figure 6.5 : Spectral energy distributions for the 21 sources observed. Red data are from SUMSS (843 MHz), NVSS (1.4 GHz), and the AT20G catalog (4.8, 8.6 and 20 GHz). Blue data is from this paper (20, 40, and 95 GHz). Open triangles represent 95 GHz flux density upper limits. Small black crosses are data from other surveys mentioned in the discussion of each source. The dotted line is a fit to the data of this paper and the AT20G using either the function of Snellen et al. (1998), or a powerlaw.

Figure 6.5 : Continued

Figure 6.5 : Continued

6.8.1 AT20G J002616-351249 - a $z \sim 0.6$ non-GPS galaxy

This source is identified as a $B_J = 22.0$ mag galaxy within the SuperCOSMOS database. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 2.25$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.51$ mag. The estimated redshift is 0.6 but the colours are bluer than expected for a normal E or S0 galaxy, suggesting that an AGN or recent star formation is present.

This source is in the PMN catalog (Wright et al., 1996), the second VLA Calibrator Survey (Fomalont et al., 2003, VCS2), and was also observed by Sadler et al. (2008). The details of these observations are summarised in table 6.8.

The 4.8 GHz variability of this source is less than 6% over a period of 14 years. There is good agreement between the AT20G and PMN fluxes. This source was added to the Australia Telescope calibrator catalog in 2005 and has thus been monitored at 20 and 95 GHz since this time. Figure 6.6 shows the flux history of this source with data from the AT calibrator catalog, the AT20G survey, Sadler et al. (2008), and this paper. The 20 GHz variability is $\sim 10\%$ over 4 years, whilst the 95 GHz flux shows an outburst and decline in flux in mid 2005. Figure 6.7 shows a five year flux history for this source as seen by the WMAP mission. The variability over the 5 years of the WMAP mission is 10, 22, 18 and 38% at 23, 33, 41, and 61 GHz respectively. The SUMSS and NVSS fluxes for this source are in agreement with the fitted radio spectrum of the AT20G, 40, and 95 GHz observations, which given the large amount of time between the SUMSS, NVSS and AT20G observations suggests that there is no significant variability below the spectral peak.

The lack of variability below the spectral peak, and an increasing amount of variability above the peak, suggests that we are seeing beamed emission and that there are blobs of material moving in and out of the beamed component. Beamed emission and a large 95 GHz variability is not indicative of a genuine GPS source. This object may be a beamed source rather than a genuine GPS galaxy.

Table 6.8 : Data summary for J002616-351249

Data Source	ν GHz	Flux Density mJy	Obs Year
PMN	4.85	121 ± 12	1990
AT20G	4.8	136 ± 7	2004.83
VCS2	8.4	<200	2002.1
AT20G	8.6	357 ± 18	2004.83
AT20G	20	1123 ± 43	2004.75
Sadler et al. (2008)	20	1273 ± 67	2005.5
This paper	20	1156 ± 79	2007.83
This paper	40	1150 ± 25	2007.83
Sadler et al. (2008)	95	1155 ± 136	2005.5
	95	1119 ± 132	2005.5
This paper	95	434 ± 38	2007.83

Figure 6.6 : Flux history at 20 and 95 GHz, with fluxes from the AT20G, Sadler et al. (2008), this paper, and the AT calibrator catalog.

Figure 6.7 : Flux history of J002616-351249 at 23, 33, 41, and 61 GHz taken from the WMAP 5 year catalog. The increasing amount of variability above the spectral peak suggests that the emission is beamed.

6.8.2 AT20G J004417-375259 - a $z = 0.48$ non-GPS galaxy

This source is identified as a $B_J = 20.3$ mag galaxy in the SuperCOSMOS database. At a measured redshift of 0.48, the optical colours of $B-R_C = 1.25$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.31$ mag, are much bluer than would be expected for a normal E or S0 galaxy. The presence of broad lines in the NTT spectrum (see fig 6.8(a)), indicates that the excess blue emission is due to an AGN. The broad emission lines and non-stellar blue continuum are typical of a QSO or broad-line radio galaxy.

J004417-37525 is present in the PMN catalog as PMN J0044-3752 with a 4.85 GHz flux density of 54 ± 9 mJy. This source shows no significant variability at 4.85 GHz and is only 7.7% variable at 20 GHz over a period of 3 years.

A radio-optical overlay is shown in Figure 6.8(b). There is no evidence for extended flux in any of the three frequencies within the AT20G. The QSO-like spectrum indicates that this source may not be a genuine GPS galaxy.

Figure 6.8 : (a) The ESO NTT spectrum of AT20G J004417-375259. Flux units are arbitrary. $H\beta$, O[III], and MgII are seen in emission, along with the high ionisation states of [NeIII] and [NeV]. The redshift is 0.483.(b) SuperCOSMOS optical image of AT20G J004417-375259 overlaid with AT20G contours. Contours are: Black - 20 GHz at 15, 30, and 60 mJy/beam, Blue - 8.6 GHz at 10, 20, 40, and 80 mJy/beam, and Red - 4.8 GHz at 15, 30 and 60 mJy/beam. The radio source is unresolved at all frequencies.

6.8.3 AT20G J004905-552110 - a $z = 0.062$ non-GPS galaxy

This source is identified as a $B_J = 16.6$ mag galaxy within the SuperCOSMOS database. The SuperCOSMOS blue image shows a bright core with some surrounding extended emission, consistent with a Seyfert type galaxy as shown in Figure 6.9(b). The ESO NTT spectrum in Figure 6.9(a) shows a redshift of 0.062 with strong emission lines superimposed on a strong-lined stellar continuum typical of an early-type galaxy. The optical colours of this galaxy are $B-R_C = 0.95$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.71$ mag, which is consistent with a $z \sim 0$ E or S0 galaxy with some excess blue emission due to either an AGN or recent star formation. In the SuperCOSMOS image in Figure 6.9(b) there is a possible bright spot towards the southwest of the image, which may be a satellite galaxy that is merging with the host galaxy and could contribute to the star formation or AGN activity.

With the exception of SUMSS there are no other radio observations of this source listed within any of the databases that are incorporated into NED or Vizier. There is no evidence for any extended emission or jet like structures at any of the AT20G frequencies. A 20 GHz variability index of 22% over two years suggests that this source may not be a genuine GPS source, and the radio SED (Figure 6.8(a)) shows some signs that the location of the spectral peak may also be variable. This source is probably not a genuine GPS galaxy.

Figure 6.9 : (a) The ESO NTT spectrum of AT20G J004905-552110. Both emission and absorption are present, giving a redshift of 0.062. The spectrum is dominated by stellar features, indicative of a late type galaxy. The unlabeled absorption feature near 7630\AA is from atmospheric oxygen. (b) SuperCOSMOS blue optical image of AT20G J004905-552110 overlaid with AT20G contours. Contours are: Yellow - 20 GHz at 15, 30, and 60 mJy/beam, Blue - 8.6 GHz at 15, 30, and 60 mJy/beam, and Red - 4.8 GHz at 12, 25, and 50 mJy/beam.

6.8.4 AT20G J005427-341949 - a $z = 0.11$ GPS galaxy

This source is identified as a $B_J = 18.0$ mag galaxy in the SuperCOSMOS database. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 1.05$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.51$ mag which are consistent with a low redshift E or S0 type galaxy with excess blue emission from an AGN or star formation. The 2dF spectrum of this object in Figure 6.10(a) shows OIII, SII and $H\alpha$ in emission, but almost no $H\beta$. This source is at a redshift of 0.11 (Colless et al., 2001).

J005427-341949 is detected as an X-ray source in the ROSAT All-Sky Faint Source Catalog (RASS-FSC Voges et al., 2000) at 3.51×10^{-2} ct/s. This source is identified as being within a cluster of galaxies by Tago et al. (2006), so it is possible that the X-ray emission may be related to the cluster rather than the galaxy. Turriziani et al. (2007) attribute the X-ray flux to the galaxy and list this source as being borderline between a radio galaxy and a flat spectrum radio quasar.

There is some evidence for extended emission in the 4.8 and 8.6 GHz AT20G images as shown in Figure 6.10(b). The sparse (u, v) coverage of the observations means that even though extended emission is able to be detected, the structure cannot be determined, and the contours of Figure 6.10(b) are not indicative of the true extended structure. The 843 MHz SUMSS and 1.4 GHz NVSS contours show a triple component source, with the central component coincident with the optical ID and AT20G radio positions (figure 6.10(c)). The core has a rising spectral index of $\alpha_{0.8}^{1.4} = +0.8$ whilst the lobes have a steep spectral index of $\alpha_{0.8}^{1.4} \sim -1.1$. The steep spectral index of the lobes, and the fact that they are not detected at 20 GHz indicates that they are no longer being powered, and that this source is probably restarted.

At a redshift of $z=0.11$ the linear scale is 1.98 kpc/arcsec, and the projected size of the lobes is ~ 155 and ~ 180 kpc for the East and West components respectively. The total projected linear size is ~ 355 kpc.

A 20 GHz variability of 13% over 2 years is consistent with that of a genuine GPS galaxy. The extended emission is possibly due to either the galaxy cluster, or the restarted nature of this source. This source is probably a genuine GPS galaxy.

Figure 6.10 : AT20G J005427-341949. (a) 2dFGRS spectrum. $H\alpha$, [SII] and [OIII] are visible in emission, and H, K and Fe are seen in absorption. The spectrum is dominated by starlight. The redshift is $z=0.11$. (b) SuperCOSMOS blue image overlaid with 15, 30, and 60 mJy/beam AT20G contours at 4.8 GHz (red), 8.6 GHz (blue), and 20 GHz (yellow). The 4.8 and 8.6 GHz contours suggest that the source may have some extended emission. (c) As in (b) with AT20G 20 GHz contours in yellow, SUMSS 843 MHz contours in black at 4, 8, 16, and 32 mJy/beam, and NVSS 1.4 GHz contours in red at 4, 8, 16, and 32 mJy/beam.

6.8.5 AT20G J010333-643907 - a $z = 0.163$ GPS galaxy

This source is identified as a $B_J = 18.6$ mag galaxy in the SuperCOSMOS database. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 1.15$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.71$ mag which are consistent with a low redshift E or S0 type galaxy with excess blue emission from an AGN or star formation. The NTT spectrum of this object in Figure 6.11 and shows strong emission in $H\alpha$, [OII], [OIII], [OI], [NeV], and [NeIII]. This is an AGN at a redshift of 0.163.

This source has been observed several times over the course of the AT20G survey and related projects as summarised in Table 6.9. The variability is $<6-7\%$ over a period of 1-2 years at each of the frequencies. The radio spectrum of this source has a peak frequency near 84 GHz.

Figure 6.12(a) shows a SUMSS-SuperCOSMOS radio optical overlay for this source. The SUMSS counterpart shows a strong radio core with two lobes. One of the lobes is equal in brightness to the core whilst the other is approximately half the power. The linear scale at $z=0.163$ is 2.77 kpc/arcsec giving a core-to-lobe separation of 235 and 225 kpc for the fainter and brighter lobe respectively. The projected linear size is ~ 460 kpc. The PMN counterpart is 395 ± 22 mJy and is halfway between the core and strong lobe seen in the SUMSS image. Figure 6.12(b) shows an AT20G-SuperCOSMOS radio optical overlay. This source is unresolved in all of the AT20G images, and the elongation seen at 4.8 and 8.6 GHz is due to an elliptical beam shape.

There is no counterpart to either of the SUMSS lobes in the AT20G catalog. This lack of emission could indicate that the lobes seen at 843 MHz are no longer being powered and the higher energy electron population has been depleted. A restarted radio galaxy would possess a young radio source which would explain the high frequency GPS nature of the core emission. A rest-frame spectral peak above 100 GHz is also consistent with a young or recently re-started radio source. The possible companion to the North-West of this object, as seen in Figure 6.12(b), is a likely merger candidate which is triggering the current phase of radio emission. With a linear scale of 2.77 kpc/arcsec the companion is at least 21kpc from the host galaxy, if it is at the same redshift. A spectrum of the possible companion would be very useful.

This source is a genuine GPS galaxy and is possibly a restarted radio galaxy.

Table 6.9 : Data summary for J010333-643907

Data Source	ν GHz	Flux Density mJy	Obs Year
Sadler et al. (2006)	4.8	173 ± 5	2003.92
AT20G	4.8	187 ± 9	2005.83
Sadler et al. (2006)	8.6	215 ± 9	2003.92
AT20G	8.6	253 ± 12	2005.83
Sadler et al. (2006)	18	200 ± 14	2003.83
Ricci et al. (2004)	18	290 ± 58	2002.83
AT20G	20	323 ± 16	2005.75
This paper	20	311 ± 21	2007.83

Figure 6.11 : The ESO NTT spectrum of AT20G J010333-643907. The emission features are wide and strong and include higher ionisation states of [NeIII] and [NeV]. The unlabeled emission feature at around 7300Å is [OI]. The very wide emission feature of H α is suppressed by atmospheric absorption by oxygen at 7630Å. This object is a redshift 0.163 emission line AGN.

Figure 6.12 : SuperCOSMOS Radio-Optical overlays for AT20G J010333-643907. **(a)** SUMSS contours in blue (33-150 mJy/beam in steps of 16 mJy/beam), PMN contours in black (300, 330 and 335 mJy/beam), AT20G 4.8 GHz in red (smaller contours, at 40, 80 and 160 mJy/beam), and 20 GHz in yellow (60 and 120 mJy/beam). The PMN flux includes contributions from both the core and both lobes, whilst the AT20G fluxes represent only the core flux. **(b)** Zoom of central region with AT20G contours only, contours as in (a) but with 8.6 GHz contours in blue at 80 and 160 mJy/beam. The elongated contours at 4.8 and 8.6 GHz are due to an elliptical beam shape.

6.8.6 AT20G J011102-474911 - a $z = 0.154$ GPS galaxy

This source is identified as a $B_J = 18.6$ mag galaxy in the SuperCOSMOS database. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 1.15$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.61$ mag which are consistent with a low redshift E or S0 type galaxy with excess blue emission from an AGN or star formation. The 2dFGRS spectrum of this source is shown in Figure 6.13 where strong emission in $H\alpha$, [OIII], and [OII] can be seen. These emission lines are typical of an emission-line AGN with a redshift of 0.154.

This source was not detected at 95 GHz and thus it is not clear where the spectrum turns over. It is possible that this source remains flat above 95 GHz as it does not require a steep 40 – 95 GHz spectral index to avoid detection.

In 2005 Sadler et al. (2008) observed this source twice at 95 GHz on consecutive days and found the flux to be <99 mJy and <64 mJy. Observations at 20 GHz within a few days of the 95 GHz observations show a flux density of 71 ± 4 mJy. The 95 GHz upper limits are consistent with the measurements of this paper, and the revised 20 GHz variability is still $<6\%$ over 3 years. The new observations strengthen the evidence that this source is not variable. The lack of variability is consistent with a genuine GPS source.

Figure 6.13 : 2dFGRS spectrum of AT20G J011102-474911 showing emission in $H\alpha$, [OIII], and [OII] and absorption of Na, Fe, Mg. The redshift is 0.154

6.8.7 AT20G J012714-481332 - possible GPS galaxy

This source has no optical counterpart in the SuperCOSMOS database. There is a galaxy 2.7 arcsec from the 20 GHz radio centroid as shown in Figure 6.14. The AT20G 4.8 and 8.6 GHz radio centroids are 2.5 and 2.6 arcsec distant from the galaxy so the association is uncertain. Further work is needed if this galaxy is to be accepted as the correct ID.

This source is present in the PMN catalog and was observed by Healey et al. (2007) and Sadler et al. (2008), as summarised in table 6.10. This source has varied by 17% at 4.85 GHz over 14 years. The 8.6 GHz flux density of Healey et al. (2007) has no quoted error, but assuming an uncertainty of up to 10%, this corresponds to a variability of 18% in just a year. When the measurements of Sadler et al. (2008) are taken into account the revised 20 GHz variability index becomes 11% over three years. The 95 GHz variability is <6% over two years.

The lack of an optical ID suggests that this source is a distant galaxy, however a spectral turnover of 89 GHz would suggest a nearby young galaxy. The low frequency variability is larger than normal for a GPS source, however the 20 and 95 GHz variability is consistent with a genuine GPS galaxy.

Table 6.10 : Data summary for J012714-481332

Data Source	ν GHz	Flux Density mJy	Obs Year
PMN	4.85	96 ± 10	1990
AT20G	4.8	140 ± 7	2004.83
Healey et al. (2007)	8.6	121.9	2005.99
AT20G	8.6	181 ± 9	2004.83
AT20G	20	237 ± 12	2004.75
Sadler et al. (2008)	20	200 ± 11	2005.5
This paper	20	174 ± 12	2007.83
Sadler et al. (2008)	95	251 ± 30	2005.5
Sadler et al. (2008)	95	232 ± 27	2005.5
This paper	95	187 ± 16	2007.83

Figure 6.14 : SuperCOSMOS blue image of J012714-481332 overlaid with AT20G radio contours at 4.8 GHz (red at 20, 40, and 80 mJy/beam), 8.6 GHz (blue at 40, 80, and 160 mJy/beam) and 20 GHz (black at 50, 100, and 200 mJy/beam). The separation between the radio and optical centroids (2.5, 2.6, and 2.7 arsec at 4.8, 8.6 and 20 GHz respectively) is too large for a confident ID to be made.

6.8.8 AT20G J012820-564939 - a $z = 0.066$ GPS galaxy

This source is identified as a $B_J = 16.5$ mag galaxy within the SuperCOSMOS database. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 0.85$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.81$ mag, which is consistent with a low redshift E or S0 galaxy with excess blue emission from an AGN or star formation. This source is in the sample of Radio-Excess IRAS Galaxies (REIG) by Drake et al. (2003) who measure a redshift of 0.066 but do not show a spectrum.

This source is in the PMN catalog and was also observed at 4.79 and 8.6 GHz by Drake et al. (2003) as is summarised in table 6.11. There is no detectable variability at 4.8 GHz but there is a change of 17% at 8.6 and 20 GHz over two years. The variability is not so high as to exclude a GPS classification of this source.

Table 6.11 : Data summary for J012820-564939

Data Source	ν GHz	Flux Density mJy	Obs Year
Drake et al. (2003)	4.79	121.0 ± 1.2	2003?
PMN	4.85	141 ± 11	1990
AT20G	4.8	130 ± 7	2005.83
Drake et al. (2003)	8.6	199.3 ± 1.7	2003?
AT20G	8.6	141 ± 7	2005.83
AT20G	20	189 ± 10	2005.75
This paper	20	131 ± 9	2007.83

6.8.9 AT20G J180859-832526 - a $z \sim 0.5$ GPS galaxy

This source is identified as a $B_J = 21.6$ mag galaxy within the SuperCOSMOS database. Although it is not the faintest source in the sample it does not have any measured R_F or I_C magnitudes so no determination of colour can be made. The redshift of this source has been estimated to be $z \sim 0.5$.

This source was observed in the AT20G survey in 2005 at 95 ± 5 mJy and again in 2006 at 95 ± 5 mJy giving a revised variability of $< 6\%$ over 2 years. The radio spectrum of this source has an optically thick fitted spectral index of $\alpha = +0.16$, which takes it outside of the original $\alpha > +0.2$ spectral index selection cutoff. There is nothing to exclude this source from being a genuine GPS source.

6.8.10 AT20G J181225-712006 - a $z = 0.199$ GPS galaxy, possibly interacting

A SuperCOSMOS blue image of this object is indicative of a $B_J = 18.4$ mag edge-on spiral galaxy and is identified as such within the catalog. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 1.65$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.51$ mag, which is consistent with a low redshift E or S0 galaxy.

The acquisition images that were taken during the ESO NTT observations show a more complex morphology. As is shown in Figure 6.15 there are three components to this object. As the three components are aligned linearly, it was possible to include each of them in the slit of the spectrograph and obtain separate spectra. The spectra are shown in Figure 6.16(a)-(c). Only absorption features are present and the average redshift is 0.199. An angular separation of approximately 2.5 arcsec at this redshift corresponds to a projected linear separation of 8.1 kpc between the central and outer components which, given the common distance to each, indicates that they are not only nearby to each other, but are probably interacting. With a redshift of $z = 0.199$, the optical colours suggest that there is some AGN or star formation activity which could be due to a recent interaction.

A radio optical overlay of this source is shown in Figure 6.15. In each of the 5, 8, and 20 GHz observations from the AT20G the radio emission is seen to be coincident with the faintest and most diffuse of the three components (C in fig. 6.15). If we are witnessing the merger of two galaxies then it is tempting to suggest that the radio emission is the result of the merger process, however if this were the case then the central, brighter, galaxy would normally be expected to host the AGN. This source is present within the 2 Micron All Sky Extended source catalog (2MASX Jarrett et al., 2000) but little else is known about this object.

Figure 6.15 : The source AT20G J181225-712006 with radio contours overlaid on an NTT optical R band image. Three optical galaxies are identified in the NTT acquisition image, with radio contours from the AT20G overlaid. Red contours are 20 GHz at 5, 10, 20 and 40 mJy/beam. The yellow and blue contours are 4.8 and 8.6 GHz respectively and are both at 30 mJy/beam.

Figure 6.16 : Spectra of the three components of AT20G J181225-712006. In each case Ca - K, -H, Mg and Na are seen in absorption giving an average redshift of 0.199. The apparent absorption lines near the H α and [SII] lines in the lower two plots are the result of cosmic rays in the subtracted sky template. The unidentified absorption line near 7630Å is atmospheric oxygen.

6.8.11 AT20G J181857-550815 - a $z = 0.073$ GPS galaxy

This source is identified as a $B_J = 15.9$ mag galaxy within the SuperCOSMOS database. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 0.95$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.81$ mag which is consistent with a low redshift E or S0 galaxy, with excess blue emission due to AGN or star forming activity. The 6dFGS spectrum of this galaxy is shown in Figure 6.17(a), and shows stellar absorption lines typical of early-type galaxies but no obvious optical emission lines. The redshift is 0.073.

This source was observed in 2008 with e-VLBI resolution at 4.8 GHz (Hancock et al., 2009). This source is likely a restarted radio galaxy with an inverted core. Figure 6.17 shows SUMSS, AT20G, and PMN radio contours on a SuperCOSMOS blue image. The 4.8 GHz image from the AT20G shows significant emission that is consistent with a hot spot within the brighter of the SUMSS radio lobes (marked B in Figure 6.17). The PMN flux is higher than that measured by the AT20G, Hancock et al. (2009), or this paper, which is likely due to contributions from both the core and lobe. At a redshift of 0.073 the linear scale of the 4.8 GHz jet is 1.3 kpc/arcsec. The separation between the core and jet is then 79 kpc. The projected linear size of the SUMSS lobes is ~ 110 kpc. The lack of 20 GHz emission from the lobe suggests that they may no longer be being powered and could be a remnant of previous activity.

The core shows no significant variability at 4.8 GHz, and is 14% variable at 20 GHz over one year. The radio spectrum of this source indicates that the spectral turnover is ~ 95 GHz or higher which is consistent with a young radio source which has recently become active. This source shows many of the characteristics of a genuine GPS source, despite the fact that the spectral turnover is yet to be observed.

Figure 6.17 : AT20G J181857-550815. **(a)** 6dFGS spectrum showing Na D, and the G-band in absorption and a strong H-K break. The redshift is 0.073. **(b)** SuperCOSMOS blue image overlaid with PMN 4.85 GHz in blue at 201 and 206 mJy/beam, AT20G 4.8 GHz in red at 25, 30, and 35 mJy/beam, AT20G 20 GHz in yellow at 16, 32, and 64 mJy/beam, and SUMSS 843 MHz in green at 40, 80 160, and 320 mJy/beam. The radio and optical identifications are at the core component marked A. The PMN source is offset by 24 arcsec and is at the center of the blue contours. The extended feature seen in the red contours at position B is the faint jet. The SUMSS contours are consistent with component A being the host galaxy, and component B being the jet.

6.8.12 AT20G J203540-694407 - a $z = 0.875$ QSO

This source is identified as being star like within the SuperCOSMOS database and has $B_J = 17.2$ mag. The optical counterpart is 2.9 arcsec distant from the 20 GHz radio contours, however the association is accepted based on the 4.8 and 8.6 GHz positions being within 2.5 arcsec as depicted in Figure 6.18(b). The optical colours are $B-R_C = 0.95$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.31$ mag, which is much bluer than expected for a normal E or S0 galaxy at the measured redshift of 0.875. An optical spectrum of this source is shown in Figure 6.18(a). The spectrum rises towards the blue and exhibits strong MgII emission, both of which are typical of quasars.

This source is in the PMN catalog with a 4.85 GHz flux of 99 ± 8 mJy, giving a variability index of 30% over 15 years, when compared to the AT20G flux. Healey et al. (2007) observed this source in 2005 with a 8.6 GHz flux of 189.5 mJy 14 arcsec away from the AT20G position. The 8.6 GHz data has no quoted uncertainty, but assuming an uncertainty as large as 10%, the variability is 8% over 2 years. The large amount of variability at and above the spectral peak (5 GHz) is an indication that this is not a genuine GPS source. Healey et al. (2008) identify this source as having associated gamma-ray emission but with a Figure of merit of 0.071 suggesting that the association is uncertain. This source is a quasar and not a genuine GPS galaxy.

Figure 6.18 : (a) SSO 2.3m spectrum of J203540-694407. Flux units are arbitrary. MgII is seen in emission. The redshift is 0.875. The spectrum rises towards the blue which indicates that we are seeing a quasar. The wide absorption feature at 7630\AA is atmospheric absorption from oxygen. (b) SuperCOSMOS blue image of AT20G J203540-694407 overlaid with AT20G radio contours at 4.8 GHz (red at 40, 80, and 160 mJy/beam), 8.6 GHz (blue at 50, 100, and 200 mJy/beam), and 20 GHz (black at 35, 70, and 140 mJy/beam). The elongation in the 4.8 and 8.6 GHz contours is due to an elliptical beam shape.

6.8.13 AT20G J203958-720655 - a $z = 1.0$ QSO

This source is identified as being star like within the SuperCOSMOS database and has $B_J = 17.1$ mag. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 0.55$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.41$ mag which is much bluer than even the low redshift normal E or S0 galaxies. The optical spectrum is shown in Figure 6.19 where a rising blue spectrum and strong MgII emission lines are indicative of a QSO at a redshift of 1.0.

This source is in the PMN catalog with a 4.85 GHz flux of 122 ± 9 mJy. This source is unresolved in all AT20G radio images. This source shows significant variability at both 4.8 GHz (20% over 15 years) and 20 GHz (9.7% over 2 years). This source is most likely a quasar and not related to the genuine GPS sources.

Figure 6.19 : SSO 2.3m spectrum of J203958-720655. Flux units are arbitrary. MgII is seen in emission and FeII, H, and K are seen in absorption. The redshift is $z=1.00$. The spectrum rises towards the blue which indicates that we are seeing a quasar. The wide absorption feature at 7630\AA is atmospheric absorption from oxygen.

6.8.14 AT20G J205503-635207 - a $z \sim 0.3$ GPS galaxy

This source is identified as being star like within the SuperCOSMOS database and has $B_J = 20.2$ mag. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 1.25$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.81$ mag, which is close to that expected for a low redshift, normal E or S0 galaxy. The estimated redshift is ~ 0.3 , which suggests an excess of blue emission.

This source is not in any of the on-line databases accessible via NED or VizieR. The 20 GHz variability is less than 6% over a year and is unresolved at all frequencies within the AT20G. There is not enough data to rule out this source as a GPS candidate.

6.8.15 AT20G J212222-560014 - a $z = 0.0518$ GPS galaxy in a cluster

This source is identified as a $B_J = 16.1$ mag galaxy within the SuperCOSMOS database. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 1.15$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.71$ mag, which is only slightly more blue than a low redshift normal E or S0 galaxy. The 6dF spectrum depicted in Figure 6.20(a) shows a redshift of 0.0518, making this the nearest object within this sample. This galaxy is part of a galaxy cluster of at least 5 members. The optical ID is labeled as ‘C’ in Figure 6.20(b).

The radio spectrum of this source remains inverted at 95 GHz, although the upper limit on the 95 GHz flux suggests that it may be beginning to turn over.

This source shows no significant variability at 20 GHz.

The 73 ± 9 mJy source PMN J2122-5600 is located 1.17 arcmin to the east of J212222-560014 and is considered by Healey et al. (2007) to be associated. This association then includes J212222-560014 within the CRATES catalog of flat spectrum radio sources.

Figure 6.20(b) shows the SuperCOSMOS blue survey image overlaid with AT20G 4.8 and 20 GHz, PMN 4.85 GHz, and SUMSS 843 MHz contours. The offset between the AT20G and PMN contours is large but still within the astrometric uncertainties of the PMN survey. The AT20G flux is clearly coming from the optical galaxy. The PMN flux does not have a clear origin but the presence of the extended SUMSS emission and some low level extended flux in the AT20G image suggests that there is some diffuse low-frequency emission present. The fact that there is more PMN flux than AT20G flux (73 ± 9 vs 28 ± 2 mJy at 4.8 GHz) is consistent with the idea that there is diffuse emission being generated by the galaxy cluster as well as more compact emission from the galaxy itself. It is also possible that this is a head-tail source within a cluster. There is no reason to exclude this source from being a genuine GPS galaxy.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6.20 : AT20G J212222-560014. (a) 6dF spectrum showing emission in $H\alpha$ and SII, and absorption in K, H, Na, and Mg. The redshift is 0.0518. (b) SuperCOSMOS blue image overlaid with radio contours. Contours are: Blue - PMN 4.8 GHz at 50 and 60 mJy/beam, Red - AT20G 4.8 GHz at 15 and 25 mJy/beam, Green - SUMSS 843 MHz at 10, 20, and 40 mJy/beam, and Yellow - AT20G 20 GHz at 20 mJy/beam. Identified objects are: A - APMUKS(BJ) B211848.98-561327.1, B - 2MASX J21222482-5600243, C - 2MASX J21222292-5600143 (also AT20G ID), D - APMUKS(BJ) B211842.26-561333.0, E - APMUKS(BJ) B211841.42-561410.4.

6.8.16 AT20G J212402-602808 - a possible QSO

This source is identified as being star like within the SuperCOSMOS database and has $B_J = 17.3$ mag. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 0.45$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.51$ mag, and the estimated redshift is ~ 1 , which indicates that there is excess blue emission due to an AGN or star formation. This source is visible at UV wavelengths and is considered by Agüeros et al. (2005) to be a candidate QSO.

The observation of the 4.8 and 8.6 GHz fluxes were carried out almost a year after the 20 GHz flux observations, which makes them almost simultaneous with the 2007 observations of this paper. A 20 GHz variability of 20% over a year is almost double the amount expected from a genuine GPS source.

Given the spectral variability, and the UV detection it is likely that this source is a quasar and not a genuine GPS galaxy.

6.8.17 AT20G J213622-633551 - a possible QSO

This source is identified as being star like within the SuperCOSMOS database and has $B_J = 19.8$ mag. This source was not detected in I_C so no determination of optical colours can be made.

This object was observed multiple times at multiple frequencies over the course of the AT20G pilot and survey. A summary of the observations is given in table 6.12. Figure 6.21 plots each of the observations. The 2003 and 2005 observations (green and pink in the Figure) show some variability in total flux but not in spectral shape. Using the 20 GHz data from 2004-2007 as well as the 18 GHz flux from 2003 corrected with a spectral index of $\alpha = +0.38$ gives a revised variability index of 17% over four years. The 4.8 GHz variability is 20% over 15 years. The amount of variability is not unheard of in genuine GPS samples, however this object is likely a quasar and not a genuine GPS galaxy.

Table 6.12 : Data summary for J213622-633551

Data Source	ν GHz	Flux Density mJy	Obs Year
PMN	4.85	395 ± 22	1990
Sadler et al. (2006)	4.8	144 ± 3	2003.92
AT20G	4.8	198 ± 10	2005.83
Sadler et al. (2006)	8.6	180 ± 4	2003.92
AT20G	8.6	281 ± 14	2005.83
Sadler et al. (2006)	18	238 ± 17	2003.83
AT20G	20	411 ± 21	2004.75
AT20G	20	358 ± 18	2005.75
AT20G	20	332 ± 16	2006.75
This paper	20	372 ± 25	2007.83
This paper	40	354 ± 7	2007.83
This paper	95	224 ± 19	2007.83

Figure 6.21 : Radio spectrum of J213622-633551 with data from the multiple AT20G observations and PMN catalog included. Despite the 17% variability seen at 20 GHz, the shape of the spectrum has not changed between 2003 and 2005.

6.8.18 AT20G J214447-694654 - a $z \sim 0.5$ GPS galaxy

This source is identified as being star like within the SuperCOSMOS database and has $B_J = 21.4$ mag. This source was not detected in I_C so no determination of optical colours can be made. The redshift for this source is estimated as ~ 0.5 . This source does not appear within in NED or VizieR in any catalog aside from SUMSS. There is a PMN source ~ 20 arcsec from this source with a flux of 30 ± 7 mJy but there is more than one possible optical ID for the PMN source so the association is uncertain. The lack of an optical counterpart suggests that this source is a faint or distant galaxy, however a radio spectral peak of 82 GHz would put a young radio source at low redshift. There is nothing to suggest that this source is not a genuine GPS source.

6.8.19 AT20G J230737-354828 - a variable radio galaxy or candidate QSO

This source is identified as being a $B_J = 20.9$ mag galaxy within the SuperCOSMOS database. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 0.95$ mag and $R_C-I_C = -0.09$ mag, which are possibly affected by variability (see below). The redshift of this source is estimated to be ~ 1 , indicating that there is a large excess of blue emission. No optical spectrum is available for this source.

Flesch & Hardcastle (2004) identify this source as having associated X-ray emission and as likely being a quasar.

Table 6.13 shows the observations that have been made over the course of the AT20G survey and related projects. Figure 6.22 shows the radio spectrum with all the listed data included. The 36% variability at 20 GHz measured in this paper is supported by the 2006 observations of Sadler et al. (2008) which were on consecutive days. The observations of the AT20G and of this paper both show convex, GPS like spectra, but with peaks at different frequencies and with different flux densities. If this amount of variability extends to the optical then the optical colours could be contaminated as the observation of the B-R-I magnitudes were separated by as much as 20 years. The large amount of variability in both total flux and spectral shape make it likely that this source is a quasar and not a genuine GPS galaxy.

Table 6.13 : Data summary for J230737-354828

Data Source	ν GHz	Flux Density mJy	Obs Year
AT20G	4.8	112 ± 7	2004.83
AT20G	8.6	186 ± 9	2004.83
AT20G	18	190 ± 9	2004.75
Sadler et al. (2008)	20	118 ± 3	2006.79
Sadler et al. (2008)	20	190 ± 3	2006.79
This paper	20	88 ± 6	2007.83
This paper	40	110 ± 2	2007.83
Sadler et al. (2008)	95	106 ± 11	2006.79
This paper	95	98 ± 8	2007.83

Figure 6.22 : Radio spectrum of J230737-354828 incorporating the data from the AT20G, Sadler et al. (2008), and this paper.

6.8.20 AT20G J233159-381147 - a $z = 1.2$ QSO

This source is a well known quasar identified as early as 1971 (Shimmins et al., 1971) and is identified as such in the SuperCOSMOS database. The source has $B_J = 17.3$ mag. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 0.55$ mag and $R_C-I_C = 0.51$ mag, and the measured redshift is 1.20.

Wright (1984) use a variability measure similar to that of this paper to calculate a variability of 1% for this source at 2.7 GHz and 19% variability at 4.8 GHz over the period 1970-1979. More recent measurements by the PMN, and AT20G show a 5 GHz variability index of <6% over 15 years and the 20 GHz observations of the AT20G and this paper puts the variability at <6% over a period of 3 years. It is likely that this quasar has long periods of quiescence with short periods of flare activity.

This quasar has been detected in polarized flux both at 8.6 GHz (9.7% Simard-Normandie et al., 1981) and in optical V (0.44% Lamy & Hutsemékers, 2000). Wolter & Celotti (2001) detect a 0.3-3.5 keV X-ray flux of $1.5 \times 10^{-13} \text{erg cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. VLBI observations of this source at 2.3 and 8.4 GHz were used to define the International Celestial Reference Frame (Johnston et al., 1995; Ma et al., 1998).

6.8.21 AT20G J234743-494627 - a $z = 0.643$ QSO

This source is identified as being star like in the SuperCOSMOS database and has $B_J = 19.8$ mag. The optical colours are $B-R_C = 1.65$ mag and $R_C-I_C = -0.81$ mag. Healey et al. (2008) identify this source as a flat spectrum radio quasar at a redshift of 0.643.

Healey et al. (2008) measure a 8.6 GHz flux of 344 mJy. It is within the PMN catalog with a 4.85 GHz flux of 367 ± 20 mJy. The variability at 4.85 and 8.6 GHz is 26% and 13% respectively (assuming 10% uncertainty at 8.6 GHz), and 16% at 20 GHz. This level of variability at three frequencies is enough to bring the shape of the spectrum from being peaked to being flat. The identification of this source as FSRQ is not altered by the addition of new observations.

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Chapter 7

Summary and conclusion

My PhD project is comprised of two separate but related components. The first component of my thesis is the work related to the scanning observations of the Australia Telescope 20 GHz (AT20G) survey. I was able to make substantial improvements to the calibration, data reduction and eventual source detection process for the AT20G. A new suite of programs was developed to make better use of the scanning redundancy and increase the accuracy and efficiency with which candidate sources lists were produced. Over the period of my PhD candidature I played a major part in the development and implementation of the data reduction and calibration schemes that eventually led to a larger and more sensitive catalog that complements the AT20G main survey catalog. The scanning survey catalog has been instrumental in the measurement of completeness of the main AT20G catalog and has identified 16 strong ($S > 0.5$ Jy) sources that are missing from the AT20G catalog.

The AT20G catalog has been used to identify a sample of 656 high frequency GPS candidates with spectral turnovers above 5 GHz. A simple estimate, based only on SuperCOSMOS class IDs, suggests that as many as 104 of the 656 sources are identified with galaxies which, if confirmed by further investigation, would more than double the total number of GPS galaxies known. The sample of GPS sources defined is also at a lower redshift (~ 0.2) than previous samples which indicates that we may soon be able to construct a local luminosity function for GPS sources without needing to rely on estimates from non-GPS populations.

Further investigation has been carried out on two subsets of the 656 GPS candidates. Firstly, a sample of 10 low redshift ($z < 0.15$) galaxies were selected for e-VLBI observations. The high resolution images showed no signs of any extended or complex morphology in any of the target sources, resulting in largest linear sizes of between 15 and 250 pc which suggests that the sources are typically less than ~ 3000 years old. Some evidence was found to suggest that the core and total radio power of GPS sources are related, as is the case for the larger and more powerful radio galaxies that they are thought to evolve into.

A second subset of 21 sources with high peaking or inverted radio spectra was observed at 40 and 95 GHz in order to identify GPS sources with peaks near or above 20 GHz as this group of sources has not been previously well studied due to their small number. Of the 21 sources only 9 were considered not to be genuine GPS sources with the remaining 12 (57%) being consistent with the observed properties of GPS sources. Three (15%) of the GPS sources showed evidence

of previous activity suggesting that restarted radio sources play a significant role in the evolution of GPS sources. If these numbers are indicative of the larger population of radio sources then as many as 400 genuine GPS sources could be contained within the AT20G with 100 of them being restarted radio galaxies.

This work has significantly increased the number of known GPS and High Frequency Peaking (HFP) sources, showing that there are many exciting possibilities for surveys such as the AT20G. Future studies of GPS and HFP sources will find the AT20G to be a rich resource and will benefit from multi-frequency observations, and a larger redshift coverage.